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T I T R E

**A sharpened close-up of R136 and NGC3603:
unshrouding the nature of their stellar population**

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In memory of

Olivier

Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to understand the different aspects of the dynamical and stellar evolution of very massive clusters. These newly formed massive clusters are the most important link between the formation of the massive star clusters and their evolution. We chose two young massive clusters, located in the most massive Galactic/extra-Galactic HII regions, NGC3603 and R136 which hosts the most massive stars in the local universe.

This thesis contains the photometric analysis of the core of R136 and NGC3603 using the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) data in the visible and the Very Large Telescope (VLT/SPHERE) in the infrared. Thanks to SPHERE extreme AO system, I detected many faint low-mass stars for the first time in the core of both clusters in the vicinity of massive bright objects. Comparing the results of the HST and SPHERE photometry analysis, NGC3603 shows no signature of mass segregation in its core for two main reasons: First, the MF slope in the very core is not flatter than the next radial bin. Second, both slopes are similar to the MF values found in previous works for the outer regions. R136 is partially resolved in SPHERE/IRDIS data. The majority (above 90%) of massive stars (brighter than 17 mag in K and 16 mag in J) have visual companions closer than $0.2''$. Among them, R136a1 and R136c have visual companions detected for the first time. R136a3 is resolved as two stars (PSF fitting). Considering the spectroscopic and photometric errors on the extinction ($A_J = 0.45 \pm 0.5$ and $A_K = 0.2 \pm 0.5$) and the age ($1.8_{-0.8}^{+1.2}$ Myr) of the cluster members, we estimate a mass range for each detected star. The generalized histogram of stellar masses (MF) was plotted at different ages with given errors on each stellar mass. We created series of simulated images of R136 from the output of Nbody6 code, to be compared with the HST/WFPC2 data of R136. These numerical simulations are done in order to check the effect of initial binarities, mass segregation and stellar evolution on the dynamical evolution of R136-like clusters at the early stages of their life (4 Myr).

The analysis of the bright stellar population (spectroscopic and photometry), shows that we need more resolution to go further on studying R136 which is 7-8 times further than NGC3603. The spectroscopic analysis find very massive stars in the core of R136 where, for some of them SPHERE data has resolved them visually.

Future instruments with higher angular resolution (milliarcsec) like E-ELT (MICADO), JWST and VLTI/GRAVITY can resolve the compact core of R136 and similar objects at further distances. The kinematics of the core of these compact clusters can be studied by using astrometric analysis with $\mu arcsec$ accuracy with GRAVITY in near future.

Keywords: Star clusters: individual (R136, NGC3603)- Stars: imaging- Stars: luminosity function, mass function- Stars: massive- Stars: pre-main sequence- Instrumen-

tation: high angular resolution- Methods: numerical- Methods: observational

Résumé

Cette thèse a pour objectif de comprendre les différents aspects de l'évolution des amas d'étoiles massives NGC3603 et R136 qui possèdent les étoiles les plus massives connues de l'univers local. L'analyse photométrique des noyaux de R136 et NGC3603 utilisant l'imagerie infrarouge de l'instrument SPHERE sur VLT et son système d'optique adaptative extrême de SPHERE, m'a permis de détecter pour la première fois un grand nombre d'étoiles de faible masse et luminosité au coeur de ces amas et pour la plupart au voisinage des étoiles les plus lumineuses et massives. La comparaison des données de SPHERE de NGC3603 à celles du HST montre l'absence de ségrégation de masse dans le noyau de cet amas. De plus la pente de la fonction de masse de cette région est la même que celle de la région suivante et similaire aux valeurs de la MF correspondant aux régions extérieures de l'amas connues jusqu'ici. L'amas R136 est partiellement résolu par SPHERE/IRDIS dans l'IR. La majorité de ses étoiles massives ont des compagnons visuels. En prenant compte des mesures spectroscopiques et photométriques et leurs erreurs sur l'extinction et l'âge des membres de l'amas, j'ai estimé une gamme de masses pour chaque étoile identifiée. La MF a été calculée pour différents âges ainsi que les erreurs sur les masses stellaires. J'ai simulé des séries d'images de R136 grâce au code Nbody6, et les ai comparées aux observations du HST/WFPC2. Ces simulations permettent de vérifier l'effet de la binarité initiale des étoiles de l'amas, la ségrégation de masse et l'évolution des étoiles sur l'évolution dynamique propre à R136. Ces analyses démontrent l'importance d'une résolution angulaire encore plus fine pour mieux comprendre la nature physique de R136, qui se trouve à une distance 7-8 fois plus loin que NGC3603. Les études spectroscopiques ont trouvé des étoiles super massives dans le noyau de R136, alors que notre présent travail avec SPHERE résoud clairement certaines d'entre elles comme multiples visuelles.

Mots-clés: Les amas stellaires: individuel (R136, NGC3603) - Etoiles: étoiles massives - Imagerie: fonction de masse-luminosité, fonction de masse - Etoiles : préséquence principale Etoiles : séquence principale - Instrumentation: haute résolution angulaire Méthodes: numérique Méthodes : observationnelle

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Formation of Star Clusters

Interstellar medium (ISM) is a space between the stars, filled by gas, dust and cosmic rays. According to the temperature and density of the ISM, it can have different phases. It can be very hot ($T > 10^6$ K) ionized gas with very low density (10^4 atoms/m³) or very cold (~ 10 K) and dense (10^{12} atoms/m³). The latter case is known as molecular clouds. The giant molecular clouds (GMCs) can reach to a total mass of a few million solar-masses, extending a few parsecs. If the molecular cloud becomes gravitationally unstable, when its internal pressure is insufficient to support gravity, it collapses and forms stars [Ward-Thompson & Whitworth (2011)]. This gravitational instability in the cloud happens 1) due to a random statistical fluctuation in the medium, leading to produce some dense self-gravity cores (Jeans instability) or 2) due to any external mechanisms that compress a molecular cloud and initiate its gravitational collapse, like collision of the molecular clouds or the external pressure of the nearby supernova explosion.

Newly-formed hot stars ionize the gas embedded within the cluster and make the whole HII region being observable in visible wavelengths (H_{α} emission).

Most stars form embedded in clusters [Lada & Lada (2003)]. Observations of the galactic embedded clusters show the signature of infant mortality as the formation rate of star clusters is much less than the formation rate of embedded star clusters [Lada & Lada (2003)]. Only about 10% of galactic embedded clusters survive longer than 10 Myr [Lada & Lada (2003)]. Destructive feedbacks from massive star formation, gas removal phase or high degree of initial mass segregation are some of the scenarios which are proposed to explain the high galactic infant mortality of star clusters.

On one side, one tries to understand the evolution of the newly formed stellar clusters and their survival from infant mortality. On the other hand, one needs to know the star formation process (specially of massive stars) within the clusters and its feedback on the evolution of the cluster. Young stellar clusters are unique objects to provide a clue on the formation and evolution of the clusters at the very early stages of their lives. In this thesis we focus on two young massive star clusters: R136 in the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) and NGC3603 in the Carina arm of our Galaxy. These two clusters are located in the largest HII regions in LMC and in Milky Way (MW), hosting very massive stars (VMSs). They provide a rare opportunity to study the formation of massive stars and their feedback on the cluster formation and evolution. The young age of the clusters opens another door to the astronomers to check the stellar masses produced by molecular clouds and their initial distribution. One can check if the Initial Mass Function (IMF) has a universal shape in MW and LMC.

It is also possible to check if massive stars tend to be formed deeper in the center of the cloud (primordial mass segregation). Mass segregation is observed in most of the globular clusters which can be explained by the dynamical evolution of gravitationally bound systems. During the close encounters, the energy and momentum are exchanged between the stellar members. According to the principle of equipartition of kinetic energy, there is an statistical tendency for stars to equalize their kinetic energies during encounters. So after a given time, called relaxation time, the kinetic

energy of the stars is roughly equalized. The kinetic energy is proportional to the mass and the square velocity. Therefore the low-mass-stars will have higher velocities and go further from the center of the cluster and the high-mass-stars will have lower velocities and sink into orbits closer to the center of the cluster (dynamical mass segregation).

In the case of young massive clusters (YMCs), if segregation exists, its origin is most likely primordial as the cluster is younger than the time needed for dynamical segregation. Primordial segregation provides additional information on the formation of the stellar clusters and massive stars.

Objects, such as R136 and NGC303, enable us to investigate these questions. But the main problem remains in the interpretation of observations and the models that we need to use for understanding the whole process. How much can we improve our telescopes and their tools to have better angular resolution to get a clear and sharp image/spectra of these clusters? How much additional physics can we put in our models to get closer to the explanation of the mechanisms that govern the nature of these clusters and their stellar populations?

1.2 Evolution of Star Clusters

After the formation of stars within the cluster, dynamical evolution begins. The dynamical evolution can be characterized by two important time-scales:

1) Dynamical timescale (T_{dyn}) which is the time required for a typical star to cross the system. The dynamic (crossing) time may be defined as the characteristic radius of the cluster divided by the mean velocity of stars with respect to the cluster center (Eq. 1.1).

$$T_{dyn}[Myr] = \frac{r_h [pc]}{\bar{v} [km/s]} \quad (1.1)$$

If the cluster is in Virial equilibrium, then:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{v}^2 &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{GM}{r_h} \\ T_{dyn}[Myr] &= 21 \times \frac{(r_h [pc])^{3/2}}{(M[M_\odot])^{1/2}}\end{aligned}\quad (1.2)$$

2) Two-body relaxation timescale (T_{rh}) which is the timescale on which two-body encounters transfer energy between individual stars and cause the system to establish thermal equilibrium [Portegies Zwart et al. (2010)]. If a stellar system consist of N stars of average mass m per star, the local T_{rh} is (Spitzer 1987):

$$\begin{aligned}T_{rh} &= 0.138 \frac{N^{1/2} r_h^{3/2}}{G^{1/2} m^{1/2} \ln \Lambda} \\ T_{rh} &\approx \frac{N}{7 \ln \Lambda} T_{dyn}\end{aligned}\quad (1.3)$$

For systems where all stars have the same mass $\Lambda \sim 0.11 N$ [Giersz & Heggie (1994)].

In the dense collisional stellar systems, like globular star clusters, T_{rh} is comparable to the cluster's lifetime. In more dilute systems the relaxation could take longer than the age of the universe. These are called collisionless stellar systems.

The star cluster lifetime is proportional to their T_{rh} and T_{dyn} . Also speed of the star cluster's evolution has a relation with the inverse T_{rh} .

For any stellar system, knowing its fundamental parameters (Age, total mass and characteristic radius), one can estimate these two important time-scales (T_{rh} and T_{dyn}), in order to better understand the evolution and survival of the system. If the T_{dyn} is shorter than the age of stellar system, then the system is gravitationally bound.

Table 1.1 compares the fundamental parameters and two dynamical time-scales of clusters in three different classes. These clusters are categorized according to their age, density and total mass. Globular clusters (GC) are old (age > 10 Gyr), massive ($M > 10^5 M_\odot$) and dense aggregate of stars.

Table 1.1 Categorization of star clusters according to their fundamental parameters (Table 1 in Portegies Zwart et al. 2010).

Cluster	Age [Gyr]	M [M_{\odot}]	ρ_c [M_{\odot}/pc^{-3}]	T_{dyn} [Myr]	T_{rh} [Myr]
OC	$\lesssim 0.3$	$\lesssim 10^3$	$\lesssim 10^3$	~ 1	$\lesssim 100$
GC	$\gtrsim 10$	$\gtrsim 10^5$	$\gtrsim 10^3$	$\gtrsim 1$	$\gtrsim 1000$
YMC	$\lesssim 0.1$	$\gtrsim 10^4$	$\gtrsim 10^3$	$\lesssim 1$	$\lesssim 100$

In contrast, Open clusters (OC) are young (age < 0.3 Gyr) with lower total mass ($M < 10^3 M_{\odot}$) and less density. YMCs, are younger than Open clusters but with comparable total mass and density of Globular clusters.

The evolution and survival of these stellar systems depends on several internal and external parameters: Dynamical interaction between the stellar masses and also between the star cluster itself with its host galaxy (tidal force); Distribution of stellar masses and its variation within time and space; Stellar evolution of stars and mass-loss from evolving stars; Formation and evolution of binary stars; Embedded gas potential and the interaction between stars and the gas within the cluster.

Note that the potential energy of YMCs is dominated by gas (embedded). The gas is removed within a few Myr by the feedback from massive stars (e.g. stellar winds and supernovae). Consequently, the cluster expands as the cluster's potential changes significantly. This expansion depends on how fast is the gas removal phase. R136 and NGC3603, host many massive stars which affects the evolution of these clusters in the early phases of their life.

1.3 Massive stars within clusters

Usually stars with masses higher than $8M_{\odot}$ during their main sequence lifetime, are considered as massive stars. They have short main sequence phase, go beyond carbon-burning phase and

produce elements heavier than Oxygen. They can end up as a blue (O,B and A-type), yellow (F and G type) or red (K and M-type) supergiant or as a Wolf-Rayet (WR) stars and luminous blue variables (LBV) with gigantic outbursts.

Massive stars have a fundamental influence on the ISM and galactic evolution for three main reasons:

- 1) They enrich their environment by producing heavy elements in their core and ejecting them in their surroundings via strong winds and when they explode as core collapse supernovae (CC-SNe).

- 2) Their powerful stellar winds inject mechanical energy into the ISM.

- 3) Because of their high effective temperature ($T_{eff} > 25000K$ on the main sequence), they are the principal source of ionizing flux which creates HII regions.

An important question is what is the upper-mass limit for the stars? The clue to tackle this question relies on young massive clusters!

Studying massive stars is not easy due to two main reasons:

- 1) Observationally, we are limited to the angular resolution of the telescopes. During the last decades the observational techniques developed using space telescopes, adaptive optics (AO) for the large ground-based telescopes (see section 1.7.1), interferometry and image analysis methods (like deconvolution). As the angular resolution improved, several very massive stars were found to be in fact multiple objects.

For example, HDE 268743 was listed as a blue supergiant in LMC, more massive than $100M_{\odot}$ [Humphreys (1983)] but later using deconvolution method, it was decomposed into 6 components [Heydari-Malayeri et al. (1988)] and later using AO observation this system revealed to be 12 stars, where the most massive one was about $50M_{\odot}$.

The mass of the brightest component of the most massive young star cluster in SMC, NGC346-1, was estimated to be about $113M_{\odot}$ [Kudritzki et al. (1989)]. But later, using deconvolution

method this object was found to be a $58M_{\odot}$ star with two other components [Heydari-Malayeri & Hutsemekers (1991)].

R136a, the brightest component of the massive cluster in LMC was claimed to be a $1000M_{\odot}$ star [Feitzinger et al. (1980)]. In 1985 Weigelt & Baier, could resolve it to eight components (R136a1 to a8) using speckle interferometry with a $0.09''$ resolution. Later on, the new data from Hubble space telescope (HST) and ground observations using AO on very large telescopes (VLT), more stars could be detected in the core of R136 [Hunter et al. (1995), Campbell et al. (2010)].

2) The other uncertainty relies on the models (stellar interiors and atmosphere) to estimate the stellar mass. Pistol is a late type massive star (probably an LBV). Using IR spectroscopy, its T_{eff} was estimated to be about $14 - 20kK$ leading to have $L \sim (0.4 - 1.5) 10^7 L_{\odot}$ and $M \sim 200 - 250M_{\odot}$ [Figer et al. (1998)]. But later, in 2009, using modern atmosphere models $T_{eff} \sim 11.8kK$ and $L \sim 1.6 10^6 L_{\odot}$ leading to $M \sim 100M_{\odot}$ [Najarro et al. (2009)].¹

1.3.1 Formation of massive stars

Very massive stars can be formed via direct gas accretion and by collision between the lower-mass stars. Krumholz (2015) presents in detail the formation of very massive stars which is not basically different from the common massive-star-formation. It seems that the formation of very massive stars can be treated in a context of the formation of upper end of the IMF. Fragmentation and radiation pressure are the main classical mechanisms that put a limit on the mass of the massive-forming star.

A collapsing cloud is unstable till it reaches the Jeans mass. Jean mass is a function of temperature and inverse of the density (Eq. 1.4). It can be calculated by balancing the gravitational energy ($\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{R}$) and the kinetic (thermal) energy ($\frac{3}{2} NKT$) of the collapsing cloud².

¹For more information on the empirical properties of massive stars see Chapter 2 of "Very massive stars in the local universe" by F. Martins

²M: total mass of the cloud; R: radius of the cloud; ρ : density; T: temperature; K: Boltzmann constant; N: number

$$M_J = \left(\frac{5KT}{Gm}\right)^{3/2} \left(\frac{3}{4\pi\rho}\right)^{1/2} \quad (1.4)$$

The fragmentation (instability) continues until stellar cores reach the Jean mass (stability). For example the Jeans-mass of a cloud with $T = 20K$ and $\rho = 10^{11} \text{molecules}/m^3$ is about $3M_\odot$. So if this cloud contains $5M_\odot$ of matter, it is Jeans-unstable and will collapse to form a star. In the simulations, if one considers just the hydrodynamics and gravity, a massive star (with the mass much higher than Jeans mass) should not form in principle. But recent simulations (radiation-hydrodynamics) considering more physical processes, like radiation feedback and magnetic fields, reduce significantly the fragmentation process by heating the surrounding gas, increasing the Pressure and thus the Jeans mass [Krumholz et al. (2007), Krumholz et al. (2010), Krumholz et al. (2011), Bate (2009), Bate (2012), Offner et al. (2009)]. Magnetic fields by removing angular momentum (magnetic braking) and providing extra pressure can prevent collapse [Hennebelle et al. (2011)]. The combination of both radiation feedback and magnetic field, which are locally complementary, shows almost no fragmentation [Commerçon et al. (2011), Myers et al. (2013)].

$$F_{grav} = \frac{GMm}{r^2} \quad (1.5)$$

$$F_{rad} = \frac{L}{c} \frac{\kappa m}{4\pi r^2} \quad (1.6)$$

The radiation pressure force is proportional to opacity (Eq. 1.6). So the radiation force of stars more massive than $20 M_\odot$ overcomes its gravitational force³ [Wolfire & Cassinelli (1987), Krumholz et al. (2009)]. The answer to the question of why stars more massive than $20 M_\odot$ (for MW dust abundances) cannot form from accretion, lies on considering the opacity source (dust mixed with gas) varying locally. One should consider non-spherically symmetric 2 (or 3) dimensional radiation-hydrodynamic simulations. In this way absorption and re-emission of photons as passing

of particles; m: average mass of the particles

³L: luminosity; κ : opacity

through dust is reprocessed within the simulation. Krumholz et al. (2009) showed the non-limiting mass accretion using three dimensional radiation-hydrodynamic simulations.

Very massive stars can also form via collision in a very dense (higher than $10^4 \text{star}/\text{pc}^3$) young stellar cluster. The Nbody simulations from Moeckel & Clarke (2011) and Baumgardt & Klessen (2011) show that the collisionally-formation of very massive stars is significant in an extremely high densities (higher than $10^7 \text{star}/\text{pc}^3$) with surface densities of $10^5 \text{star}/\text{pc}^2$. Although no observed cluster provides such a condition for collisional formation of VMS, it does not mean that none of the observed clusters never experienced such a condition to produce collisionally-formed massive stars.

New models/simulations introduce mechanisms which overcome the stellar mass limitations in previous models. But it does not mean no mechanism can limit stellar mass.

To distinguish the original route of the VMS formation (accretion or collision), one can follow the observable consequences and predictions of these models (for more details see [Krumholz (2015)]).

1.3.2 Evolution and Fate

Evolution of the structure of stars can be described with a series of differential equations involving mass, pressure, temperature, and density. The basic equations are conservation of mass (Eq.1.7), momentum (Eq.1.8), energy (Eq.1.9) and energy transport equation (Eq.1.10), to study the thermal structure of the star⁴. The evolution of chemical elements abundances⁵ (schematically shown

⁴**m**: Lagrangian mass coordinate; **r**: Radius of the shell enclosing mass **m**; **G**: Gravitational constant; **L**: Luminosity; **P**: Pressure; **T**: Temperature; **t**: Time; ϵ : Energy generation rate per unit mass for nuclear reactions (ϵ_n) or neutrinos (ϵ_ν); c_p : Specific heat at constant pressure; κ : Total opacity; σ : Stefan-Boltzmann constant; ρ : Density; $\delta = \partial \ln \rho / \partial \ln T$

⁵ X_i : the composition variable; r_{ji} is the rate at which species *i* is created from species *j*, and r_{ik} the rate at which *i* is destroyed to create *k*.

in Eq.1.11) should be added to the equations of the stellar structure as these equations are supplemented by some physical inputs (like opacity and nuclear reaction rate) influenced by local chemical elements.

$$\frac{\partial r}{\partial m} = \frac{1}{4\pi r^2 \rho} \quad (1.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial m} = -\frac{Gm}{4\pi r^4} - \frac{1}{4\pi r^2} \frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} \quad (1.8)$$

$$\frac{\partial L_r}{\partial m} = \varepsilon_n - \varepsilon_v - c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{\delta}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} \quad (1.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} &= -\frac{GmT}{4\pi r^4 P} \nabla \\ \nabla &= \nabla_{rad} = \frac{3}{16\pi\sigma G} \frac{\kappa L_r P}{mT^4} \\ \nabla &= \nabla_{con} (\approx \nabla_{ad}) = \frac{P\delta}{T\rho c_p} \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

$$\frac{\partial X_i}{\partial t} = \frac{m_i}{\rho} \left(\sum_j r_{ji} - \sum_k r_{jk} \right) \quad (1.11)$$

Depend on how energy is transported from the core to stellar surface, there will be convective (by gas) or radiation zones (photon diffusion). Low-mass stars have radiative cores as photons carry energy away, but convective envelope as high-energy-photons are absorbed by neutral hydrogen near the surface (opacity is high). Massive stars have a steep temperature gradient (very hot core) and radiation is not sufficient to transfer the energy of the high-photon-flux in a very dense core. So they have convective cores, but a radiative envelope as photons can carry energy without being absorbed by the ionized hydrogen in the outer layers.

The evolution of massive stars is different from low mass stars because they have large convective cores during the MS phase leading to evolve quasi-chemically homogeneously (internal

mixing). For example, stars massive than $150 M_{\odot}$ have a convective core larger than 75% of the total stellar mass (Figure 1 in Yusof et al. 2013). Very massive stars, due to their high mass-loss and strong internal mixing (convection), evolve vertically in the HRD. They cover a small range of T_{eff} and a very large range of L . It is different from low-mass stars that show this behavior only at high rotation rate.

Rotation and mass-loss affect the evolution and life-time of massive stars significantly. Stars in regions with lower metallicity have smaller mass-loss, larger convective core (total mass decreases slower than the convective core mass) and they enter to the WR-phase at an older age. Evolutionary tracks of the lower metallicities are shifted to higher L and T_{eff} . Rotation increases the mass-loss and the size of a convective core. Stars without rotation have less chemical-mixing so transition between H-He burning phase happens earlier (shorter MS life) and they end up with higher L (Figure 2 in Yusof et al. 2013).

More massive stars have shorter MS life. They live longer in lower metallicity regions. Fate of the VMS can be determined with the Carbon-Oxygen core mass (part of the core's mass in which fraction of C+O is more than 75%) or Helium core mass, regardless of their prior evolutions (Figure 18 in Yusof et al. 2013). Rotation and mass-loss affect the fate of massive stars significantly. For example, rotation by introducing additional mixing elements, produce larger He-core mass. Rotation also increases the MS life of the VMSs avoiding them to go to the supergiant phase. VMSs have high luminosities and a strong mass-loss in radiation zones, leading instabilities mostly in the stellar envelope and in some conditions in the interiors. According to the mass of the star and the different element-layers, they can end up in PreSupernova (with or without remnants), forming a Black-Hole, pulsational pair instability supernova or pair instability supernova.

1.4 Mass estimation

Depending on the kind of observational data and the nature of the object itself, different estimates of stellar masses can be derived. For example, it can be evolutionary (photometric), spectroscopic mass for imaging or spectroscopic data or direct dynamical mass estimation for the binary systems (spectroscopic or visual with high angular resolution instruments). Usually, effective temperature (T_{eff}) and Luminosity (L) are estimated using the spectral energy distribution (SED) fitting from the atmospheric models. Evolutionary mass is determined using evolutionary models which provide a direct relation between L and initial mass in HR diagram. In the spectroscopic mass, we need to estimate surface gravity ($\log g$) in addition to T_{eff} and L to estimate the mass directly from Eq. 1.12

$$M = \frac{g}{G} \frac{L}{4\pi\sigma T_{eff}^4} \quad (1.12)$$

$\log g$ is obtained from the fit of Balmer, Paschen or Brackett lines in the visible and infrared as the line wings are sensitive to pressure broadening, especially Stark broadening. As Stark broadening is created by neighboring charged particles, the broadening is stronger in denser environment. The best indicator lines are $H\beta$ and $H\gamma$ in the visible and $Br\gamma$ and $Br10$ in the infrared. Usually an accuracy of 0.1 dex in $\log g$ is achieved which corresponds to 25% uncertainty in mass, itself [Martins (2015)].

T_{eff} is a most important parameter to constrain since the derived luminosity scales as T_{eff}^4 . Atmosphere models are the tools to derive T_{eff} by providing the emitted flux by a star and its SED. For low and intermediate mass stars, SED peak is in visible wavelengths so their T_{eff} can be obtained from optical photometry. For (very) massive stars the SED peak is in (extreme) UV and the spectra is affected by line opacity (far UV). In the visible, the Rayleigh-Jeans tail of SED is located where the slope depends weakly on T_{eff} . So ionization balance method is usually used to estimate T_{eff} for massive stars. Synthetic spectra from the atmosphere models, shows that the

ionization increases as T_{eff} increases. The ratio of the different ionization states of a specific element is sensitive to the T_{eff} .

For hot stars (30 - 45 kK), the ratio of HeI and HeII is considered. In this range of temperature, as the T_{eff} increases, the ratio of HeII lines to HeI lines increases. For the higher temperatures ($T_{eff} > 45$ kK), HeI lines disappear and nitrogen lines (N IV/N V) can be used instead of helium lines. For lower temperatures ($T_{eff} < 30$ kK), as HeII lines disappear Si lines (SiII/SiIII, SiIII/SiIV) can be taken into account.

So the determination of effective temperature of a massive star requires an atmosphere model which predicts the flux emitted at the top of the atmosphere so that it can be compared with the observed spectrum. The current atmosphere models for massive stars are far from the ideal 3D and time-dependent models. Still some of them have the main three characteristics which are necessary for the massive stars: 1) They have to be calculated in non-LTE (non Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium); 2) The assumption of thin atmosphere (plane-parallel) cannot be applied as these stars emit strong stellar winds with sizes much larger than the stellar radius; 3) They have to include as many elements as possible heavier than hydrogen and helium (Line-Blanketing effects).

CMFGEN (Hillier & Miller 1998), FASTWIND (Puls et al. 2005) and POWR (Hamann & Grafener) are the model atmospheres which account for three key ingredients. In this thesis, We used TLUSTY⁶ model atmospheres [Hubeny & Lanz (1995)], as comprehensive grids of non-LTE, metal line-blanketed, plane-parallel, hydrostatic model atmospheres cover the parameter space of O and B-type stars [Lanz & Hubeny (2003), Lanz & Hubeny (2007)]. Despite neglecting the stellar wind, these model atmospheres provide very good predictions of the continuum flux (especially in the visible and near-IR), as demonstrated by Hillier & Lanz (2001) for the case of the WC5 Wolf-Rayet star HD 165763. A fortiori, in most O and B stars, the continuum flux is formed in a quasi-static photosphere with limited extension and, hence, the TLUSTY model assumptions

⁶Model atmospheres and source codes are available at <http://nova.astro.umd.edu>

are not a limitation for our application. We note furthermore that there are no comparable grids of model atmospheres with winds. For cooler stars, we use Kurucz [Castelli et al. (1997)] LTE line-blanketed model atmospheres.

1.5 Binary systems

Binary systems are important in astrophysics since knowing their orbital parameters leads to estimate the component's stellar masses directly. Moreover, stellar parameters of the stars can be estimated indirectly from their mass and the mass-luminosity relation can be tested on these systems.

According to the detection method of binary systems, they are classified in four main groups: Visual, Spectroscopic, Eclipsing and Astrometric binaries.

In visual binaries, two components can be individually resolved in imaging surveys. Relative positions of the components can be derived in long-term observations. Then the orbital parameters (period and separation) can be estimated after some epochs. Usually visual binaries have long periods, widely separated and need to be relatively close to us to be resolved visually (observational bias).

If the components are physically very close to each other or the whole system is very far from us, then they can be detected by Doppler shifts in their spectral lines. These systems are called spectroscopic binaries. In observation of spectroscopic binaries, the spectrum of two components are collected but the spectral signature of one (SB1) or both stars (SB2) can be separated. The Doppler shift in the lines can be measured using Gaussian profile fitting to several observed lines, or cross-correlation techniques that are more efficient with many lines. Then according to the Doppler shift in the lines, Radial Velocities (RV) can be calculated from Eq. 1.13. Final RV is an

average of the RVs of several lines.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} = \frac{RV}{C} \quad (1.13)$$

The spectroscopic binaries should be close enough to each other, to produce significant variation of RVs. That is why most of the detected spectroscopic binaries have short periods between 1 day up to few years (observational bias).

Semi-amplitude of RV variations (K) is related to orbital elements (Eq. 1.14)

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P}\right)^{1/3} M_1^{1/3} \frac{q}{(1+q)^{2/3}} \frac{\sin i}{\sqrt{(1-e^2)}} \\ K_2 &= \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P}\right)^{1/3} M_1^{1/3} \frac{1}{(1+q)^{2/3}} \frac{\sin i}{\sqrt{(1-e^2)}} \end{aligned} \quad (1.14)$$

Where $q = \frac{M_2}{M_1}$

So the mass ratio M_2/M_1 is the inverse of the RV amplitude ratio (K_1/K_2)

$$\frac{K_1}{K_2} = q = \frac{M_2}{M_1}$$

Using Radial Velocity (RV) curves, one can estimate the lower limits of the binary components masses (Dynamical mass), $M_1 \sin i$ and $M_2 \sin i$.

If there is a periodic change in the apparent magnitude of a star, it can be due to:

1) A change in the intrinsic luminosity of a single star (pulsating variables) or 2) An edge-on binary system which periodically eclipse one another (eclipsing binary).

If the binary system is eclipsing, we can obtain the inclination of the system ($\sin i \simeq 1$) leading to estimate the dynamical mass instead of the lower limit.

The last group of binaries is the Astrometric binaries which can be detected by the wave-like (wobble) in the proper motion of one or two components. Sirius system is an example of astrometric binary [Bessel (1844)]. Astrometric binaries are hard to detect due to the need for long-term observations and also the uncertainty in position and proper motion measurements.

By improving angular resolution (single telescope or interferometry), one can push further the limits of the visual binaries observations, so that the combination of visual binaries determined

parameters added to spectroscopic binaries equations (Eq. 1.14), completely solves the unknown parameters.

Note that all suspected very massive stars in multiple systems discovered so far, are in spectroscopic systems. For example, multi-epoch spectroscopic analysis of 360 O-type stars in the VLT-FLAMES Tarantula Survey of massive stars, shows that more than 50% of observed O-type stars are in binary systems [Sana et al. (2013)].

Massive stars can be born in a binary system as they have high accretion rate and possibility of disk fragmentation leading to produce a very massive companion [Kratter & Matzner (2006), Kratter et al. (2008), Kratter et al. (2010)]. Massive stars born in a crowded core of the young clusters have a chance to have massive companions within close encounters (expelling the low-mass companions).

1.6 Case of R136 and NGC3603

R136 is a very young massive star cluster in the heart of 30 Doradus in LMC. This dense cluster by hosting many massive stars (most observed massive stars in the Local Universe) provides a unique opportunity to study the formation of massive stars and clusters and the evolution in their early stages.

NGC3603 is located in the most massive Galactic HII region. This cluster hosts many massive O-type stars (up to 50) and three WR stars similar to those found in the core of R136. This cluster also is very young (few Myr) and massive (about $10^4 M_{\odot}$).

Lack of high angular resolution brought two main hypothesis for the nature of the fuzzy object in the core of R136: a super-massive star with a mass $> 1000 M_{\odot}$ [Feitzinger et al. (1980), Cassinelli et al. (1981), Savage et al. (1983)] or a dense cluster core that contains normal-mass O stars [Walborn (1973), Melnick (1982), Melnick (1983), Moffat & Seggewiss (1983), Huchra et al. (1983), Moffat et al. (1985)]. Figure 1.1 shows the observation by Feitzinger et al. 1980 in the

visible. They could not resolve the core so R136a was thought to be a single $1000 M_{\odot}$ object at that time.

Observational difficulties to resolve the core of NGC3603 was less than R136 as this cluster is about 7-8 times closer than R136 but still, studying this cluster is not straightforward as it is located in a high-extinction region ($A_V = 4.5$). Figure 1.4 shows an example of images of NGC3603 taken in the visible in 1964 and 1985. Later on, when HST and AO-assisted ground telescopes came, NGC3603 was studied better in several wavelengths both imaging and spectroscopically (Figure 1.5).

Observations improved using different methods in order to find the nature of R136a: Photometry and Spectroscopy from UV to IR, Speckle-interferometry, Optical surface photometry. Figure 1.2 shows the later observations by Moffat et al. (1985) and Weigelt et al. (1985) where they could resolve R136a from Spectrophotometry and Speckle-Interferometry.

Thinking to have data from space to overcome the atmosphere turbulence problem opened a new era in astronomy. HST brought a new images and spectroscopic data with higher resolution on R136a revealing many sources within the core of R136. Figure 1.3 shows the observation on R136 with HST in visible and infrared. Combination of photometry and spectroscopy analysis from HST data put more constrains on the nature of R136 and its member stars.

In parallel to the improvements on space telescopes, larger telescopes were built on the ground that could overcome atmospheric turbulence problems using Adaptive Optics technique. Figure 1.3 (Bottom) shows one of the images from the core of R136 in Ks band taken by VLT/MAD in K band. Atmosphere effects were corrected by AO facilities in ESO. This image is the best and most recent one from the core of R136. Then the ESO/VLT telescope second generation instruments came which have better AO systems like SPHERE. R136 was observed in the GTO time of SPHERE in K and J bands. Thousands stars can be detected in a compact core of R136 ($r < 6''$). This thesis describes these observations to improve our knowledge on the nature of R136.

Figure 1.1 Feitzinger+1980 observation in Visible (630-880nm) using ESO 3.6m telescope. R136a was recognized as a single object covering 0.7pc^2 or $2.8''^2$ with T_{eff} about 50 to 55 kK and mass of 250 to $1000 M_{\odot}$

As usual, theoretical models improved step by step with the improvement of telescopes and new observational data from better angular resolutions.

1.7 Observation

An astronomical object can be observed by several methods: Spectroscopy, imaging, interferometry and their combinations.

In order to better resolve the object, the angular resolution should be improved. The angular resolution of a telescope is limited by the aberration and diffraction. The origin of aberration comes from the instrument optics so it can be fixed by improving the optic quality of the instrument. Diffraction comes from the wave nature of the light as it interferes with itself while passing through the telescope aperture (Airy pattern). Diffraction is related to the wavelength (λ) of the light

Figure 1.2 Top: CCD image of R136 taken by 4m CTIA telescope in 470nm with FoV of 3' x 5'. Moffat+1985 using spectrophotometry on the core of R136, deduced R136a contains 4-5 WN stars.

Bottom: Resolving core of R136 and R136a's members using speckle-interferometry. Right: Weigelt+1985 for the first time, R136a resolved as 8 stars (R136a1 to R136a8). Left: Pehlemann+1992 used the same method with more frames, found more than 40 objects in the core of R136 (4".9 x 4".9). Both observations were done using 1.54m Danish/ESO telescope.

Figure 1.3 TOP: A region of $50 \times 50 \text{ pc}^2$ ($3.3' \times 3.3'$) around the cluster R136 in the 30 Doradus region of the LMC, at the distance of 50 kpc taken by HST/WFC3. Left: in the visible; Right: in the Infrared (1.1, 1.6 μm)

Bottom: VLT/MAD image of R136 in Ks band covering $12'' \times 12''$ [Campbell et al. (2010)] together with a $4'' \times 4''$ central view of the core. Image courtesy of Crowther et al. 2010 where he analyzed spectroscopic data on the 5 WR stars in the core of r136 using HST/HRS, HST/FOS and VLT/SINFONI. They found the initial mass of $320_{-40}^{+100} M_{\odot}$ for R136a1 with T_{eff} of $53 \pm 3 \text{ kK}$.

Figure 1.4 Right: Central part of NGC3603 with 4 minutes exposure, taken by 74-inch (1.88m) reflector plate in Mount Stromlo observatory by Sher 1964. Left: CCD image of NGC3603 taken by 4m CTIA telescope in 470nm. Circle has a diameter of 59". Mof-fat+1985 using spectrophotometry on the core of NGC3603, found this cluster contains 2-3 WN stars.

and the diameter of the aperture (D). The angular resolution of an ideal telescope (diffraction limited) scales as λ/D . So larger telescopes have better angular resolution in principle, specially in shorter wavelengths. But for the ground telescope, the atmosphere brings another limitation to the resolution. The images from large telescopes are blurred and distorted by the atmospheric turbulence. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the blurred image is called seeing which is usually around 1".

If λ/D is larger than FWHM of the seeing disk, then there is no need to correct the atmosphere turbulence. But for λ/D smaller than the FWHM of the seeing disk, the resolution will be limited to the seeing (regardless to the diameter of the telescope).

Figure 1.6 shows the diffraction-limited resolution (λ/D) of telescopes with different diameters at four different wavelengths (300, 500, 1000 and 2000 nm). For example, a 10cm telescope in 500nm has a resolution of about 1" so for larger telescopes in the same wavelength, one should correct the atmosphere-effects to reach to the resolution better than seeing (1"). The same telescope

Figure 1.5 Top: Image of NGC3603 taken by HST/WFC3 in visible and infrared.

Illustration Credit: NASA, ESA, and Z. Levay (STScI).

Bottom: Left: HST/HRC image of the core of NGC3603, three WR stars has been shown. Middle: Average spectra (VLT/SINFONI in K-band) of the three WR stars. Right: Same as middle but just for A1 almost at quadrature phase. Primary and secondary are shown viwh upward and downward arrows respectively. Spectra in middle and right are taken from Schnurr et al. 2008.

Figure 1.6 Diffraction limited resolution of telescopes with different diameter in four different wavelengths (300, 500, 1000 and 2000 nm).

(10cm) at larger wavelengths (like 2 um) does not need AO correction as its resolution (4") is already worse than the seeing!

The instrumentation to correct the atmosphere-turbulence-effects, is called Adaptive Optics (AO). So to reach to the diffraction limited resolution of large telescopes ($D \geq 1\text{m}$) one should use AO systems. But still, some part of the electromagnetic spectrum is totally blocked by the atmosphere (Gamma-rays, X-ray, UV and most of the IR). Using the space telescopes is a solution proposed to overcome the atmosphere effect on the blocked spectrum and also on the degraded resolution by the atmosphere turbulence.

Figure 1.7 Left: Atmosphere turbulence and its effect on the wavefront is shown schematically. Right: AO system.

Source: <http://slittlefair.staff.shef.ac.uk/teaching/phy217/lectures/telescopes/L10/index.html>

1.7.1 Adaptive Optics

The effects of turbulence in Earth's atmosphere on a wavefront can be quantified with three parameters⁷:

1) Fried parameter (r_0), is a length over which the wavefront can be considered as planar. It is approximately equal to the size of the turbulent cells. Figure 1.7 (left) schematically shows the Fried parameter. Theoretically, $r_0 \propto \lambda^{6/5}$. Typically r_0 is about 10 cm in the visible ($\lambda = 500\text{nm}$) and 70 cm in the infrared ($\lambda = 2.5\mu\text{m}$).

2) Coherence Time (t_0), is a time that the wavefront changes according to the turbulence cells movement by wind across the aperture of the telescope. Figure 1.7 (left) shows two wavefronts at time t_1 and t_2 . Then, the coherence time is $t_0 = t_2 - t_1 = \frac{r_0}{V}$ where V is a wind velocity. If the wind

⁷On-line lectures of Stuart Littlefair on observational astronomy at the University of Sheffield:

<http://slittlefair.staff.shef.ac.uk/teaching/phy217/lectures/telescopes/L10/index.html>

Figure 1.8 Right: Image of the core of R136 ($12'' \times 12''$) using SPHERE AO in K band. The resolution is about 49 mas. Left: Same image without AO so the resolution is limited by seeing ($0.8''$).

velocity is about 10 m/s, then the coherence time would be about 10 ms in the visible and 70 ms in the infrared.

3) Isoplanatic angle (θ_0), is the largest separation of the stars to have their light passes through the same turbulence region. If the height of the turbulent layer is h , the $\theta_0 = r_0/h$. In a good seeing condition, isoplanatic angle is about $2''$ in visible and $14''$ in infrared.

Figure 1.7 (right) shows the schematics of an AO system. The atmosphere aberrations are measured by a device called the Wave Front Sensor (WFS). Then, the aberrations are corrected by a deformable mirror (DM). Figure 1.8 shows an example of AO correction using VLT/SPHERE extreme AO system in K band. In the left, the resolution of the image is limited by the seeing (about $0.8''$). After correcting the atmosphere distortions (right image) with AO system, the resolution of the image approaches to the diffraction limited resolution (49mas) of the VLT/Melipal telescope (UT3).

Figure 1.9 SPHERE instruments (courtesy of ESO).

source: <https://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/paranal/instruments/sphere/inst.html>

1.7.2 SPHERE

For the purpose of this thesis we used the data taken for the first time by a second generation VLT instrument, The Spectro-Polarimetric High-contrast Exoplanet Research (SPHERE)⁸ [Beuzit et al. (2008)]. The first aim of this instrument is to detect new extra-solar giant planets orbiting nearby stars by direct imaging of their circumstellar environment. The instrument has been designed in a way to detect planets with the flux ratio higher than 12.5 magnitudes (or 10^5 in flux ratio) with their host stars at very small angular separations, typically a fraction of the seeing halo. I used SPHERE's high contrast and angular resolution to resolve the crowded core of the young massive clusters, R136 and NGC3603.

SPHERE is located at the Nasmyth focus of UT3 in VLT. The instrument as shown in Figure 1.9 is composed of 4 major subsystems: the common path including the powerful AO system and the three science instruments Infra-Red Dual-beam Imager and Spectrograph (IRDIS), Infrared Integral Field Spectrograph (IFS) and Zurich Imaging Polarimeter (ZIMPOL) each fed by a sophisticated pupil apodized Lyot, Lyot, or phase-mask coronagraphs.

⁸<https://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/paranal/instruments/sphere.html>

An eXtreme AO system (SAXO) uses a 1600 actuators DM, thus correcting up to 1200 modes at loop frequencies up to 1.2kHz. The system also provides a stabilized pupil for the coronographic system and extra-stable PSFs during calibration procedures.

ZIMPOL, an innovative and state-of the art differential polarimeter working at visual to very near infra-red wavelengths. It provides diffraction limited classical imaging (CI) and differential polarimetric imaging (DPI).

IRDIS, a dual-band imager providing simultaneous imaging in two channels throughout the near-IR bands. It provides classical imaging (CI), dual-band imaging (DBI), dual-polarization imaging (DPI), and also long slit spectroscopy (LSS) with low and medium resolution (LRS and MRS).

IFS, an integral field spectrograph working in near-IR bands, the concept of which will allow to exceed the contrast limits of conventional differential imaging by a factor of 3-10. It provides a data cube of 30 monochromatic images in Y-J (0.95-1.35 μm) with spectral resolution of $R\sim 50$ or in Y-H (0.95-1.65 μm) with $R\sim 30$.

The Adaptive Optic System of SPHERE is based on the Shack-Hartmann WFS, with an array of 40×40 sub-apertures. It has a Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO) Controlling System and Stacked Actuator Mirror (SAM) with a grid of 41×41 .

For R136 and NGC3603 observations, we used imaging mode of IRDIS which has a FOV of $11''\times 12.5''$ with a pixel scale of 12.25 mas. Figure 1.10 shows the layout of IRDIS instrument. The common path beam passes through two main wheels, 1) common filter wheel which contains 18 broad and narrow band filters and 2) Lyot stop wheel which contains 14 sections for different coronagraphs of the CPI, LRS prism and MRS grism. Then two parallel beams are produced using a beam-splitter combined with a mirror. These parallel beams passes through the third wheel which contains several dual-band filters. For our observations, we used classical imaging mode of IRDIS using just J and Ks broad-band filters.

Figure 1.10 Inside view of IRDIS instrument (courtesy of ESO). The common path beam enters the common filter wheel and Lyot stop wheel, then it splits into two beams and passes through dual filter wheel and at the end lands on the detector.

source: <https://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/paranal/instruments/sphere/inst.html>

1.7.3 Telescopes comparison

Table 1.2 compares the capabilities of four telescopes (instruments): in space we already have HST and in future there will be James Webb Space Telescope (JWST). The resolution of these telescopes is limited by their diameters and the wavelength. There are also larger ground telescopes like the VLT (8.2m), with a resolution depending not only by the diameter and wavelength but also by the AO system. The better the AO system, the closer we get to the diffraction limited resolution (λ/D). SPHERE has already the best AO system at the VLT which can reach to the diffraction limited resolution specially in longer wavelengths. European Extremely Large Telescope (E-ELT) is a future ground instrument which can reach to the best resolution among the mention telescopes. Multi-AO Imaging Camera for Deep Observations (MICADO) is one of the first-light instruments for the E-ELT. Table 1.3 compares the VLT/SPHERE's different imaging modes with E-ELT/MICADO ⁹

⁹<https://www.eso.org/public/teles-instr/e-elt/e-elt-instr/micado/>

Table 1.2 Comparison different telescopes resolving powers

Telescope	Type	Diameter [m]	λ_{cen} [μm]	optimum resolution [mas]	Pixel scale [mas/pix]
HST/WFPC2,WFC3	space	2.4	0.3 - 1.6	30 - 160	40-90
JWST/NIRCam	space	6.5	0.6 - 5.0	22 - 145	23-65
VLT/SPHERE/IRDIS	ground	8.2	1.0 - 2.3	25 - 50	12.25
E-ELT/MICADO	ground	39	0.8 - 2.4	6 - 12	2-3

Table 1.3 SPHERE imaging modes compared to E-ELT/MICADO

Main Characteristics	IRDIS	ZIMPOL	MICADO
wavelength range[um]	0.9-2.3	0.6-0.9	(0.6)-0.8-2.5
FoV [arcs]	13.5x13.5	3x3	53 x 53
Pixel scale [mas]	12.25	7.5	2-3
FWHM [mas]	31(J),55(K)	15(V)	6(J), 10(K)
observing modes	On axis guide star - Dual-band Imaging - Differetial Imaging - Dual-Polarimetric Imaging - Polarimetric Imaging - Long-slit Spectroscopy		Off axis AO loop

instrument, as an example.

1.8 This thesis

The aim of this thesis is to understand the different aspects of the dynamical and stellar evolution of very massive clusters. These newly formed massive clusters are the most important link between the formation of the massive star clusters and their evolution. The YMCs fill the gap between two

main types of the stellar clusters (globular and open) in terms of mass and density [Portegies Zwart et al. (2010)]. By accepting the clustered formation of the stars, one should consider a possibility that YMCs are the progenitors of the globular clusters.

We chose two YMCs, located in the most massive Galactic/extra-Galactic HII regions NGC3603 and R136 which hosts the most massive stars in the local universe. The works on this thesis have two different eras, before and after SPHERE!

In the first era, we started to study these clusters using HST data with improved atmosphere models. To know more on the dynamics of such compact clusters with many massive stars, we used N-body simulations with different initial conditions.

In the second era, the same clusters were analyzed, this time with SPHERE data, taken by the largest available telescope at ESO Paranal using the most efficient AO instrument. These challenging observations showed the capabilities of SPHERE for imaging distant clusters. Moreover, its higher angular resolution and high dynamic imaging capabilities, open discovery windows to resolve objects which have remained unresolved to date by any other instrument.

In Chapter 2 we present the results on the HST analysis on both clusters. We used WFPC2-PC data for R136 and ACS/HRC data on NGC3603 in addition to WFPC2. We created the isochrones using Geneva evolutionary models and TLUSTY atmosphere models (for O and B type stars) and KURUCZ (for other spectral types). After correcting the extinction in each HST data independently, we estimated the stellar masses and MF for each cluster in different filters, locally.

For R136, we used the NBODY6 code to initiate a new method to study R136-like clusters. Chapter 3 shows the results of these simulations. The effect of stellar evolution, initial binaries and mass segregation on the evolution of the cluster till 4 Myr are discussed in this chapter. The new method, compares the direct results of the simulations with observational data (HST/WFPC2/F814W). We used stellar atmosphere models to estimate the flux of each star and create a synthetic scene that we compare to HST data. Four different method are used to find the

closest synthetic image to HST data on R136.

Chapter 4 shows the results of SPHERE data on NGC3603 cluster. The IRDIS data covers three fields of the core of NGC3603. After correcting the extinction in IRDIS J and K band data for 31 spectroscopically known O stars, we estimated the stellar masses in the range $0.6 - 120M_{\odot}$. We detected 286 and 406 stars in K and J band, respectively, in the very core of the cluster (F0). In the next radial bin (F1 and F2) we detected 1003 and 561 stars in K and J band respectively. This study shows no signature of mass segregation in the core of NGC3603 for two main reasons: First, MF slope in the very core (F0) is not flatter than the next radial bin (F1 and F2). Second, both slopes are similar to the MF values found in the previous works for the outer regions.

Using the same method to analyze NGC3603, the results on the HST (Chapter 2) and SPHERE (Chapter 4) data are different. This leads to understand the effect of observational confusion on the astrophysical analysis. In Chapter 3 we precisely added this confusion on the Nbody simulations of R136.

In Chapter 5 we discuss the results of SPHERE data on the core of R136. The SPHERE/IRDIS data covers $10.9'' \times 12.3''$ of the core of R136 in J and K band. Using Starfinder, we detected 1110 and 1059 sources in J and K band data and 818 common sources between two bands. More than 70% of the detected sources have companions closer than $0.2''$ in both J and K band data. The majority (above 90%) of massive stars (brighter than 17 mag in K and 16 mag in J) have visual companions closer than $0.2''$. Among them, R136a1 and R136c have visual companions which are detected for the first time. R136a3 was resolved as two stars (PSF fitting) separated by $0.06''$ which is larger than the FWHM of the PSF. Thanks to SPHERE high resolution data, we detected many stars in the compact crowded core of this unique cluster. To correct the extinction we used 55 spectroscopically known bright stars in the core of R136 from [Crowther et al. (2016)]. Knowing the T_{eff} and $\log g$ of these sources, we could estimate the extinction in J and K using the grid of evolutionary models at different ages. The age of $1.8_{-0.8}^{+1.2}$ Myr is the most probable age for these

sample of stars. The extinction in J and K are $A_J = 1.3 \pm 0.5$ and $A_K = 0.4 \pm 0.5$ respectively. Considering the spectroscopic and photometric errors on the extinction and the age of the cluster members, we estimate a mass range for each detected stellar source. The generalized histogram of stellar masses (MF) was plotted at different ages with a given error on each stellar mass.

In the last Chapter, the summary of the results will be explained for both NGC3603 and R136. I will compare the results of the HST analysis in visible (Chapter 2) with SPHERE in near-IR (Chapter 4 and 5). The results of the Nbody6 simulations on R136-like clusters will be summarized regarding to the HST data. At the end I will explain the future projects and prospects.

Top: Vincent Willem van Gogh's *Starry Night*, without adaptive optics!

Bottom: With adaptive optics (ref: <http://thescinder.com/tag/atmospheric-turbulence>)

Chapter 2

HST Photometry (R136, NGC3603)

Abstract In this chapter, we present a new analysis of archival HST WFPC2 and ACS images of two young massive star clusters, R136 and NGC 3603. Combining HST multi-color photometry with new bolometric correction tables set in the native HST photometric system, model stellar spectra and Geneva evolutionary models assuming cluster ages between 1Myr and 2Myr, we derived stellar masses and constructed mass functions (MF) of the two clusters. We found consistent MF derived in the different colors, supporting that the constant extinction correction over the cluster fields is a reasonable approximation. The derived MF of the two clusters is top-heavy compared to the standard Salpeter law, with a slope that is steeper in outer annuli than in the cluster cores. Mass segregation is well supported in NGC 3603, but uncertainties remain in the case of R136 because of the limited resolution and interstellar extinction. The difference between the two clusters then suggest that NGC 3603 had a single formation burst 1Myr ago, while R136 underwent sequential star formation from 1 to 2Myr ago.

2.1 Introduction

Massive stars shape their environment at the various stages of their evolution, from their formation in dense clusters to their demise as core-collapse supernovae. Locally two young massive clusters, NGC 3603 in the Carina spiral arm of the Milky Way and R136 in the heart of the 30 Doradus star forming region in the LMC, are remarkable concentrations of massive stars that can guide us for understanding the formation of massive stars and their influence on their environment.

R136 is a very massive ($10^5 M_{\odot}$) young star cluster (less than 2 Myr in the core, [de Koter et al. (1998), Massey & Hunter (1998), Crowther et al. (2010)]) containing a large number of massive stars that have been formed in a relatively small space [Hunter et al. (1995)]. The total number of O3 stars (at least 41) in this one cluster exceeds the total number known elsewhere in the Milky Way or Magellanic Clouds [Massey & Hunter (1998)]. The WN stars in R136 have individual luminosities that are a factor of 10 higher than normal for WN stars of similar types, showing that they are actually very massive hydrogen-core burning stars whose spectrum mimic Wolf-Rayet (WR) stars because of their thick stellar wind. Their spectrum closely resembles these of WN stars in the Galactic cluster NGC 3603 [Massey & Hunter (1998)].

Among the Galactic spiral arm clusters, the NGC 3603 young cluster, located in its namesake giant H II region NGC 3603 [Kennicutt (1984)], is the most compact and youngest cluster with an age of about 1 Myr [Kudryavtseva et al. (2012), Stolte et al. (2004), Sung & Bessell (2004), Brandl et al. (1999)] and a central density of $6 \times 10^4 M_{\odot} pc^3$ [Harayama et al. (2008)]. The cluster contains three WR stars and up to 50 O-type stars [Drissen et al. (1995)]. Its total mass is estimated to be $10^4 M_{\odot}$ [Harayama et al. (2008)] with an upper dynamical mass limit of $17600 \pm 3800 M_{\odot}$ [Rochau et al. (2010)]. The WR stars show characteristics of WN6 stars, but also have Balmer absorption lines [Drissen et al. (1995)], indicating that these stars are actually hydrogen-core burning rather than stars that have evolved off the main sequence [Conti et al. (1995), de Koter et al. (1997)].

Both clusters provide a rare opportunity to study the formation and early stages of evolution of

massive stars and star clusters as they are very massive, young and close to be spatially resolved.

These clusters are the relevant objects for studying the formation and evolution of massive stars and star clusters, and for addressing questions such as the determination of the top end of the initial mass function and to establish whether or not the massive stars tend to be formed in the core of the cluster and show mass segregation.

The initial step is therefore the accurate determination of stellar masses. Except the case of eclipsing binary systems, this determination relies on spectroscopic and evolutionary models to tie the mass to the stellar luminosity. For this latter quantity, a correction to interstellar extinction plays a crucial role.

This work is based on HST WFPC2 and HRC/ACS multi-color photometry described in Section 4.2, and our methodology is discussed in Section 2.3. Correction to interstellar extinction is presented in Section 2.4 Our results on the mass functions of the two clusters are discussed in Section 2.5, and are compared to earlier results in Section 2.6. Our main results are summarized in Section 2.7.

2.2 Data and photometry

Deep imaging data of R 136 and NGC 3603 obtained by the NASA/ESA Hubble Space Telescope have been extracted from the STScI MAST archive, focusing on data with the highest resolution and longest exposure times.

HST/WFPC2 observations of R 136 were carried out on 1994-09-25 (PI: Westphal), from which we use a combination of shallow, intermediate and long exposures ranging from 3–5 s to 80–120 s with the planetary camera (PC) and the F555W and F814W filters. We use also similar HST/WFPC2 PC data of NGC 3603 obtained on 1997-07-30 (PI: Drissen), with shallow, intermediate and long exposures ranging from 0.4–1 s to 20–30 s, but with the F547M, F675W and F814W

filters. Details of the exposures are given in Table 2.1. HST observations of NGC 3603 with the High Resolution Channel (HRC) of the Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) have also been conducted on 2005-12-29 (PI: Maiz Apellaniz). Details of the exposure times and filters are given in Table 2.2. After applying a mask for the border noise, the FoV of the WFPC2/PC images is about $32.5'' \times 32.5''$ and about $24.8'' \times 25.7''$ for the NGC 3603 ACS/HRC images.

We performed Point Spread Function (PSF) photometry for the detection of stellar objects and the derivation of instrumental magnitudes using the STARFINDER package implemented in IDL [Diolaiti et al. (2000)]. We assumed precomputed PSFs based on analytical models with a detector-dependent FWHM instead of choosing empirical PSFs extracted from sources in the image itself that is more suitable for AO-assisted imaging. We adopted threshold values in such a way that the second peak of the Airy pattern of the very bright stellar sources is not detected. In the R 136 data, we found respectively 2509 and 2660 sources in the F555W and F814W images. In the NGC 3603 WFPC2 images, we found 1333, 2063 and 1493 sources in the F547M, F675W and F814W images, respectively, while we detected 282, 376 and 562 sources in the ACS/HRC F550M, F658N and F850LP images.

2.3 Method

We aim at deriving stellar masses by combining the HST photometry with stellar evolution and stellar atmosphere models. We use photometric data in each filter for independent estimates of the stellar mass. The basic output of stellar structure models the luminosity L and the effective temperature T_{eff} must be first converted into observable photometric quantities, i.e. magnitudes and colors. This conversion is performed by means of bolometric corrections BC and T_{eff} -color relations, and later by considering the proper distance, absorption and reddening of the observed population, and the photometric errors [Girardi et al. (2002)].

Table 2.1 Exposure log of HST/WFPC2 observations

Shallow ¹ / N ²	Middle ¹ / N ²	Deep ¹ / N ²	Filter	Pixel Scale [arcsec/pix]	Spatial Resolution [arcsec]	Observation Date
R 136						
3.0 / 1	23.0 / 16	120.0 / 7	F555W	0.050	0.110	1994-09-25
5.0 / 1	40.0 / 16	80.0 / 7	F814W	0.050	0.121	1994-09-25
NGC 3603						
1.0 / 3	10.0 / 12	30.0 / 8	F547M	0.050	0.110	1997-07-30
0.4 / 15	...	20.0 / 8	F675W	0.050	0.115	1997-07-30
0.4 / 3	5.0 / 12	20.0 / 8	F814W	0.050	0.121	1997-07-31

¹ Exposure time of each frame in seconds

² Number of frames

Table 2.2 Exposure log of HST/ACS observations of NGC 3603

Exp. Time[s]	Frames	Detector	Filter	Pixel Scale	Spatial Resolution	Observation Date
44.0	4	HRC	F250W	0.025	0.049	2005-12-29
10.0	4	HRC	F330W	0.025	0.052	2005-12-29
2.0	4	HRC	F435W	0.025	0.057	2005-12-29
2.0	4	HRC	F550M	0.025	0.065	2005-12-29
10.0	4	HRC	F658N	0.025	0.071	2005-12-29
1.5	4	HRC	F850LP	0.025	0.088	2005-12-29

Our work proceeds in three steps. First, we have constructed BC tables for the HST filters listed in Tables 2.1 and 2.2. Second, we need to correct the observed photometric magnitudes for extinction. For each cluster, we have obtained an averaged extinction based on a sample of spectroscopically known O-type stars. Finally, for each filter, we combine the photometric data, the extinction correction, the proper BC table, and stellar evolution models to derive the stellar masses.

2.3.1 Bolometric Corrections for HST filters

We start from extended libraries of stellar model spectra F_λ , as calculated from stellar model atmospheres for a grid of effective temperatures T_{eff} , surface gravities $\log g$, and metallicities $[M/H]$. We aim at deriving absolute magnitudes M_{S_λ} for each star of known stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[M/H]$) and hence known F_λ for the model library. These magnitudes M_{S_λ} can be obtained by means of Eq. 2.1:

$$M_{S_\lambda} = M_{bol} - BC_{S_\lambda} \quad (2.1)$$

Eq. 2.2 (taken from Eq. 7 in Girardi et al. 2002) is used to calculate BC_{S_λ} :

$$BC_{S_\lambda} = M_{bol\odot} - 2.5 \log[4\pi(10\text{pc})^2 \sigma T_{\text{eff}}^4 / L_\odot] + 2.5 \log\left(\frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \lambda F_\lambda S_\lambda d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda^0 S_\lambda d\lambda}\right) - m_{S_\lambda}^0 \quad (2.2)$$

We adopt $M_{bol\odot} = 4.77$, and $L_\odot = 3.844 \times 10^{33} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ [Bahcall et al. (1995)]. $f_{ST,\lambda}^0$ and $m_{ST,\lambda}^0$ are the zero-points in the HST STmag system and are defined as follows:

$$f_{ST,\lambda}^0 = 3.631 \times 10^{-9} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ \AA}^{-1}$$

$$m_{ST,\lambda}^0 = 0 \text{ at all wavelengths.}$$

F_λ is the flux at the stellar surface (from the model atmosphere library) in a given passband with transmission curve S_λ in the interval $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$.

Figure 2.1 WFPC2/F814W image of R136 with the 26 selected O stars shown by circles. The color-bar represents the range of extinction values and the selected stars are marked with blue or red circles depending on the estimated extinction. We divided the cluster in three different concentric regions with annulus of $4''.5$ (corresponding to about 1 pc at a distance of 48.5 kpc).

We used TLUSTY¹ model atmospheres [Hubeny & Lanz (1995)], as comprehensive grids of non-LTE, metal line-blanketed, plane-parallel, hydrostatic model atmospheres cover the parameter space of O and B-type stars [Lanz & Hubeny (2003), Lanz & Hubeny (2007)]. Despite neglecting the stellar wind, these model atmospheres provide very good predictions of the continuum flux (especially in the visible and near-IR) as demonstrated by [Hillier & Lanz (2001)] for the case of the WC5 Wolf-Rayet star HD 165763. A fortiori, in most O and B stars, the continuum flux is formed in a quasi-static photosphere with limited extension and, hence, the TLUSTY model assumptions are not a limitation for our application. We note furthermore that there are no comparable grids of model atmospheres with winds. For cooler stars, we use Kurucz [Castelli et al. (1997)] LTE line-blanketed model atmospheres. We apply Eq. 2.2 to tabulate BC_{S_λ} for all spectra in our model spectral libraries, and for several different photometric filters in the HST system. For any intermediate (T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[M/H]$) values, BC_{S_λ} can then be derived by interpolations (we used cubic interpolations). In the following, these tables will be referred as the Atmosphere-BC tables.

2.3.2 Correcting the extinction

Knowledge of the intrinsic properties and colors is required in order to derive the extinction in each filter toward the star clusters. Only limited information is available for these two clusters, mostly about their hottest and brightest stars. We had then to start from the known spectral types of some O stars from which we could assign stellar parameters and intrinsic colors.

In R136, we selected 26 O-type stars classified by [Massey & Hunter (1998)]. The selected stars are shown in Fig. 2.1. We then adopted effective temperatures from the spectral type– T_{eff} relation in Table 1 of [Simon-Diaz et al. (2014)]. Surface gravities, $\log g$, (and hence luminosities) are assigned using isochrones (1.0, 1.5 and 2 Myr) in the Geneva stellar evolution models. Bolometric corrections are then interpolated from the Atmosphere-BC tables constructed from model atmo-

¹Model atmospheres and source codes are available at <http://nova.astro.umd.edu>

Figure 2.2 WFPC2/F814W image of NGC 3603 with the 21 selected O stars. Three concentric regions are also shown (at 5", 10" and 15"). At the cluster distance, 5" corresponds to about 0.17 pc.

spheres with a half-solar metallicity appropriate for LMC stars. Intrinsic magnitudes, and then the extinction, in the F814W and F555W filters follow from Eq. 2.1 and the measured magnitudes.

For NGC 3603, we proceeded in a similar way selecting 21 O-type stars (15 class V stars and 7 class III stars) from [Melena et al. (2008)], as shown in Fig. 2.2. The stellar parameters of these stars are derived from Table 4 or Table 5 of [Martins et al. (2005)] depending on their luminosity class. We obtained the extinction and color excesses for the three WFPC2 filters and the seven ACS/HRC filters, similarly to R136 but for using the Atmosphere-BC tables calculated for model atmospheres with solar metallicity and the 1 Myr isochrone. The results are discussed in Section 2.4.

2.3.3 Estimating stellar masses

We finally built sets of evolutionary tables that are a combination of stellar evolution models and Atmosphere-BC tables. Hereafter, we call these sets of tables Evolutionary-BC tables. These tables gives the mass of stars and their T_{eff} , $\log g$ and $\log L$ according to their BC calculated in different HST WFPC2 and ACS/HRC filters. It is the reverse relation built on the common entries, metallicity, T_{eff} and $\log g$, between the Atmosphere-BC tables and the stellar evolution models.

To create the Evolutionary-BC tables, we used the Geneva stellar evolution models² [Lejeune & Schaerer (2001)], and in particular the 1.0, 1.5 and 2 Myr isochrones at half-solar metallicity for R136 and the 1 Myr isochrone at solar metallicity for NGC 3603. To derive luminosities, we assumed that stars were on the main sequence given the young age of the two clusters and we adopted the following distances to the clusters: 48.5 kpc for R136 [Selman et al.(1999), Gieren et al. (1998)] and 7 kpc for NGC 3603 [Moffat (1983), Sagar et al. (2001), Sung & Bessell (2004), van den Bergh (1978), De Pree et al. (1999)].

²<http://webast.ast.obs-mip.fr/equipe/stellar/>

Figure 2.3 Histogram of extinction of 26 O-type stars with known spectral types in R136 in two HST/WFPC2 filters (F555W and F814W) using three different isochrones: 1 Myr (top), 1.5 Myr (middle) and 2 Myr (bottom). Red and pink histograms represents extinction in the F814W and F555W filters and the filled blue histogram shown to the color excess distribution.

2.4 Extinction and CMDs of the two clusters

Figure 2.3 shows the histogram of the extinction of the 26 O-type stars in R136 in two filters (F814W and F555W) as well as the (F555W-F814W) color excess, obtained using in turn the 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 Myr isochrones (from top to bottom). The distribution of extinction values become bimodal when using the 2 Myr isochrone with O3 stars showing the larger extinction and the later O stars being distributed in the first peak. The reason of this behavior remains unclear.

The histogram of the extinction toward the 21 O stars in NGC 3603 is similarly displayed in

Figure 2.4 Top: Extinction toward 21 O-stars in NGC 3603 in three different HST/WFPC2 filters. Bottom: Same in seven different HST/HRC filters.

Table 2.3 Maximum-weighted values of Extinction and color excess of R136 in different HST/WFPC2 filters at the ages of 1, 1.5 and 2 Myr and distance of 48.5 kp, using models with standard (c008) and high (e008) mass-loss rates.

Models	c008			e008		
	1 Myr	1.5 Myr	2 Myr	1 Myr	1.5 Myr	2 Myr
A(F555W)	2.56	3.03	3.63	2.56	3.63	4.47
A(F814W)	1.00	1.59	2.12	1.38	2.10	3.06
E(F555W-F814W)	1.19	1.19	1.19	1.19	1.19	1.19

Fig. 2.4 that shows extinction in the three WFPC2 filters (upper panel) and in seven ACS/HRC filters (lower panel). The filled histograms pertain to the labeled color excesses. The uncertainty on the cluster distance cancels out when examining color excesses. We point at the general trend of increased extinction at shorter wavelengths that can be seen clearly for NGC 3603 in both the WFPC2 and HRC filter sets. Both, in the WFPC2 data and in the HRC data, the RI color excess ($E(F675W-F814W)$) is larger than the VR color excess ($E(F547M-F675W)$). The calculated extinction and color excess are derived independently with the two instruments. The same general trend therefore provides confidence with the adopted methodology.

We examine the spatial distribution of the extinction over the cluster fields. As no trend seems obvious, we decided to apply the same extinction correction to all the cluster stars adopting the median value for O stars derived in each filter for each cluster. For R136, we have thus determined a VI color excess, $E(F555W - F814W) = 1.19$. The extinctions and color excesses adopted for NGC 3603 are listed in Table 2.4. In this Table, the Galactic extinction law values by Rieke & Lebofsky (1985) are shown in the fourth column (R&L) to be compared with the extinction values we estimated for different HST filters shown in third column. For the ACS/HRC data, the extinction law is consistent with the Galactic extinction law. Note that the HST filter transparency is different from the filters which Rieke & Lebofsky (1985) estimated the extinction law, especially

Table 2.4 Median values of Extinction and color excess of NGC3603 in different HST filters at the age of 1 Myr and distance of 7 Kpc. The Galactic extinction law values by Rieke & Lebofsky (1985) are shown in the fourth column (R&L) to be compared with the extinction values we estimated for different HST filters shown in third column.

λ	A_λ	A_λ/A_{F547M}	R&L	
WFPC2/F547M	5.46	1.0	1.0	E(F547M-F675W): 0.54
WFPC2/F675W	5.05	0.92	0.75	E(F675W-F814W): 0.93
WFPC2/F814W	4.16	0.76	0.48	
λ	A_λ	A_λ/A_{F550M}	R&L	
ACS/HRC/F220W	12.09	2.19	-	E(F220W-F250W): 2.33
ACS/HRC/F250W	9.83	1.78	-	E(F250W-F330W): 1.55
ACS/HRC/F330W	8.24	1.49	1.53	E(F330W-F435W): 1.39
ACS/HRC/F435W	6.80	1.23	1.32	E(F435W-F550M): 1.58
ACS/HRC/F550M	5.23	1.0	1.0	E(F550M-F658N): 0.85
ACS/HRC/F658N	4.37	0.79	0.75	E(F658N-F850LP): 1.08
ACS/HRC/F850LP	3.30	0.59	0.48	

for WFPC2 broad-band filters. A_{F547M} is narrower than standard V-filter used to extract extinction law, this can explain the larger A_λ/A_{F547M} values compared to Rieke & Lebofsky (1985).

The R136 CMD is constructed from the F555W and F814W magnitudes. We identified 1674 stars in common between the WFPC2 frames obtained with these two filters. The selection threshold was set as to avoid assigning the Airy pattern second peak of very bright stars as (spurious) single stars. We found 420 common stars in the core ($r < 4''.5$) region, 558 stars in the first annulus region ($4''.5 < r < 9''$) and 696 stars in the outer annulus ($4''.5 < r < 9''$) – see Fig. 2.1. The CMDs are displayed in Fig. 2.5 for the whole cluster and the three different sub-fields. The solid lines are the Geneva isochrones (using Evolutionary-BC tables) with LMC metallicity at age 1.0

Figure 2.5 Color-Magnitude Diagrams of R136. Panels from left to right show the CMD for the whole cluster, and in the three regions (core and annuli shown in Fig. 2.1). The 10 Wolf-Rayet stars in the FoV are shown with black crosses. Solid lines are the 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 Myr Geneva isochrones.

(blue), 1.5 (green) and 2 (pink) Myr, assuming a distance of 48.5 kpc, and corrected by the median extinction values and the adopted VI color excess. The brightest stars in the CMD favor a cluster age of about 2 Myr (a younger cluster might have even brighter stars). We point out to the top of R136 main sequence (MS). As expected the brightest O stars are leaving the MS, evolving to the red as expected from classical stellar evolution. However, the top of the MS turns back to the blue: this is a telltale sign of fast rotation leading to homogeneous evolution of the most massive stars [Meynet & Maeder (2000), Kohler et al. (2015)].

For NGC 3603, we built separate CMDs from WFPC2 and ACS/HRC data. We identified 609

Figure 2.6 Color-Magnitude Diagrams of the core of NGC 3603 from WFPC2 (top) and HRC (bottom) data. Panels from left to right show the CMD for the whole cluster, and in the three regions (core and annuli shown in Fig. 2.2). The solid line is the 1.0 Myr Geneva isochrone.

common stars in WFPC2/F547M and WFPC2/F814W frames. Among them, 192 stars are in the cluster core region ($r < 5''$), 156 stars in the annulus ($5'' < r < 10''$) and 139 stars in the outer region ($10'' < r < 15''$). The CMDs are displayed in upper panel of Fig. 2.6. The solid blue line shows the 1 Myr Geneva isochrone (using Evolutionary-BC tables) with solar metallicity assuming a cluster distance of 7 kpc, and the median values of extinction and color excess as before. In the HRC data, we found 237 common stars in the HRC/F550M and HRC/F850LP frames (121, 69 and 47 common stars in three different regions). The CMDs are shown in the lower panel of Fig. 2.6. The top part of the CMD does not reveal any star that is evolving off the MS, suggesting a very young age for NGC 3603 and, therefore, we have adopted an age of 1 Myr.

2.5 Mass Functions

Following Sect. 2.3.3, we derived the stellar masses from photometric data of R136 in two filters (WFPC2/F555W and WFPC2/F814W) independently, combining them with stellar atmospheres and stellar evolution models. As explained above, we have used in turn the 1.0, 1.5 and 2 Myr isochrones to estimate the stellar masses. The mass functions (MF) is displayed in Fig. 2.7 (at 1 Myr), Fig. 2.8 (at 1.5 Myr) and Fig. 2.9 (at 2 Myr) in the whole cluster (red dots and lines) and in three pre-defined regions (core and annuli - blue dots and lines). In both photometric colors, the MF turns down indicating that our photometry is incomplete at the lowest mass end ($\log(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}) < 0.8$). The MF is commonly modeled by a log-log relation:

$$\log(N) = \Gamma \log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right) + b \quad (2.3)$$

For NGC3603, WFPC2 data we considered all mass bins for deriving the slopes while for the ACS/HRC data we excluded the first mass bin to calculate the MF slopes. For R136, in outer regions, we excluded the first mass bin and in the core, 2 (at 1, 1.5 Myr) and 3 (at 2 Myr) mass bins are excluded.

Table 2.5 Slopes of the mass function of the R136 cluster.

WFPC2	F555W	F814W
1 Myr isochrone		
Whole cluster	-0.98 ± 0.19	-1.04 ± 0.12
$r < 4''.5$	-0.15 ± 0.20	-0.74 ± 0.23
$4''.5 < r < 9''$	-1.17 ± 0.19	-1.33 ± 0.15
$9'' < r < 13''.5$	-1.03 ± 0.12	-1.07 ± 0.07
1.5 Myr isochrone		
Whole cluster	-0.73 ± 0.14	-0.77 ± 0.07
$r < 4''.5$	-0.34 ± 0.28	-0.25 ± 0.16
$4''.5 < r < 9''$	-1.03 ± 0.20	-0.98 ± 0.12
$9'' < r < 13''.5$	-0.83 ± 0.09	-0.93 ± 0.10
2 Myr isochrone		
Whole cluster	-0.48 ± 0.11	-0.59 ± 0.08
$r < 4''.5$	-0.12 ± 0.18	-0.27 ± 0.09
$4''.5 < r < 9''$	-0.72 ± 0.17	-0.77 ± 0.13
$9'' < r < 13''.5$	-0.65 ± 0.11	-0.79 ± 0.10

Figure 2.7 Mass function derived independently in two filters (F555W in the left and F814W in the right) assuming 1.0 Myr isochrone to derive stellar luminosities. The MF is plotted for the whole cluster (red dots) and in the three different regions (core and two annuli from top to bottom).

Table 2.5 gives the MF slopes Γ for the different spatial regions, filters and assumed isochrones. The MF slopes derived from F555W and F814W photometry are consistent, with the exception of the cluster core assuming the 1 Myr isochrone. The MF slope in the core of R136 is much flatter than in the two outer annuli, in both colors and for all the assumed isochrones. The steeper slope at 1 Myr for the F814W data thus appears as an outlier that might be ignored. The flatter slope in the core may either reveal the mass segregation of the cluster or may be explained by a confusion effect in a way that massive bright objects in the dense core mask fainter low-mass stars. Between the two outer regions, however, the MF slope does not decrease from the inner to the outer annulus. Hence, either the most massive stars are concentrated in the inner core, or the confusion effect is not as acute as in the core.

Figure 2.8 Mass function derived independently in two filters (F555W in the left and F814W in the right) assuming 1.5 Myr isochrone to derive stellar luminosities. The MF is plotted for the whole cluster (red dots) and in the three different regions (core and two annuli from top to bottom).

For NGC 3603, we calculated the stellar masses starting from six different photometric datasets, three WFPC2 images with F547M, F675W, and F814W filters and three ACS/HRC images (F550M, F658N, F850LP). The derived MFs are shown in Fig. 2.10. The upper panels relate to WFPC2 data and the lower panels to HRC data. As for R136, we show the MF for the whole cluster and for three spatial regions and we fitted log-log relations with derived slopes listed in Table 2.6. While the MF slopes derived from different sets of filters and detectors are mostly consistent, a close examination suggests that the MF slope derived from WFPC2 data is somewhat steeper than the MF slope from HRC data. We may identify two competing effects that are responsible of this difference: WFPC2 data reach deeper with more low-mass stars identified in the images; on the other hand, the higher resolution of HRC (25 mas/pix) allows to resolve better close stars than on

Figure 2.9 Mass function derived independently in two filters (F555W in the left and F814W in the right) assuming 2.0 Myr isochrone to derive stellar luminosities. The MF is plotted for the whole cluster (red dots) and in the three different regions (core and two annuli from top to bottom).

WFPC2 images (50 mas/pix). Despite these differences, we point out that the general trend of MF slopes is decreasing in both datasets revealing the fingerprints of mass segregation in NGC 3603. This is illustrated more particularly in Fig. 2.11 that shows the values of MF slopes for both HRC (blue) and WFPC2 (red) data. In the inner three regions (common in both detectors), slopes trend similarly. In the outer two regions, the MF slopes in WFPC2 are even steeper.

Finally, we check the sensitivity of our derived MF with the two classes of Geneva evolutionary models, with standard (c008 and c020 models) and with enhanced mass loss rates (e008 and e020 models) for massive stars. We do not find any substantial changes in our results as illustrated in Fig. 2.12 for R136. MF slopes derived from the two colors are closer for models with enhanced mass loss and larger ages (1.5 and 2 Myr). Similar comparison for NGC 3603 is shown in Fig. 2.13

Table 2.6 Slopes of the mass function of NGC 3603 cluster (1 Myr isochrone).

WFPC2	F547M	F675W	F814W
Whole cluster	-0.86 ± 0.12	-0.89 ± 0.14	-0.90 ± 0.15
$r < 5''$	-0.37 ± 0.09	-0.42 ± 0.12	-0.30 ± 0.14
$5'' < r < 10''$	-0.83 ± 0.16	-0.80 ± 0.12	-0.77 ± 0.10
$10'' < r < 15''$	-1.11 ± 0.17	-1.14 ± 0.14	-1.08 ± 0.14
ACS/HRC	F550M	F658N	F850LP
Whole cluster	-0.58 ± 0.08	-0.60 ± 0.07	-0.73 ± 0.04
$r < 5''$	-0.40 ± 0.08	-0.47 ± 0.08	-0.49 ± 0.04
$5'' < r < 10''$	-0.73 ± 0.17	-0.74 ± 0.13	-0.74 ± 0.07
$10'' < r < 15''$	-0.78 ± 0.20	-0.71 ± 0.15	-1.01 ± 0.14

with the same kind of agreement.

2.6 Comparison with earlier analyses

Table 2.7 summarizes the results from previous determinations of the mass functions of these two young massive star clusters.

The MF slope that we derived for R136 is generally flatter than earlier published values. There is marginal consistency with the MF slope in R136 core from [Malumuth & Heap (1994)] and our value in the red F814W filter and a 1 Myr isochrone. We note however that this steeper slope in the core was considered an outlier compared to the other flatter values derived in the core. In the outer annuli, [Selman et al.(1999)] slope is consistent with our slopes derived in both colors and with the younger isochrones. We note in both cases that the MF slopes obtained using the 2 Myr isochrone – the age favored by the CMD, see Sect. 4 – are flatter than the earlier results. A direct comparison

Table 2.7 Mass function slopes for R136 and NGC 3603 from previous analyses.

R136		
MF slope	condition	Reference
-0.90	$(20 - 70) M_{\odot}, r < 3''.3$	[Malumuth & Heap (1994)]
-1.89	$(20 - 70) M_{\odot}, 3''.3 < r < 17''.5$	[Malumuth & Heap (1994)]
-1.0 ± 0.1	$(2.8 - 15) M_{\odot}, 2''.0 < r < 18''.8$	[Hunter et al. (1996)]
$(-1.3) - (-1.4)$	$(15 - 120) M_{\odot}$	[Massey & Hunter (1998)]
-1.59	$r < 1''.6$	[Brandl et al. (1996)]
-1.33	$1''.6 < r < 3''.2$	[Brandl et al. (1996)]
-1.63	$3''.2 < r$	[Brandl et al. (1996)]
-1.17 ± 0.05	$4''.6 < r < 19''.2$	[Selman et al.(1999)]
-1.37 ± 0.08	$15'' < r < 75''$	[Selman et al.(1999)]
-1.28 ± 0.05	$(2 - 6.5) M_{\odot}, 4'' \lesssim r \lesssim 20''$	[Sirianni et al. (2000)]
-1.2 ± 0.2	$(1.1 - 20) M_{\odot}, 20'' < r < 28''$	[Andersen et al. (2009)]
NGC 3603		
-0.73	$(1 - 30) M_{\odot}$	[Eisenhauer et al. (1998)]
-0.9	$(2.5 - 100) M_{\odot}$	[Sung & Bessell (2004)]
-0.5 ± 0.1	$r < 6''$	[Sung & Bessell (2004)]
-0.8 ± 0.2	$6'' - 12''$	[Sung & Bessell (2004)]
-1.2 ± 0.2	$r > 12''$	[Sung & Bessell (2004)]
-0.91 ± 0.15	$(0.4 - 20) M_{\odot}$	[Stolte et al. (2006)]
-0.31	$0 - 5''$	[Harayama et al. (2008)]
-0.55	$5'' - 10''$	[Harayama et al. (2008)]
-0.72	$10'' - 13''$	[Harayama et al. (2008)]
-0.75	$13'' - 30''$	[Harayama et al. (2008)]
-0.26	$0 - 5''$	[Pang et al. (2013)]
-0.55	$5'' - 10''$	[Pang et al. (2013)]
-0.76	$10'' - 15''$	[Pang et al. (2013)]

to explain this difference is however hindered by two main issues. First, the resolution and depth of the images are different: [Malumuth & Heap (1994)] used early (1992) WFPC observations that were not corrected for the spherical aberration of HST primary mirror, while the other studies are based on early AO observations with ground-based 4m telescopes. Second, extinction correction is difficult and possibly variable across the cluster. Our consistent results from V and I photometry increases confidence in our approach to correct extinction, although there is no clear explanation to the bimodal distribution of extinction (at 2 Myr) that we found for the 26 O-type stars with known spectral types. In all cases, however, the results show a flatter MF in the cluster core and steeper in the outer regions. [Malumuth & Heap (1994)] interpreted this result as the first indication of mass segregation in young massive clusters. We have argued that confusion from limited resolution and extinction remains major issues. These issues may hopefully be in good part solved with upcoming VLT/SPHERE observations of R136 with HST-like resolution and lower extinction in the K band.

Deriving the median of the six values tabulated in Table 2.6 for NGC 3603, we obtain $\Gamma = -0.41 \pm 0.07$ in the core region ($r < 5''$), $\Gamma = -0.76 \pm 0.04$ in the inner annulus ($5'' < r < 10''$), and $\Gamma = -1.05 \pm 0.18$ in the outer annulus ($10'' < r < 15''$). These values agree with earlier studies [Sung & Bessell (2004), Harayama et al. (2008), Pang et al. (2013)] within error bars, though we obtained consistently slightly steeper MF slopes. [Sung & Bessell (2004)] and [Pang et al. (2013)] used the same WFPC2 data in their analyses, demonstrating the sensitivity of the results to the instrumental resolution as discussed above for R136.

2.7 Summary

We have analyzed archival HST images of two young massive clusters obtained with WFPC2 and ACS/HRC with broad filters covering the visual and red spectral regions. From native multi-color HST photometry, model stellar atmospheres and stellar evolution models, we have derived the

extinction, age, the mass function and its radial dependency of the two clusters. We apply the same methodology for the two clusters, to assess our method and to compare the two clusters.

Extinction was determined for a set of over 20 O stars in both clusters. In NGC 3603, we can examine the behavior of extinction with wavelength thanks to available images in 7 different HRC filters. The extinction decreases smoothly with increasing wavelength, from the UV (220 nm) to the red (814 nm), as expected. For R136, such wavelength coverage is not available. However, the extinction shows an unexpected bimodal distribution that cannot be assigned to a spatial variation of the extinction. VLT/SPHERE data in the near-IR will be most helpful to enlighten this issue. As there is no obvious distribution of extinction over the two clusters, we assigned a unique extinction value: the median extinction for each filter of the O star samples. Based in this extinction correction, we built CMDs for both clusters and fitted Geneva isochrones. The favored ages for NGC 3603 and R136 are 1 Myr and 2 Myr, respectively, in agreement with earlier studies [Pang et al. (2013), Crowther et al. (2010)].

In both clusters, we found a more top-heavy MF than the Salpeter standard MF in agreement with earlier studies (see Sect. 6). The combined analysis of WFPC2 and higher-resolution HRC/ACS data confirm the mass segregation in NGC 3603 found in previous studies based on the WFPC2 data alone [Sung & Bessell (2004), Pang et al. (2013)]: NGC 3603 cluster core contains all massive stars with the most top-heavy MF, while the MF is steeper in outer annuli. This agreement provides good support to our method combining multi-color photometric data to derive the MF. The results for R136 are also possibly suggestive of mass segregation, though the evidence is not as strong because of uncertainties due to lower resolution from the larger distance and due to extinction.

A comparison between the two clusters is not straightforward because the larger distance of R136 means that the selected spatial regions in R136 are actually 7 times larger than the NGC 3603 regions. The mass segregation evidenced in NGC 3603 would therefore fit within the central 2" core

of R136. Nevertheless, the fact that the younger (1 Myr) and less massive ($10^4 M_{\odot}$) cluster is segregated while the older (up to 2 Myr) and more massive ($10^5 M_{\odot}$) is possibly not segregated may seem surprising. A possible scenario would be that NGC 3603 was formed during a unique burst about 1 Myr ago, while R136 might have undergone sequential star formation up to 1 Myr ago when star formation was quenched by the most massive stars ($M > 80 M_{\odot}$). If star formation was propagating spatially in the R136 and 30 Dor region, then this might explain the lack of similar evidence of mass segregation in R136. Such sequential star formation was also suggested to have taken place in the SMC young cluster NGC 346, with the most massive star MPG 355 formed less than 1 Myr ago and the late O stars formed 4 to 7 Myr ago [Bouret et al. (2003), Bouret et al. (2013)].

Figure 2.10 Mass function of NGC 3603 derived for the whole cluster (red dots) and in three different regions (from top to bottom). Top: Data from three WFCPC2 filters (F547M, F675W, F814W). Bottom: Data from three ACS/HRC filters (F550M, F658N, F850LP)

Figure 2.11 Mass function slopes of NGC 3603 derived in three WFPC2 filters (F547M, F675W, F814W from top to bottom) for the whole cluster and in three spatial regions (HRC data - dashed blue) and 5 spatial regions (WFPC2 data - solid red).

Figure 2.12 Mass function slopes of R136 derived in F555W (red) and F814W (blue) for the whole cluster and in three different regions using three different isochrones: 2, 1.5 and 1 Myr from top to bottom. Left plot is for the standard mass loss (c-models from Geneva stellar evolution models) and right plot for enhanced mass loss (e-models from Geneva stellar evolution models)

Figure 2.13 Mass function slopes of NGC 3603 derived in three WFPC2 filters (F547M, F675W, F814W from top to bottom) for the whole cluster and in three different regions. Red and blue represents standard and high mass loss from Geneva stellar evolution models (c020 and e020 models).

Top: HR 5171, a yellow hypergiant, a very rare type of stars with only a dozen known in our galaxy, discovered by Olivier Chesneau. Bottom: The artistic impression of this system.

Credit:ESO

Chapter 3

Simulations

Abstract: In the present study, we have adopted a new approach to unveil the different facets of R136. Our approach is primarily motivated by the fact that presently operated 8-10m class optical telescopes and foreseen extremely large telescopes like E-ELT should deliver diffraction limited visible and IR images of crowded field clusters such as R136.

Having this in mind we created a series of simulated images of R136 from the output of the numerical dynamical model (NBODY6 code, [Aarseth et al. (2003)]). In this work, we present the results from the comparison of the HST/WFPC2 imaging data with synthesized images from the output of the NBODY6 simulations at the age of 2 Myr. For this we used Geneva stellar evolution models [Lejeune & Schaerer (2001)] and TLUSTY [Lanz & Hubeny (2003)] or KURUCZ ([Castelli et al. (1997)] model atmospheres depending on the spectral type of stars to calculate their flux in WFPC2/F814W filter at the age of 2 Myr.

The present chapter is organized as followings. In Section 3.1 we shortly describe the NBODY6 code with special emphasis on the options and parameters that are relevant to the present work. We outline the initial conditions from which the evolution of R136 can be simulated and recorded following different tracks. Section 3.2 describes the results of these simulations, including their

observational aspects. These results are compared to the HST observations ¹ in Section 3.3. We introduce our method to create the synthetic images from the output of the NBODY6 code. For this comparison we define a number of criteria applied to simulated scenes from HST versus observed scenes. The relevance of the comparisons is then discussed in the Section 3.4. While we derive some general and preliminary results in perspective of high dynamic, high dynamic and spatially resolved images of R136 to become soon available with SPHERE and GPI in the coming years in Section 3.5 .

3.1 Modeling a young massive star cluster

We used NBODY6² code which includes the individual stellar equations of motion for all members of the cluster without any simplifying assumption and approximation ([Aarseth et al. (2003)]). We remind that NBODY6 integrates the particle orbits using the highly accurate fourth-order Hermite scheme and deals with the diverging gravitational forces in close encounters through regularizations. In addition, this code can track the evolution of the individual stars since it employs the well-tested Single Star Evolution (SSE) and Binary Star Evolution (BSE) recipes [Hurley et al. (2000), Hurley et al. (2002)].

The whole modeling intends to better understand the nature of R136 as it can be imaged nowadays, by taking into account the parameters and different mechanisms that drive the evolution of the cluster such as the degree of initial mass segregation, initial binary fraction, lower/upper stellar masses and stellar evolution. The initial parameters for R136 have been set to the values that represent the best this cluster according to its general properties.

¹Based on observations made with the NASA/ESA Hubble Space Telescope, obtained from the data archive at the Space Telescope Institute. STScI is operated by the association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc. under the NASA contract NAS 5-26555.

²<http://www.ast.cam.ac.uk/sverre/web/pages/nbody.htm>

3.1.1 Physical conditions and Mechanisms

Stellar clusters are born embedded in giant molecular clouds, with a few percent of them surviving and becoming bound clusters [Lada & Lada (2003)]. It is generally admitted that the fate of the clusters must occur during the early stages of their evolution. In massive star-burst clusters, such as R136, dynamical evolution of the cluster can be affected by their significant number of massive stars. The initial distribution of these massive stars (mass segregation) in space, specially if they form in binary systems, plays an important role on the evolution of the cluster.

In order to include such effects, we simulated full segregated clusters (in which most massive stars are located deeper in the core) versus non-segregated clusters (in which the massive stars are randomly distributed in space). The result of these simulations can tell us if R136 is more similar to an initially segregated cluster or not. A result that should put important constraints on theories of massive star formation and the cluster consequent evolution as a whole.

Following clusters without initial binaries, we also considered clusters with 30 and 60 % initial binaries which is not far from the observation as lower-limit of the spectroscopic binaries detected in the clusters of 30 Dor is found to be 45% [Bosch et al. (2009)].

Finally, by comparing the results from clusters with and without stellar evolution, one can check for the effect of stellar evolution on the binaries and the dynamical effect of the binaries themselves on the evolution of the cluster.

3.1.2 Initial conditions

Initial setup of the clusters made by MCLUSTER ³ [Kupper et al. (2011)]. The simulation time is limited to an age of 4 Myr with 0.1Myr time-steps. The total mass of the cluster is estimated by Selman & Melnick (2013) to be in the range of:

$$4.6 \times 10^4 M_{\odot} < M_{\odot} < 1.3 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$$

³<https://ahwkuepper.wordpress.com/mcluster/>

Therefore we adopt the total mass of the cluster to be $1.0 \times 10^5 M_\odot$. Kroupa IMF with mass ranging between $0.2M_\odot$ or $0.5M_\odot$ to $150M_\odot$. For the density profile we adopted Plummer model [Aarseth et al. (1974)]. Simulated clusters are assumed isolated and not impacted by tidal fields (tf=0). The initial half mass radius of the clusters is 0.8 pc. And finally the metallicity of LMC (R136) is taken as half of the solar metallicity. All the clusters are in virial equilibrium as [Henault-Brunet et al. (2012)] find that R136 is in virial equilibrium.

The set-up of the numerical experimentations is as follows: half of the clusters are segregated (s=1.0) and the others are non-segregated (s=0.0). We adopted 60%, 30% and 0% percent of initial binary for the simulated clusters. There will be two groups of clusters. These groups are totally similar to each other (even the initial position and velocity of stars) but for one group stellar evolution is ON and for other group stellar evolution is OFF to see the effect of stellar evolution Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 depicts the main characteristics of simulated clusters ⁴. The first column is the name

⁴Explanation on the naming of the clusters:

$$\underbrace{S}_1 \underbrace{10 \text{ seg}}_2 \underbrace{03 \text{ bin}}_3 \underbrace{01 \text{ m } 100}_4$$

- 1 : **S** means Stellar evolution is ON and **D** means Stellar evolution is OFF (Pure Dynamically evolution).
- 2 : Number before **seg** shows the degree of mass segregation. **10 seg** means fully segregated and **00 seg** means non-segregated.
- 3 : Number before **bin** shows the initial binary fraction. **03 bin** means 0.3 binary fraction (30 percent of binaries) and **00 bin** means no initial binaries.
- 4 : The numbers before and after **m** shows the mass range. The first number before **m** can be **01** which means the low mass cutoff is $0.1M_\odot$ or it can be **10** which means the low mass cutoff is $1.0M_\odot$ and the second number after **m** can be **100** which means the maximum mass of the particles is $100M_\odot$ or it can be **300** which mean the maximum mass is $300M_\odot$.

So name **S10seg03bin01m100** stand for a cluster with stellar evolution is ON and it is fully segregated with 0.3 binary fraction and mass range between $0.1M_\odot$ to $100M_\odot$. Also **D00seg00bin10m300** means this cluster evolves just

of the cluster. The second column says if stellar evolution is ON or OFF. Column 3 corresponds to the degree of mass segregation, 0.0 means non-segregation and 1.0 means the cluster is fully segregated. The fourth column corresponds to the binary fraction. The fifth column defines the number of initial binaries. M_{min} and M_{max} are the lower and upper mass cutoff respectively of initial mass function (The canonical Kroupa, [Kroupa (2001)]) and N is the initial number of stars.

For the initial number of binaries we used random pairing but separate pairing for components with $m > m_{sort}$. In this way, pairing of primary and secondary components of binary stars above m_{sort} are randomly paired among each other. The motivation for this lies in extensive observational data showing that massive O, B stars are more likely to be found in an equal mass binary system [Sana & Evans (2011)]. m_{sort} is equal to $5M_{\odot}$ in agreement with [Kobulnicky & Fryer (2007)]. More detail about semi-major axis and period distribution of binaries can be found in section 3.2.3.

The period distribution was taken from the [Kroupa (1995)] period distribution since it unifies the observed Galactic field and pre-main sequence populations (see also [Kroupa (2008)]). But for massive binaries with $M_{primary} > m_{sort}$ we used the period distribution from Sana&Evans 2011 since the period distribution of massive O,B spectroscopic binaries has been found to be significantly different from what is observed for low-mass binaries [Sana & Evans (2011)]. Massive binaries are found to have short periods in the range from 2 days to 10 years with a peak at 10 days.

Eccentricities are assumed to have a thermal distribution i.e. $f(e)=2e$ [Kroupa (2008)] and for the eccentricities of high mass binaries the distribution is taken according to [Sana & Evans (2011)], leading to the computation of the semi-major axis (a) of each binary.

Dynamically without stellar evolution and it is not initially segregated without any initial binaries and mass range between $1.0M_{\odot}$ to $300M_{\odot}$.

Model	SE	Seg	BF	N_{bin}	M_{min}	M_{max}	N
S00seg00bin05m150	ON	0.0	0.0	0	0.5	150	55992
D00seg00bin05m150	OFF	0.0	0.0	0	0.5	150	55992
S10seg00bin05m150	ON	1.0	0.0	0	0.5	150	55815
D10seg00bin05m150	OFF	1.0	0.0	0	0.5	150	55815
S00seg03bin05m150	ON	0.0	0.3	8404	0.5	150	56032
D00seg03bin05m150	OFF	0.0	0.3	8404	0.5	150	56032
S10seg03bin05m150	ON	1.0	0.3	8536	0.5	150	56908
D10seg03bin05m150	OFF	1.0	0.3	8536	0.5	150	56908
S00seg06bin05m150	ON	0.0	0.6	17000	0.5	150	56669
D00seg06bin05m150	OFF	0.0	0.6	17000	0.5	150	56669
S10seg06bin05m150	ON	1.0	0.6	16686	0.5	150	55622
D10seg06bin05m150	OFF	1.0	0.6	16686	0.5	150	55622
S00seg00bin02m150	ON	0.0	0.0	0	0.2	150	105666
D00seg00bin02m150	OFF	0.0	0.0	0	0.2	150	105666
S10seg00bin02m150	ON	1.0	0.0	0	0.2	150	107722
D10seg00bin02m150	OFF	1.0	0.0	0	0.2	150	107722
S00seg03bin02m150	ON	0.0	0.3	16134	0.2	150	107565
D00seg03bin02m150	OFF	0.0	0.3	16134	0.2	150	107565
S10seg03bin02m150	ON	1.0	0.3	16084	0.2	150	107230
D10seg03bin02m150	OFF	1.0	0.3	16084	0.2	150	107230
S00seg06bin02m150	ON	0.0	0.6	32225	0.2	150	107419
D00seg06bin02m150	OFF	0.0	0.6	32225	0.2	150	107419
S10seg06bin02m150	ON	1.0	0.6	32309	0.2	150	107698
D10seg06bin02m150	OFF	1.0	0.6	32309	0.2	150	107698

Table 3.1 Different simulated clusters grouped by minimum mass. Total mass of the clusters is $10^5 M_{\odot}$. Summary of naming convention for these simulated clusters is explained hereafter:

3.2 Results of the simulations

3.2.1 Expansion of the cluster

Figure 3.1 shows the evolution of half mass radii of 24 simulated clusters in 4 Myr. The upper plots correspond to clusters with a mass distribution in the range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and bottom plots correspond to clusters with mass distribution in the range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. From left to right the plots depict clusters with 0%, 30% and 60% initial binaries. It can be seen in all plots that segregated clusters expand more than non-segregated ones due to dynamical interactions. Stellar evolution plays also an important role in the expansion of the cluster, especially around 3-3.5 Myr on the evolution of massive stars and their high mass-loss. The expansion due to the stellar evolution (mass-loss) is larger than the expansion due to initial segregation, unless there are binary systems. Dynamical interaction for the clusters with binaries is very significant. So segregated clusters which contains binaries expand remarkably even if the stellar evolution is OFF for them (red-dashed lines in the middle and left plots in Figure 3.1).

Clusters which contain more massive stars, present a larger expansion. This can be checked by comparing the half-mass radius evolution of clusters with pure dynamical evolution (D-clusters). At the same time, changing the binary fraction does not affect the expansion of the clusters in a significant way.

3.2.2 Escapers and cluster's mass loss

Clusters lose mass due to escaping stars and also if stellar evolution is ON, which drives the mass-loss of massive stars. Figure 3.2 to 3.4 show the total mass loss of each cluster per time-step. In these figures, top plot correspond to 4 clusters in the mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and bottom plot for 4 clusters with the mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. The numbers at the top of each bin correspond to the number of escapers. In each plot, all 4 clusters have similar initial total mass,

Figure 3.1 Half-mass radius evolution of different clusters within 4 Myr. Up: mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Down: $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Left: No initial binaries, Middle: 30% initial binaries, Right: 60% initial binaries. Green and Blue: Non-segregated; Pink and Red: Segregated.

mass-range and binary fraction. But they differ in initial segregation and stellar evolution. In each plot, from top to bottom, 4 clusters stand for initially: 1) Non-segregated with stellar evolution (Green), 2) Segregated with stellar evolution (Pink), 3) Non-segregated without stellar evolution (Blue) and 4) Segregated without stellar evolution (Red).

Figure 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 represent clusters with 0%, 30% and 60% initial binaries.

The mass-loss of the clusters with stellar evolution (hereafter call S-clusters) is much larger than the clusters without stellar evolution (here after call D-clusters) especially around time 3.5 Myr which is a time when massive stars ($M > 60M_{\odot}$) turn out to supernova events. Clusters on the left with $M_{min} = 0.5M_{\odot}$ contain indeed more massive stars than clusters at the right (with $M_{min} = 0.2M_{\odot}$), so for these clusters mass loss is more than for clusters with $M_{min} = 0.2M_{\odot}$. that for D-clusters the number of escapers increases with the increasing binary fraction.

3.2.3 Binary fraction

Figure 3.5 shows the fraction of bound binary systems for different clusters versus time. Segregated clusters lose less binaries than non-segregated clusters. It seems that the segregated clusters are safer places for binaries to be survive. It can be explain by two main reasons: Location of the binaries and their neighbors.

In segregated clusters binaries are located deeper in the cluster and they interact mostly with the same-mass neighbors so the chance to be disrupted by single massive star and massive binaries decreases in segregated clusters. Also when a binary is disrupted in the segregated cluster, If it is going to be ejected/evaporated from cluster, It has to pass from a outer layer of the cluster which is contaminated by single stars. This star still has a chance to interact with single stars and remain in the cluster which decreases the evaporation probability. This is not a case for Non-segregated clusters.

For clusters with 30% binaries it can be seen that if they contain more low mass stars and less

Figure 3.2 Total mass loss of the clusters (with 0% initial binaries) per time-step. Top: mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Bottom: mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. The numbers at the top of each bin correspond to the number of escapers. Green and Blue: non-segregated; Pink and Red: Segregated. Stellar evolution is ON for Green and Red, and OFF for blue and Red.

Figure 3.3 Total mass loss of the clusters (with 30% initial binaries) per time-step. Top: mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Bottom: mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. The numbers at the top of each bin correspond to the number of escapers. Green and Blue: non-segregated; Pink and Red: Segregated. Stellar evolution is ON for Green and Red, and OFF for blue and Red.

Figure 3.4 Total mass loss of the clusters (with 60% initial binaries) per time-step. Top: mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Bottom: mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. The numbers at the top of each bin correspond to the number of escapers. Green and Blue: non-segregated; Pink and Red: Segregated. Stellar evolution is ON for Green and Red, and OFF for blue and Red.

massive binaries (the case of clusters with $M_{min} = 0.2M_{\odot}$), they lose more binaries than clusters with $M_{min} = 0.5M_{\odot}$.

Figure 3.5 Fraction of bound binary systems for different clusters in each time-steps. Left, Up: clusters with mass range of $1.0M_{\odot} - 100M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries. Right, Up: clusters with mass range of $1.0M_{\odot} - 300M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries. Left, Down: clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries. Right, Down: clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 60% Initial binaries. Green and Blue: non-segregated; Pink and Red: Segregated. Stellar evolution is ON for Green and Red, and OFF for blue and Red.

3.2.4 Periods and eccentricities

Figures 3.6 to 3.9 shows the histogram of periods in units of days (logarithmic) in six time-steps for 16 clusters. These clusters have similar initial total mass but they differ in the number of initial binaries and mass-range. 1) Figure 3.6 belongs to 4 clusters with 30% initial binaries and mass-range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Figure 3.8 is similar to Figure 3.6 but with the mass-range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$. Finally Figure 3.7 and 3.9 are similar to previous plots but with 60% initial binaries.

Different colors represent different times. For example red plot is at the time of 0.0 Myr which is the initial distribution of periods that we have chosen according to observations reported in literature (see Section 3.1.2). It is a bimodal distribution, for low mass binaries it is Kroupa distribution and for massive O, B binaries it is Sana&Evans 2011 which exhibits in its a first part a peak around 10 days.

Evolution of the first part is according to stellar evolution, that is why it is not visible in D-clusters. Evolution of second part is according to the dynamics of the cluster, that is wht we see this for both S-clusters and D-clusters.

Almost half of the low-mass binaries dissolve within 1 Myr.

Figures 3.10 to 3.13 show the evolution of eccentricity distributions in 6 time-steps for the same 16 clusters that the histogram of periods were plotted (Figures 3.6 to 3.9). Initial distribution ($T = 0.0$ Myr) is the red plot. Like the period distribution, eccentricities also have a bimodal distributions, for low-mass and massive binaries (with a peak close to $e=0.0$). Stellar evolution, affects the evolution of the first peak (for massive binaries) that is why for D-clusters the peak does not evolve. For low-mass binaries, during the evolution (in different time-steps) the distribution keeps the memory of the initial distribution for different eccentricities.

For period distribution, after 2-3 Myr the new distribution could keep the memory of initial distribution of massive binaries not for low-mass binaries. But for eccentricity distribution, cluster

keeps the memory of initial distribution of eccentricities.

Figure 3.6 Histogram of the Log(period [days]) of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries.

3.3 Comparison with observations

For R136, the main observational data result from imaging in different filters. From these data, one can estimate the mass of stars and compare the density profile with simulations. In such an approach errors can dramatically increase from converting magnitudes to mass as the theoretical evolutionary models may not provide enough information for very massive and Wolf-Rayet stars

Figure 3.7 Histogram of the Log(period [days]) of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 60% Initial binaries.

specially. On the other hand, we probably cannot detect many low mass stars during the photometry. Moreover, if the detected object is a binary then estimated mass is biased.

At this point of our study we prefer to produce the imaging data from the simulations with the spatial resolution of HST/WFPC2 data from R136. HST/WFPC2 observations of R136 were carried out on 1994-09-25 (PI: Westphal), from which we use a combination of shallow, intermediate and long exposures ranging from 3–5 s to 80–120 s with the planetary camera (PC) and the F814W filter. So we wrote a code which reads the information of stars from the NBODY6 simulations as an input and creates the synthetic scenes that mimic HST/WFPC2 resolution in different HST

Figure 3.8 Histogram of the Log(period [days]) of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries.

filters. During this simulation we also need proper stellar evolution models and atmospheric models for calculating Bolometric Correction (BC) of different HST/WFPC2 filters. We created sets of BC tables (see Chapter 2) at the age of 2 Myr using Geneva stellar evolution models⁵ [Lejeune & Schaerer (2001)]. For calculating BCs we used SEDs from TLUSTY atmosphere models for O and B stars⁶ [Hubeny & Lanz (1995), Lanz & Hubeny (2003), Lanz & Hubeny (2007)] and KURUCZ⁷ [Castelli et al. (1997)] for the rest of the stellar types with a half-solar metallicity ap-

⁵<http://webast.ast.obs-mip.fr/equipe/stellar/>

⁶Model atmospheres and source codes are available at <http://nova.astro.umd.edu>

⁷ATLAS9 Kurucz ODFNEW /NOVER models

Figure 3.9 Histogram of the Log(period [days]) of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 60% Initial binaries.

appropriate for LMC stars. TLUSTY provides grids of non-LTE, metal line-blanketed, plane-parallel, hydrostatic model atmospheres which is well suited for the very massive stars specially in visible and near-IR.

At a given time (2 Myr) it is possible to calculate the flux (in different HST filters) for each star in the simulation using computed BC tables. We simulated a 800×800 pixels scene corresponding to a field of $32.5'' \times 32.5''$ on the detector where a star with a given flux falls on the detector with a Gaussian distribution as the PSF profile.

Figure 3.15-3.18 show synthetic scenes of 12 simulated clusters at time 2 Myr both in XY and

Figure 3.10 Histogram of the eccentricity of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries.

XZ plane. One can compare the synthetic images with real HST/WFPC2 data on R136 shown in Figure 3.14. Both images are in F814W filters.

However the question is at what degree a simulated cluster with thousands of stars within a given volume projected once on the sky to reproduce HST image of R136. What is the best criterion to select the closest simulated cluster to R136?

One useful way is to compare the Surface Brightness Profile (SBP) of R136 to those of synthetic scenes (Section 5.5). It is also possible to compare the Half-Light radius (R_{hl}) of R136 and synthetic scenes (Section 3.3.3). In Section 3.3.2 we compared the Mass Function (MF) slopes of

Figure 3.11 Histogram of the eccentricity of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.5M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 60% Initial binaries.

R136 with the MF slopes from simulations. The MF is not directly derived from simulation. The mass of stars in the FoV is estimated by the photometry on the synthetic scenes and we used the BC-tables for finding the mass of each detected star in a given field. In Section 3.3.4 we introduce a new definition for double checking. In this section we calculate a neighbor radius ($R_{neighbor}$) of each star in each cluster which is a radius containing for example, 100 neighbor stars. In a crowded regions (in the core) this radius is very short for each star while in outer regions it can be larger.

Figure 3.12 Histogram of the eccentricity of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 30% Initial binaries.

3.3.1 SBP of R136

Figure 3.19 shows the SBP of R136. It can be seen that at some radial distances from the core of the cluster the SBP suddenly increases with a significant deviation from the general trend. We checked for the distribution of the spectral type of R136 stars in the FoV of HST/WFPC2-PC imaging data and we found 9 WR stars. Figure 3.19 shows the radii at which a given WR is detected.

For synthetic scenes we have calculated the SBPs in the same regions as R136. Figure 3.20 and 3.21 shows the SBPs of the simulated R136 versus its simulated twin (pink stars).

To determine the closest SBP value of the simulated to the observed R136 we calculated the

Figure 3.13 Histogram of the eccentricity of bound binary systems in 6 time-steps (0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 3.5 and 3.9 Myr) for 4 clusters with mass range of $0.2M_{\odot} - 150M_{\odot}$ and 60% Initial binaries.

χ^2 for each cluster in three regions in addition to the whole cluster. Table 3.2 (simulated scenes in XZ plane) and Table 3.3 (simulated scenes in XY plane) depict the χ^2 values. Clusters with the smallest value have an SBP more closer to that of R136. Thus the non-segregated clusters match better R136 in all regions.

3.3.2 MF slopes

After having created series of synthetic scenes, in the first step photometry on each image have to be done. For the photometry on HST/WFPC2 data and also on the synthetic images we used

Figure 3.14 Synthetic scenes from simulation of S-clusters with the mass range of $(0.2 - 150)M_{\odot}$ and 0% initial binaries at time 2 Myr. Not segregated: Left images; Segregated clusters: Middle images; Top is in XZ plane and bottom is in XY plane. R136 image taken by HST/WFPC2-PC in F814W filter is in the Right top.

Figure 3.15 Synthetic scenes from simulation of S-clusters with the mass range of $(0.5 - 150)M_{\odot}$ at time 2 Myr in XZ plane. Not segregated: Upper images; Segregated clusters: Bottom images; 0% initial binaries: left; 30% initial binaries: middle; 60% initial binaries: right

Figure 3.16 Synthetic scenes from simulation of S-clusters with the mass range of $(0.2 - 150)M_{\odot}$ at time 2 Myr in XZ plane. Not segregated: Upper images; Segregated clusters: Bottom images; 0% initial binaries: left; 30% initial binaries: middle; 60% initial binaries: right

Figure 3.17 Same as Figure 3.15 but in XY plane.

Figure 3.18 Same as Figure 3.16 but in XY plane.

Figure 3.19 SBP of R136 in two filters F814W and F555W. 9 WR stars are shown in the plot.

Figure 3.20 SBP from simulations at time 2 Myr for different sets of clusters in a mass range of $(0.2 - 150)M_{\odot}$. Top is the synthetic scenes created in XZ plan and Bottom belongs to XY plan. Solid lines belong to initial non-segregated clusters and dashed lines represent initial segregated clusters.

Pink stars shows the SBP of R136 from WFPC2-PC data. Reddening is corrected for the HST data.

Figure 3.21 SBP from simulations at time 2 Myr for different sets of clusters in a mass range of $(0.5 - 150)M_{\odot}$. Top is the synthetic scenes created in XZ plan and Bottom belongs to XY plan. Solid lines belong to initial non-segregated clusters and dashed lines represent initial segregated clusters.

Pink stars shows the SBP of R136 from WFPC2-PC data. Reddening is corrected for the HST data.

0.2 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.165	0.105	0.114	0.244	0.339	0.275
reg2:	0.311	0.592	0.420	3.600	3.514	3.232
reg3:	2.002	2.233	2.258	8.679	11.800	8.542
total:	2.469	2.682	2.602	12.412	14.685	11.389
0.5 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.234	0.279	0.200	0.315	0.327	0.379
reg2:	0.283	0.481	0.311	1.562	1.538	1.776
reg3:	1.368	1.533	1.339	8.448	7.462	4.861
total:	1.839	2.186	1.846	10.008	9.226	6.498

Table 3.2 χ^2 of SBP of simulated scenes at 2 Myr in XZ plane in three different regions and for the whole cluster. The smallest value is the closest one to SBP of R136.

0.2 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.134	0.121	0.109	0.297	0.288	0.292
reg2:	0.314	0.346	0.233	3.535	3.247	3.147
reg3:	2.246	2.988	2.469	9.672	11.517	11.688
total:	2.646	3.444	2.808	12.837	14.238	14.153
0.5 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.199	0.277	0.201	0.364	0.312	0.352
reg2:	0.268	0.388	0.334	2.085	2.056	1.620
reg3:	1.250	1.712	2.109	8.941	7.852	7.393
total:	1.680	2.278	2.644	10.902	9.824	9.145

Table 3.3 χ^2 of SBP of simulated scenes at 2 Myr in XY plane in three different regions and for the whole cluster. The smallest value is the closest one to SBP of R136.

STARFINDER ([Diolaiti et al. (2000)]) to extract the sources using analytical prepared Point Spread Function (PSF) related to the F814W filter. For HST/WFPC2-F814W we extracted 2660 stars and for the synthetic images, we extracted from 1759 up to 3193 sources depending on the scene. Using BC tables (explained in Section 3.3), we estimated the photometric mass of detected stars in each imaging data for different clusters. Furthermore we computed the MF for each simulated cluster at the evolution time of 2 Myr as following:

$$\log(N) = a \log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right) + b$$

Table 3.4 and 3.5, for the scenes in XZ and XY planes respectively, show the MF slopes for three regions ($r < 4''.5$, $4''.5 < r < 9''$, $9'' < r < 13.5''$) and also for the whole cluster at time of 2 Myr. MF slope of R136 in the same filter is as follow (see Figure 2.12 at 2 Myr with standard mass loss models.):

$$r < 4''.5 : a = -0.39 \pm 0.24$$

$$4''.5 < r < 9'' : a = -1.18 \pm 0.21$$

$$9'' < r < 13.5'' : a = -0.97 \pm 0.09$$

$$\text{For the whole FoV: } a = -0.89 \pm 0.14$$

To better compare the slopes Figure 3.22 on can compare them MF between simulations and R136 (Black solid line). In region 2 and 3 non-segregated simulated clusters exhibit closer values to the observed MF of R136.

3.3.3 Half-light radius

In a next step, we estimated the half-light radius (R_{hl}) of R136 versus those of synthetic scenes from the simulations at time 2 Myr.

In order to compare the simulated scenes to the observed R136 we computed R_{hl} in the same FoV as to HST imaging data (32.5"x32.5" in terms of PC). Corresponding results are outlined in Table 3.6. It can be seen that, unlike what $R_{half-mass}$ shows in the simulations, non-segregated

0.2 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Not segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.06 ± 0.67	-0.06 ± 0.32	-0.03 ± 0.35	-0.23 ± 0.26	-0.31 ± 0.15	-0.19 ± 0.24
reg2:	-1.43 ± 0.15	-1.14 ± 0.17	-1.16 ± 0.28	-1.65 ± 0.02	-1.64 ± 0.13	-1.68 ± 0.15
reg3:	-1.32 ± 0.14	-1.06 ± 0.23	-1.31 ± 0.20	-1.44 ± 0.02	-1.58 ± 0.05	-1.47 ± 0.58
total:	-0.77 ± 0.09	-0.69 ± 0.15	-0.68 ± 0.19	-0.64 ± 0.06	-0.67 ± 0.16	-0.67 ± 0.67
0.5 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non-segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.13 ± 0.60	0.31 ± 0.54	0.11 ± 0.49	-0.04 ± 0.59	-0.08 ± 0.36	-0.09 ± 0.24
reg2:	-1.18 ± 0.11	-1.26 ± 0.40	-1.01 ± 0.14	-1.89 ± 0.24	-1.64 ± 0.26	-1.69 ± 0.29
reg3:	-1.17 ± 0.06	-1.33 ± 0.22	-1.22 ± 0.13	-1.79 ± 0.01	-2.54 ± 0.17	-1.20 ± 0.69
total:	-0.72 ± 0.04	-0.61 ± 0.22	-0.65 ± 0.10	-0.70 ± 0.04	-0.71 ± 0.15	-0.70 ± 0.12

Table 3.4 MF's slopes from simulated scenes at 2 Myr in XZ plane in three different regions and also for the the whole cluster.

0.2 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non-segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.01 ± 0.43	-0.05 ± 0.37	0.00 ± 0.54	-0.24 ± 0.23	-0.28 ± 0.29	-0.21 ± 0.21
reg2:	-1.42 ± 0.26	-1.18 ± 0.29	-1.26 ± 0.84	-2.03 ± 0.49	-1.64 ± 0.47	-1.61 ± 0.30
reg3:	-1.28 ± 0.01	-1.29 ± 0.29	-1.38 ± 0.43	-1.60 ± 0.44	-1.78 ± 0.28	-1.37 ± 0.29
total:	-0.75 ± 0.03	-0.70 ± 0.17	-0.73 ± 0.19	-0.66 ± 0.08	-0.68 ± 0.17	-0.65 ± 0.07
0.5 – 150 M_{\odot}						
Non-segregated			Segregated			
Binary:	0%	30%	60%	0%	30%	60%
reg1:	0.12 ± 0.62	0.11 ± 0.29	0.17 ± 0.46	-0.10 ± 0.41	-0.10 ± 0.35	0.01 ± 0.40
reg2:	-1.22 ± 0.11	-1.23 ± 0.15	-1.12 ± 0.20	-1.69 ± 0.10	-1.80 ± 0.28	-1.73 ± 0.35
reg3:	-1.32 ± 0.12	-1.29 ± 0.27	-1.06 ± 0.42	-1.99 ± 0.02	-1.49 ± 1.11	-1.93 ± 0.65
total:	-0.75 ± 0.05	-0.66 ± 0.12	-0.62 ± 0.13	-0.71 ± 0.07	-0.72 ± 0.14	-0.68 ± 0.13

Table 3.5 MF's slopes from simulated scenes at 2 Myr in XY plane in three different regions and also for the the whole cluster.

Figure 3.22 MF Slopes from simulated synthetic scenes at 2 Myrs in XZ (Top plots) and XY (Bottom plots) plane. Black solid lines belong to R136 from HST/WFPC2 data taken in F814W filter. Blue, Green and Red represents clusters with 0%, 30% and 60% initial binaries.

Model	Seg	BF	M_{min}	M_{max}	$R_{hl}(XY)$	$R_{hl}(XZ)$
			$[M_{\odot}]$	$[M_{\odot}]$	[pc]	[pc]
S00seg00bin05m150	0.0	0.0	0.5	150	0.43	0.50
S10seg00bin05m150	1.0	0.0	0.5	150	0.30	0.28
S00seg03bin05m150	0.0	0.3	0.5	150	0.40	0.43
S10seg03bin05m150	1.0	0.3	0.5	150	0.26	0.26
S00seg06bin05m150	0.0	0.6	0.5	150	0.46	0.48
S10seg06bin05m150	1.0	0.6	0.5	150	0.29	0.26
S00seg00bin02m150	0.0	0.0	0.2	150	0.42	0.43
S10seg00bin02m150	1.0	0.0	0.2	150	0.27	0.27
S00seg03bin02m150	0.0	0.3	0.2	150	0.36	0.38
S10seg03bin02m150	1.0	0.3	0.2	150	0.23	0.25
S00seg06bin02m150	0.0	0.6	0.2	150	0.42	0.43
S10seg06bin02m150	1.0	0.6	0.2	150	0.25	0.27

Table 3.6 R_{hl} calculated for different simulated scenes at 2Myr in XY and XZ plane.

clusters have larger half light radii than segregated ones.

At time 2Myr, clusters with $M_{min} = 0.5M_{\odot}$ have larger R_{hl} than clusters with $M_{min} = 0.2M_{\odot}$. It means that clusters with larger number of low-mass (high-mass) stars have smaller (larger) half-light radius. Also R_{hl} of the clusters with 0% and 60% initial binaries are more close together and both are larger than clusters with 30% initial binaries.

3.3.4 Neighbor radius

Neighbor radius ($R_{neighbor}$) is an arbitrary distance to find 100 neighbor stars from a given star. In the core of the cluster that has a higher stellar density, this radius is smaller than in the outer

regions of the cluster. For R136 we calculated this radius for all the sources that have been detected in the HST image. We carried the same procedure on every simulated scene, with different characteristics, i.e. segregated or not, different binary fractions, etc... both in XY and XZ planes. Figure 3.23 and 3.24 depict the corresponding results. Red dots in each plot correspond to R136, Green and Blue dots correspond to not-segregated and segregated clusters. One can conclude that for all the simulated scenes, non-segregated clusters better fit to the R136 by HST considering the general trend of the slope.

3.4 Discussion of the results

We carried out a study of R136 in two steps. In a first and as exhaustive as possible step based on the NBODY6 code, we simulated a grid of synthetic young starburst compact clusters similar to R136, starting from its state-of-the-art basic parameters: i.e. age, distance, luminosity of individual member stars. In a second step we selected the likeliest synthesized images of R136 that match the observed visible wavelengths data from HST. The choice of this image provides a set of physical properties that explain best the expansion, the mass loss of the stellar populations in R136 as well as their binary fraction for instance.

Regarding the expansion of the cluster we found that in all cases segregated clusters expand more than non-segregated clusters, and that the former have larger R_h than the latter. Clusters with stellar evolution (S-clusters) expand significantly around 3 Myr because of the evolution of very massive stars, that possess for some of them extreme winds of $10^{-8} - 10^{-5} [M_{\odot}/\text{yr}]$ [Lamers& Cassinelli (1999)]. Clusters with dynamical evolution (D-clusters) alone expand more due to the presence of more massive stars.

Regarding the mass loss of the cluster and escapers: the total mass loss of S-clusters is larger than for D-clusters. This is due to the evolution of massive stars themselves whilst D-clusters

Figure 3.23 $R_{neighbor}$ of simulated scenes in XZ-plane compare to R136 (Red dots). Blue and Green dots belong to the Segregated and Non-Segregated clusters. Left: clusters with the mass range of $(0.2 - 150)M_{\odot}$ and Right plots are for $(0.5 - 150)M_{\odot}$. Upper, middle and bottom plot represents clusters with 0%, 30% and 60% initial binaries.

Figure 3.24 $R_{neighbor}$ of simulated scenes in XY-plane compare to R136 (Red dots). Blue and Green dots belong to the Segregated and Non-Segregated clusters. Left: clusters with the mass range of $(0.2 - 150)M_{\odot}$ and Right plots are for $(0.5 - 150)M_{\odot}$. Upper, middle and bottom plot represents clusters with 0%, 30% and 60% initial binaries.

undergo escapers loss only. S-clusters containing more massive stars, present a larger mass loss in their early stages of evolution. D-clusters lose more escapers as the binary fraction increases.

On the other hand segregated clusters lose less binaries than non-segregated ones and in the special case of clusters with 30% initial binaries made of low-mass stars, the binary loss is significantly larger.

Concerning periods and eccentricities: almost half of the low-mass binaries dissolve within 1 Myr. Clusters with stellar evolution lose their massive binaries according to the evolution of massive stars themselves. In all cases binaries keep the memory of initial eccentricities distribution during the first 4 Myr. For this period, only the massive binaries keep the memory of initial period distribution.

Having these general properties in mind we used synthetic scenes with the same observational resolution as HST/WFPC2-PC/F814W. For this purpose we computed a grid of bolometric correction tables which provide the flux of different stars in F814W filter using Geneva stellar evolution models and model atmosphere (TLUSTY for O,B stars and Kurucz for other spectral types). These synthetic images have the same pixel scale, spatial resolution and FoV of WFPC2 data on R136.

To conclude on the best R136 from its synthesized images we used 4 different criteria based on: SBP, MF's slopes, R_{hl} and R_{conf} .

We calculated the surface brightness profiles (SBP) of R136 and the synthetic scenes (in both XY and XZ planes). A χ^2 criterion on the SBP permits to chose can the most probable synthesized R136 in three different regions and also for the whole cluster. SBP, R_{hl} can easily be driven for each scene. Thus, using the photometry on each synthesized R136 image, we derived the mass of detected sources and plotted the mass function (MF) and $R_{neighbor}$.

Using the 4 criteria all together, even though they are not completely independent, we conclude that R136 is best represented by a non-segregated cluster (in $r < 4\text{pc}$).

This result can explain the dominant mechanism for the formation of very massive stars among

two main formation scenarios of gas accretion and collision between less massive stars that are explained in details by [Krumholz (2015)]. Initially a non-segregated cluster cannot provide sufficient dense conditions and a higher mean stellar mass in the core, for collisions to occur before the final stages of massive stars evolution. Presently, no convincing evidence exists such as fragmentation, radiation pressure, photoionization and stellar winds to stop the growth of stars by accretion [Krumholz (2015)]. So initially non-segregated clusters may better explain the formation of massive stars by accretion.

Effectively, accretion based models predict the low-mass companions, in addition to their massive companions, at separation of 100-1000 AU [Kratter & Matzner (2006), Kratter et al. (2008), Kratter et al. (2010), Krumholz et al. (2012)] while the collisionally-formed stars will lack low-mass companions. These companions can be observationally detected by using high angular resolution and high contrast instruments like VLT/SPHERE [Zurlo et al. (2014)], the future E-ELT where R136 would be resolved as NGC3603 by the VLT and NGC3603 resolved by the VLT as the Trapezium cluster in Orion by a 1-2m class telescope.

Note that for the comparison of synthesized versus observed images of R136, we considered the median value of the extinction (in F814W filter) derived from 26 known O-type stars in the FoV of the HST data (Khorrami et al. in prep). If the spatial distribution of dust were taken into account according to the real position of massive stars in the cluster, the effect of confusion would even be worse. Since massive stars are expected to clear out dust from their neighborhood, the extinction would affect the low mass stars specially. This would make them undetectable in the visible wavelengths, that introduces an additional bias on the HST images reinforcing the segregation scenario for R136 [Ascenso et al. (2009)].

3.5 Summary

In this work we proposed a new approach to compare the results of the NBODY6 code with data from high contrast imaging observations obtained on large optical telescopes at their diffraction limit. In previous studies, the direct output of the code is compared with observational material where one compares for example the density profile of hundred thousands of stars with the density of a few thousands of them extracted from observations in practice. Our method is rather based on synthesizing the observations directly from NBODY6 itself. These synthesized images are matched to real observations in a final step for their likeliness.

We based our study on data taken from HST/WFPC2 archives. For this we produced simulated scenes at the resolution of HST/WFPC2-pc/F814W images) and created BC tables which provide the flux of different stars in F814W filter using Geneva stellar evolution models and TLUSTY atmosphere model for O,B stars and Kurucz model for other spectral types. These synthetic images have the same pixel scale, spatial resolution and FoV as the WFPC2 data of R136 from HST. Note that our modeling of stellar members atmospheres could be improved by considering more appropriate atmosphere codes for the WR components of R136, for example using grids of model atmosphere like TLUSTY but including winds [Neugent et al. (2015)]. On the other hand our synthesized R136 clusters could be improved for their evolution by adding time-space depending gas potential to the model. This could ideally be included in NBODY6 code itself (private communication R. Wunsch).

In summary our study is in favor of the R136 to be a non-segregated cluster: a result contradicting the generally accepted picture. A result that deserves more exhaustive and systematic observations of R136 to be conclusive. Such observations should be carried out in as many spectral bands as possible: from the visible to optical and thermal IR wavelengths to overcome the confusion effect specially. This becomes possible using the VLT and high contrast AO imaging in the optical, future observations from space (JWST) or the E-ELT [Zinnecker (2006)]. Ultimately

long baseline imaging interferometry from the ground should enable us to resolve the stellar binary components of R136 or similar compact clusters.

ESO's Paranal Observatory. The first photograph from the ESO Ultra HD Expedition. The four Unit Telescopes, Antu, Kueyen, Melipal and Yepun, one of the Auxiliary Telescopes of the Very Large Telescope (VLT) and the VLT Survey Telescope (VST), are captured from an unusual perspective in this image. Taken by a fish-eye lens, this photography technique produces a 360 degree view of the location, creating an immersive Paranal world with the swirling Milky Way at the centre of it.

Credit: ESO/B.Tafreshi (twanight.org)

Chapter 4

VLT/SPHERE Photometry on NGC3603

Abstract: In this chapter we present new near-infrared photometric measurements of the core of the young massive cluster NGC 3603 obtained with extreme adaptive optics. The data were obtained with the SPHERE instrument mounted on ESO's Very Large Telescope, and cover three fields in the core of this cluster. We applied a correction for the effect of extinction to our data obtained in the J and K broadband filters and estimated the mass of detected sources inside the field of view of SPHERE/IRDIS, which is $13.5'' \times 13.5''$. We derived the mass function (MF) slope for each spectral band and field. The MF slope in the core is unusual compared to previous results based on Hubble space telescope (HST) and very large telescope (VLT) observations. The average slope in the core is estimated as -1.06 ± 0.26 for the main sequence stars with $3.5 M_{\odot} < M < 120 M_{\odot}$. Thanks to the SPHERE extreme adaptive optics, 814 low-mass stars were detected to estimate the MF slope for the pre-main sequence stars with $0.6 M_{\odot} < M < 3.5 M_{\odot}$, $\Gamma = -0.54 \pm 0.11$ in the K-band images in two fields in the core of the cluster. For the first time, we derive the mass function of the very core of the NGC 3603 young cluster for masses in the range 0.6 - 120 M_{\odot} . Previous studies were either limited by crowding, lack of dynamic range, or a combination of both.

4.1 Introduction

Among Galactic spiral arm clusters, the NGC 3603 young cluster, located in its namesake giant HII region [Kennicutt (1984)], is the most compact and youngest cluster with an age of 1 Myr [Brandl et al. (1999), Stolte et al. (2004), Sung & Bessell (2004)] and a central density of $6 \times 10^4 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ pc}^{-3}$ [Harayama et al. (2008)]. The cluster is known to contain three massive and luminous central stars with spectral types as early as O2V [Walborn et al. (2002), Moffat et al. (2004)], and up to 50 O-type stars in total [Drissen et al. (1995)]. The most massive stars exhibit both characteristics of WN6 stars and Balmer absorption lines [Drissen et al. (1995)], suggesting that they are actually core hydrogen burning rather than evolved stars [Conti et al. (1995), de Koter et al. (1997)]. Two of these three Wolf-Rayet (WR) stars are very close binaries [Schnurr et al. (2008)]. The total mass of the cluster is estimated as 10^4 M_\odot [Harayama et al. (2008)], with an upper limit to the dynamical mass of $17600 \pm 3800 \text{ M}_\odot$ [Rochau et al. (2010)]. NGC 3603 provides a unique opportunity to study the formation of massive stars embedded in clusters at their early stages. Studying such clusters is not generally straightforward owing to the limited angular resolution of telescopes in addition to uncertainties from existing models [Ascenso et al. (2009)]. Besides, extinction from the Galactic plane and the birth place of massive stars, which is immersed in dust and gas, play an important role.

All these combined effects can introduce an observational bias that hampers differentiating models of massive star and cluster formation: i.e., singular collapse of a rotating molecular cloud core with subsequent fragmentation in a flattened disk or competitive accretion, or, for example, external triggering by cloud-cloud collision (ref., e.g., Johnston et al. 2014). To test these models, high angular resolution observation in the infrared are the best strategy as they minimize the effects of source confusion and spatial extinction variations.

In this context, the extreme adaptive optics (XAO) of the new instrument SPHERE [Beuzit et al. (2008)] on the VLT, enabled us to observe deeper in the core of NGC 3603 in the near-infrared

J and K bands to better probe the massive star cluster at a high resolution in the range of 20-40 mas resolution, which is comparable to the HST in the visible.

4.2 Data and photometry

We obtained data via Guaranteed Time Observation (GTO) runs to image NGC 3603 using the dual mode of IRDIS [Langlois et al. (2014)], enabling simultaneous observations in two spectral bands on the VLT. The observations were performed in two epochs in 2015 (March and June), with high dynamic and spatial resolution imaging of three regions, each with a field of view (FoV) of $13.5'' \times 13.5''$, one centered on the core of the cluster (F0 shown in Figure 4.1) and two regions (F1 and F2 shown in Figure 4.2 and 4.3) to cover the radial extent of the cluster (Figure 4.5 Top). To facilitate homogeneous photometric calibrations, F1 and F2 partially overlap with F0. The data consist of 400, 300, and 320 frames of 0.8s exposures in the IRDIS broadband K filter (IRDIS/BB-K) for F0, F1, and F2, respectively, and 400, 150, and 160 frames of 4.0, 2.0, and 2.0s exposures in IRDIS broadband J (IRDIS/BB-J), respectively, during the two observing epochs. Neutral density (ND) filters were used for the IRDIS/BB-J data to avoid saturating the brightest stars. The average airmass during these observations was 1.25-1.26. A log of the observations is presented in Table 4.1.

We used the SPHERE pipeline package¹, for correcting dark, flat, distortion, and bad pixels. As SPHERE filters in BB-J and BB-K are similar to ESO's Nasmyth Adaptive Optics System Near-Infrared Imager and Spectrograph (NACO), we corrected the photometric zero-points of SPHERE by comparing them to the magnitudes of spectroscopically known stars (preferentially isolated sources) in NACO [Harayama et al. (2008)] J and K filters.

For the photometry, we used the STARFINDER package implemented in IDL [Diolaiti et al.

¹http://www.mpia.de/SPHERE/sphere-web/nightly_builds-page.html

Figure 4.1 SPHERE/IRDIS image of NGC3603-F0 in J (left) and K (right)

Figure 4.2 SPHERE/IRDIS image of NGC3603-F1 in J (left) and K (right)

Figure 4.3 SPHERE/IRDIS image of NGC3603-F2 in J (left) and K (right)

(2000)] to derive the local point spread function (PSF) to detect stellar objects, while estimating instrumental magnitudes, i.e., before the photometric zero-point corrections. For this, each field is divided into subregions to extract the empirical local PSFs from isolated sources in the image itself. Local PSFs are then used to extract the flux of the sources to compensate for the local distortion effect. This is particularly suitable for AO-assisted imaging data where one can face locally distorted PSFs that hamper photometric measurements along different parts of the IRDIS FoV.

Consequently, 410 (290), 149 (364), and 445 (682) sources were detected in the J and K bands in F0, F1, and F2, respectively, by limiting them to a minimum correlation of 0.8 with the PSF. We also put a threshold limit of one standard deviation of sky brightness. Table 4.2 gives the details of the total number of detected sources in each field for a given filter.

The high Strehl ratio, and the resulting high dynamic range close to bright stars, enabled us to detect stellar sources that are 10.6 and 9.8 magnitudes fainter than the brightest sources in J and K

Table 4.1 Exposure time log and faintest stars (SNR > 4.2) of VLT/SPHERE observations. Δ_J and Δ_K are the differences between the maximum and minimum magnitudes in F0, F1 and F2 fields.

Field (Obs. date)	Filter	Single/Total Exposure[s]	λ_{cen} [nm]	$\Delta\lambda$ [nm]	mag_{max}	mass [M_{\odot}]	Δ_{mag}
F0 (2015-03-31)	B-J	4.0/1600	1245	240	18.7	0.43	10.6
F0 (2015-03-31)	B-K	0.83/335.0	2182	300	16.4	0.63	9.5
F1 (2015-06-07)	B-J	2.0/300.0	1245	240	18.9	0.35	9.0
F1 (2015-06-07)	B-K	0.83/251.3	2182	300	18.1	0.16	9.8
F2 (2015-06-07)	B-J	2.0/320.0	1245	240	18.9	0.35	9.3
F2 (2015-06-07)	B-K	0.83/269.0	2182	300	18.8	0.11	9.6

bands, respectively. Sources with K magnitude of 18.8 and J magnitude of 18.9 could be detected in the core of NGC 3603.

Our test experiments (shown in 4.4) for completeness correction (500 artificial-star per flux) suggest that we should reach a completeness level $\geq 80\%$ for stars brighter than 17.5 mag in F1 and F2 (0.22 M_{\odot} in K-band and 0.94 M_{\odot} in J-band). The quality (Signal to Noise Ratio) of data in F0 in K-band (in March 2015) was not as good as in F1 and F2 in the second run (June 2015) thus the dynamic range is smaller. In F0, stars brighter than 15.3 in K-band (1.57 M_{\odot}) and 16.5 in J-band (1.8 M_{\odot}) have completeness level $\geq 80\%$. Table 4.1 gives the faintest magnitudes obtained in the different fields F0, F1 and F2 by SPHERE within the exposure time limits of the run.

4.3 Extinction and CMD

In order to correct for extinction, 31 O stars on or close to the main sequence (class V) were selected from [Harayama et al. (2008)]. These stars are encircled in green in the top panel of Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.4 Incompleteness test on three fields in NGC3603 of SPHERE data in J (left) and K (right). Each point represent the 500 artificial star test. Up: F0; middle: F1 and F2; bottom: shows the final results with fitted line in F0 (left) and F1-F2 (right).

To estimate their intrinsic magnitude, their T_{eff} were estimated from Table 4 of [Martins et al. (2005)] and their $\log g$ as a function of age (1.5 Myr) according to the PARSEC² stellar evolution models [Bressan et al. (2012)], adopting Galactic metallicity. We assumed a distance of 6 kpc (Section 4.4) for these O stars.

We derived the color excess for selected O stars in the two IRDIS-BB J and K filters at the distance of 6 kpc. We adopted the maximum weighted value for $E(J-K)$, which is 0.76 ($A_V = 4.5$). This value results in A_J and A_K as 1.269 and 0.504, respectively, (from [Rieke & Lebofsky (1985)]).

We found 239, 118, and 191 sources detected in both J and K data in F0, F1, and F2, respectively. The color magnitude diagrams (CMDs) for these different fields are shown in Figure 4.6.

4.4 Mass Functions

We used the stellar evolution tracks from PARSEC mentioned above to estimate stellar masses at the age of 1 Myr. The distance of the cluster was taken as 6 kpc which fits well with the observed CMD, isochrone and extinction, and is also in good agreement with [Stolte et al. (2004)], [?] and [Harayama et al. (2008)].

Using grids of stellar evolutionary tracks and extinction for each filter we can estimate the stellar masses separately from the photometry in each filter.

The slope of the mass function Γ can be estimated from Eq. 4.2 where M is stellar mass and N is number of stars in the logarithmic mass interval $\log_{10}(M)$ to $\log_{10}(M) + 0.2 \log_{10}(M)$. We used an implementation of the nonlinear least-squares (NLLS) Marquardt-Levenberg algorithm to

²<http://stev.oapd.inaf.it/cgi-bin/cmd>

Figure 4.5 HST/WFPC2-PC/F814W core of NGC 3603: blue squares depict the three fields observed with SPHERE-IRDIS. Green circles refer to the known O-type stars from [Harayama et al. (2008)]. Red circles show the stars in [Harayama et al. (2008)] catalog, which we used for calibrating zero-points in different fields. There are 113, 45, and 51 stars common between [Harayama et al. (2008)] in the SPHERE F0, F1, and F2 fields.

Figure 4.6 CMD of the core of NGC 3603 in IRDIS J and K band for the whole FoV (left) followed to the right for the three fields F0, F1, and F2. Black circles show the K-excess stars. Three black crosses represent stellar models with initial masses of 100, 120, and 150 M_{\odot} . The black arrow signifies the effect of extinction, $A_V = 4.5$.

Figure 4.7 CMD from VLT/NACO (from [Harayama et al. (2008)]) overlapped with SPHERE data (red circles) to set the zeropoints of SPHERE/IRDIS detectors. The stars are shown in Figure 4.5 (Red circles in three fields)

Figure 4.8 The sources with $E(J - K) > 1.8$ in F0, F1 and F2 shown in red circles. The image is a combination of all three fields in IRDIS/B-J.

fit the MF.

$$\log(N) = \Gamma \log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right) + \text{cst.} \quad (4.1)$$

We used the stellar evolution tracks from PARSEC mentioned above to estimate stellar masses at the age of 1.5 Myr. The distance of the cluster was taken as 6 kpc, which fits well with the observed CMD, isochrone, and extinction, and is also in good agreement with [Stolte et al. (2004)], [?], and [Harayama et al. (2008)].

Using grids of stellar evolutionary tracks and extinction for each filter, we can estimate the stellar masses separately from the photometry in each filter. The slope of the mass function Γ can be estimated from Eq. 4.2, where M is the stellar mass and N is the number of stars in the logarithmic mass interval $\log_{10}(M)$ to $\log_{10}(M) + 0.2 \log_{10}(M)$. We used a double size bin at the pre-main sequence (PMS) and main sequence (MS) transition, around $4 M_{\odot}$, to smooth out the degeneracy (same as [Harayama et al. (2008)]). We used an implementation of the nonlinear least-squares (NLLS) Marquardt-Levenberg algorithm to fit the MF,

$$\log(N) = \Gamma \log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right) + \text{cst.} \quad (4.2)$$

Mass functions for the two IRDIS BB-J and BB-K filters are shown in Figure 4.9 for the core (F0) and in Figure 4.10 for F1 and F2. One can compare the MF in the very core of the cluster (F0) with the next radial bin (F1 and F2) to check the radial variation of MF. The two latter were observed with similar exposure times and very close conditions as both fields were recorded within one hour slot of a SPHERE/VLT run on 2015-06-07. Also, minimum and maximum magnitudes in both fields are very similar especially in the K band. All these conditions result in similar mass range of detected sources in J and K. Thus we could plot the MF for F1 and F2 together, where 586 sources are detected with masses less than $1 M_{\odot}$ (fainter than 16.5 magnitude) in the K band.

In F0, we were able to reach $0.66 M_{\odot}$ (J=18.7) in the J band and $1.08 M_{\odot}$ (K=16.4) in the K band. Figure 4.9 depicts the MF in F0. Three WR stars (A1, B, C) are located in this region where

two of them (A1 and C) were identified as spectroscopic binaries by [Schnurr et al. (2008)]. The MF can be treated in three possible ways (Table 4.2): 1) considering all WR stars: two as binaries with masses estimated from [Schnurr et al. (2008)] and one (B) as a single star (*All*); 2) considering just two WR stars as two binary systems (*All-B*); and 3) excluding these three WR stars (*All-WRs*).

Figure 4.10 depicts the MF for the next radial bin from the core of NGC3603 (F1 and F2). The mass range covered in K band starts from $0.14 M_{\odot}$, ending at $69 M_{\odot}$. More than 800 sources with a mass smaller than $4 M_{\odot}$ are detected.

The change of the MF slope for the MS and PMS stars occurs around $4 M_{\odot}$. We also fitted a separate line on MF (dash-dotted line in Figure 4.10) for the low-mass PMS stars. The mass function in the low-mass part is corrected for the number of detected sources above an incompleteness level of 80% (black bins in the low-mass part in Figure 4.9 and 4.10).

Table 4.2 lists the derived MF slopes in F0, F1, and F2 regions and derived slopes for MS/PMS stars. MS is a common mass range in J and K and in F0 and F1+F2 with an incompleteness level of 100%. The MF slopes are consistent in the J band and K band and also in the different regions, for the main sequence stars and for the whole mass range.

The MF slopes for the whole mass range is flatter than the main sequence part. The MF slopes even for the massive stars (main sequence) are flatter than Salpeter, $\Gamma_{Salpeter} = -1.35$ [Salpeter (1955)] and Kroupa, $\Gamma_{Kroupa} = -1.3$ [Kroupa (2001)]. The average value agrees with those found in the outer regions of NGC3603 according to previous works. For pre-main sequence stars, the MF slope is flatter than for the whole mass range and for the main sequence.

If we assume that binary properties like binary fraction and mass-ratio distribution do not change strongly with the mass of the primary stars, then the deduced mass function slope should be very similar to the mass function slope of the primary stars.

We could detect 11, 4, and 4 K-excess sources with an E(J-K) that is higher than 1.8 (for MS) and 2.0 (for PMS), in F0, F1, and F2, respectively, corresponding to 14 sources in total (black

Figure 4.9 Mass functions derived for IRDIS data in BB-J (right) and BB-K (left) in F0 (shown in Figure 4.5 Top). Last three red bins represent the MF considering the A1 and C as binaries and B as a single source. The last three black stars represent the MF if the WR stars are considered single objects, which is the case for the photometry analysis.

circles in Figure 4.6 and red circles in the bottom panels of Figure 4.5). For these stars, the mass estimated in K is higher than in J because of their K excess. Twelve of these stars are on the sequence parallel to the MS ($M > 4 M_{\odot}$). In this case, the MF slopes for the main sequence part in the J band should be more reliable than in the K band.

4.5 Discussion

NGC 3603 has been observed with various instruments and the slope of its mass function has been calculated in previous works (Table 2.7). These works reach conclusions on the general trend of decreasing MF slopes in the core as the signature of mass segregation. The slopes of the MF in different filters (Table 4.2) in the core of NGC 3603 is steeper than the previous works and does not show a radial dependence in the observed fields. The slope value for the main sequence stars and for the whole mass range is consistent in all observed regions of the core of the cluster.

Figure 4.10 Mass functions derived for IRDIS data in BB-J (right) and BB-K (left) in F1 and F2 together. F1 and F2 are shown in Figure 4.5 Top.

Table 4.2 Number of detected stars (N_J and N_K in J and K bands) and MF slopes (Γ_J and Γ_K in J and K bands) using Equation 4.2, at 1.5 Myr in three F0, F1, and F2 fields of NGC 3603 from SPHERE/IRDIS.

F0	N_K	Γ_K	N_J	Γ_J
<i>All</i>	288	-1.09 ± 0.11	408	-1.07 ± 0.08
<i>All-B</i>	287	-0.98 ± 0.12	407	-0.99 ± 0.08
<i>All-WR_s</i>	283	-0.85 ± 0.06	403	-0.98 ± 0.09
F1+F2	N_K	Γ_K	N_J	Γ_J
Total	1003	-0.82 ± 0.08	561	-0.94 ± 0.10
MS	189	-1.12 ± 0.14	200	-1.20 ± 0.11
PMS	814	-0.54 ± 0.11	361	-

Shape of MF at the massive end, can be used as an observational test that may be able to settle the question of which mechanism (accretion or collision) is a dominant route for the formation of the most massive stars [Krumholz (2015)]. According to the accretion models, as the massive stars form by the same accretion processes that produce low-mass stars (normal star formation), the high end of the stellar mass function should be continuous and does not depend radically on the environment [Krumholz (2015)]. On the other hand, collisional formation predicts a large gap in the stellar MF, separating the bulk of the accretion-formed stellar population from the few collisionally formed stars [Baumgardt & Klessen (2011), Moeckel & Clarke (2011)]. This feature should only appear in the most massive and densest clusters. Figure 4.9 shows this signature in the core (F0), but we know that the last bin corresponds to the three WR stars in which two of them have been found to be multiple objects and not single stars [Schnurr et al. (2008)]. Therefore, collisional formation of very massive objects seems unlikely at least for the NGC 3603 cluster. Accretion models also predict that massive stars are likely to have low-mass and high-mass companions [Kratter & Matzner (2006), Kratter et al. (2008), Kratter et al. (2010), Krumholz et al. (2012)], but the collisionally formed stars lack low-mass companions, which provokes segregation.

This study shows no signature of mass segregation in the core of NGC 3603, first, because the MF slope in its very core is not flatter than the next radial bin. Second, both slopes are similar to the MF values found in previous works for the outer regions (references in Table 2.7). Therefore, it appears that nonsegregated clusters with a smooth MF agree better with accretion models for massive star formation. Our SPHERE results demonstrate that, by improved photometric dynamic range and spatial resolution from XAO, we can overcome the effect of confusion that in the past has led to the conclusion of observational segregation (see also [Ascenso et al. (2009)]) as far as NGC 3603 is concerned.

VISTA Magellanic Cloud Survey taken in Y, J and Ks filters in the near-infrared, coloured blue, green and red respectively. The image covers a region of sky about 52 by 70 arcminutes.

Credit: ESO/M.-R. Cioni/VISTA Magellanic Cloud survey.

Chapter 5

VLT/SPHERE Photometry on R136

Abstract: In this chapter I present the results of sharpest near-IR images of the massive cluster R136 to date, based on the extreme adaptive optics of the SPHERE focal instrument implemented on the ESO Very Large Telescope and operated in its IRDIS imaging mode.

The crowded stellar population in the core of the R136 starburst compact cluster remains still to be characterized in terms of individual luminosities, age, mass and multiplicity. SPHERE/VLT and its high contrast imaging possibilities open new windows to make progress on these questions.

Stacking-up a few hundreds of short exposures in J and Ks spectral bands over a Field of View (FoV) of $10.9'' \times 12.3''$ centered on the R136a1 stellar component, enabled us to carry a refined photometric analysis of the core of R136. We detected 1110 and 1059 sources in J and Ks images respectively with 818 common sources that were secured from systematic photometric error analysis and correlation coefficients exceeding 65% and 80%, in Ks and J band, for their reliability.

We found that more than 62.6% (16.5%) of the stars, detected both in J and Ks data, have visual companion closer than 0.2" (0.1"). The closest stars are resolved down to the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the point spread function (PSF) measured by Starfinder. Among newly resolved and/or detected sources R136a1 and R136c are found to have optical companions

and R136a3 is resolved as two stars (PSF fitting) separated by 59 ± 2 mas. This new companion of R136a3 presents a correlation coefficient of 86% in J and 75% in Ks. The new set of detected sources were used to re-assess the age and extinction of R136 based on 54 spectroscopically stars that have been recently studied with HST slit-spectroscopy [Crowther et al. (2016)] of the core of this cluster. Over 90% of these 54 sources identified visual companions (closer than 0.2"). We found the most probable age and extinction for these sources are $1.8^{+1.2}_{-0.8}$ Myr, $A_J = 0.4 \pm 0.5$ and $A_K = 0.2 \pm 0.5$ within the photometric and spectroscopic error-bars. Additionally, using PARSEC evolutionary isochrones and tracks, we estimated the stellar mass range for each detected source (common in J and K data) and plotted the generalized histogram of mass (MF with error-bars).

Using SPHERE data, I have gone one step further and partially resolved and studied the IMF covering mass range of 3-300 M_{\odot} at the age of 1 and 1.5 Myr. The density in the core of R136 (0.1 - 1.4 pc) is estimated and extrapolated in 3D and larger radii (up to 6pc). I show that the stars in the core are still unresolved due to crowding, and the obtained results are upper limits. Higher angular resolution is mandatory to overcome these difficulties.

5.1 Observations

We obtained data via Guaranteed Time Observation (GTO) runs to image R 136 using the dual mode of IRDIS [Langlois et al. (2014)], enabling simultaneous observations in two spectral bands on the VLT. The observations were performed in September 2015, with high dynamic and spatial resolution imaging in J and K bands with a FoV of $13.5'' \times 13.5''$, centered on the core of the cluster (Figure 5.1 and 5.2).

One can compare these data with HST (WFPC2 and WFC3) in V-band (Figure 5.3 Top). The quality of data is much better than previous data and many stars are resolved thanks to SPHERE/IRDIS resolution in J and K.

Figure 5.1 SPHERE/IRDIS images of the core of R136 in K-band.

Our data consist of 300 frames of 4.0s exposures in both the IRDIS broad-band Ks and J filters (BB-Ks, BB-J). The Wolf-Rayet star R136a1 was used for guiding the AO loop of SPHERE confirming its better than nominal performances surpassing NACO and MAD observations (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.2 SPHERE/IRDIS images of the core of R136 in J-band.

The range of airmass during these observations was 1.54 to 1.67. A log of observations is presented in Table 5.1.

We used the SPHERE pipeline package¹, for correcting dark, flat, distortion, badpixels and

¹http://www.mpia.de/SPHERE/sphere-web/nightly_builds-page.html

Figure 5.3 Top: HST images in V-band (F555W) from the core of R136, same FoV of SPHERE/IRDIS data. Left: WFPC2, Right:WFC3. Bottom: VLT images of the core of R136 in K band. Left: MAD, Right: SPHERE.

detector thermal emission (in Ks). In order to reach the highest sensitivity and the largest number of detectable sources, additional corrections were carried out onto the images. Based on Gaussian

Figure 5.4 Zoom to the WR stars in the core of R136 in K-band (left) and J-band (right). Each frame covers about 2". In the top R136a1, R136a2 and R136a3 can be seen and in Bottom, R136b and R136c with its new companion.

fit using selected stars we estimated and corrected the subpixels images drifts before combining the individual images. This allowed to correct for residual tip tilt errors with a few mas accuracy. Still, some uncorrected atmospheric leaks persist in our final images due to the adaptive optics residual

Table 5.1 Exposure time log of VLT/SPHERE observations on R136.

Obs. date	Filter	Single/Total Exposure[s]	λ_{cen} [nm]	$\Delta\lambda$ [nm]
2015-09-22	B-J	4.0/1200	1245	240
2015-09-22	B-K	4.0/1200	2182	300

halo which is more important in J than in Ks, that we accurately considered to estimate correct error bars in addition to the Starfinder reduction tool providing photometric errors (see Section 5.2).

5.2 Photometry of R136's compact core

For the present study we used the Starfinder package implemented in IDL [Diolaiti et al. (2000)]. Starfinder is designed for the analysis of of AO images of crowded fields, like the Galactic Center for instance [Pugliese et al. (2002)]. It determines the empirical local Point Spread Function (PSF) from several isolated sources in the image and uses this PSF to extract other stellar sources across the FoV. Starfinder estimates also the formal error on the estimated photometry based on photon noise, variance due to the sky and the PSF fitting procedure itself. This error is called "**PSF fitting error**" hereafter.

Our photometry analysis of R136 was conducted in two steps: 1) stellar sources detection using Starfinder and 2) the background analysis to obtain realistic error bars on the photometry of individual stars beyond the formal PSF fitting error.

In the first step 1110 and 1059 sources were detected in the J and Ks bands, respectively. Figure 5.25 shows the reconstructed image of SPHERE/IRDIS in Ks band for the 1059 stellar sources detected by Starfinder. We stopped source extraction after we attained a minimum correlation of 65% and 80%, in Ks and J bands, between the extracted star with the locally determined PSF

according to Starfinder procedures. Indeed, stars with higher correlation coefficients, i.e. more similarity to the PSF, represent higher reliability on their photometric measure.

Figure 5.6 shows the map of the correlation coefficient across the field of J (left) and Ks (right) images of R136. One can notice that the PSF changes as a function of radial distance and azimuth along the field (Figure 5.6). Actually, the AO correcting efficiency degrades as a function of distance from R136a1, which is the reference star for the AO loop. At the borders of the FoV one also approaches the isoplanatic limits. Overall the PSF is not centro-symmetric at large distances from R136a1. We took into account these distortions to estimate the local statistical errors, which become significant on the distant sources from the center of the image, typically $>3''$.

In addition to the correlation coefficient criterion, we applied the limit of standard deviation from the sky brightness (σ_{sky}) for stopping the extraction of sources by Starfinder, i.e. the local PSF maximum value must exceed $2\sigma_{sky}$ over the sky. The faintest common detected stars between J and Ks band, present a signal to noise ratio (SNR) better than 2.

Strehl ratio (S_r) is a ratio of the peak intensity of the observed PSF to the peak intensity of the ideal diffraction limited PSF of the same optical system. In the AO system data, the flux of each stellar object is divided into two parts: 1) corrected airy-pattern with the FWHM of about the diffraction-limited telescope, and 2) AO halo with the FWHM of the seeing, usually with Gaussian distribution. Figure 5.5 depicts the ideal and observed shape of the flux distribution at the cross-section of a simulated image. The ratio of the integrated flux of the first part (corrected by AO) over the total flux of the star (corrected part plus AO halo), is the S_r . In the IRDIS images, the FWHM of the AO halo (seeing) is about 82. pixels ($1''$).

The Strehl Ratio in J and Ks are determined as 0.40 ± 0.05 and 0.75 ± 0.03 respectively on average. These estimates are assessed from the SPARTA files recorded during SPHERE runs simultaneously with AO corrected images of R136. They are based on the slope measurements of the Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor in SAXO, by extrapolating the phase variance deduced

Figure 5.5 Theoretical diffraction pattern PSF (Airy disc) is shown in Red (left) and the simulation of the observed PSF with $S_r=0.3$ is presented in Blue. The green Gaussian profile indicates the AO halo.

from the reconstruction of SAXO open-loop data using deformable mirror, tip tilt voltages and wavefront sensor closed-loop measures (Fusco et al., 2004). The method has been proved quite robust in the past for a differential imaging by NACO (A.L. Maire et al., 2014). We are therefore quite confident on our photometry corrected for the SR effect in J and Ks bands.

To convert stellar fluxes to magnitudes, we set the zeropoint magnitude to the instrumental zeropoint (one ADU/s in J and Ks, are 25.405 and 24.256 magnitudes, respectively) in addition to the SR effect ².

² To double check our calibration method, we compared our WR stars K magnitude with 6 WR stars in Crowther et al. 2010. R136c is located further from the very bright core of R136 and it has one close neighbour with K-flux ratio of 0.114. R136c in Crowther et al. 2010 has Kmag of 11.34 ± 0.08 and in our catalogue is 11.48, considering the flux of companion in addition to R136c then it becomes 11.36.

Figure 5.6 Map of the correlation coefficients calculated by starfinder along the FoV in J (left) and in K (right).

In the second step, after extracting sources, the background image was used to estimate the residual errors in addition to the formal photometric PSF fitting errors of Starfinder. The background image contains 1) AO halo from the atmospheric turbulence, 2) residuals from the photometric analysis in the first step and 3) undetected faint stars. We define the residual error as the fluctuation of the background due to the remaining flux from the photometry using Starfinder and also from the undetected faint sources.

The image of the background is shown in Figure 5.7-Top.

Since the core of R136 is crowded with the brightest stars, the AO halo is the brightest at the center of R136. We removed this large halo in the Fourier space by applying a high bandpass filter (hat function with the diameter equal to the FWHM of the background halo), in order to estimate the fast variations of the background at the scale of the PSF, i.e. $30 \times 30 \text{ pixel}^2$ area around the source.

Figure 5.8 shows these errors separately for each detected sources. The PSF fitting errors (red-pluses) are smaller in K-band as the AO works better in larger wavelengths. But the residual errors

(blue-crosses) are larger in K-band because the background fluctuation in longer wavelengths is higher. Figure 5.11 shows the maps of these two errors in J and K across the field.

The final photometric error is set to the quadratic combination of PSF fitting errors, residual errors and the photometric calibration error (0.042 in K and 0.128 in J).

In order to interpret the photometric distribution of the 1110 and 1059 sources in J and Ks bands we conducted an incompleteness test to the core ($r < 3''$) of R 136 and outside its core ($r > 3''$) in both J and Ks-band imaging data. Figure 5.12 shows the result of incompleteness test which is done by putting 500 artificial stars, one by one, in each image for each flux value (magnitude). The faintest star in the artificial star test has a flux of 83.14 [ADU/s] in J-band ($J_{\text{mag}}=21.87$) and 328.614 [ADU/s] in Ks-band ($K_{\text{mag}}=19.91$). For this star we iterate the test 500 times in the inner region ($r < 3''$) and 500 times in the outer region ($r > 3''$). This experiment is done for 187 (in J) and 158 (in Ks) fluxes, 500 times for each flux value, with the $\Delta(\text{flux})$ about 12.5 [ADU/s] on average. Each time one artificial star was added to these images and Starfinder was used again to detect the artificial star. The core of the cluster is very crowded so that the incompleteness does not reach 100% even for the bright artificial stars. This effect is more important for J-band data where the core is fuzzy because of a lower AO correction.

5.3 Age and extinction

To estimate the stellar ages and the extinction of the core of R136, we used the effective temperature (T_{eff}) and luminosity ($\log L$) of 54 stars studied spectroscopically by Crowther et al. (2016). We also chose a grid of isochrones at different ages (from 0.1 up to 8 Myr) with the LMC metallicity ($0.006 Z_{\odot}$), from the latest sets of PARSEC evolutionary model³ [Bressan et al. (2012)] which is a complete theoretical library that includes the latest set of stellar phases from pre-main sequence to

³<http://stev.oapd.inaf.it/cgi-bin/cmd>

Figure 5.7 Top: Background images in J (left) and in K (right) after removing the detected sources using Starfinder. Bottom: Residual images in J (left) and K (right) after filtering out the AO halo in the background image at Fourier space.

Figure 5.8 PSF fitting errors (red pluses) and residual errors (blue crosses) in J (bottom) and K (top). PSF fitting error is the outcome of the Starfinder. Residual errors is the outcome of the background analysis after removing the stellar sources signals from the image.

main sequence and covering stellar masses from 0.1 to $350 M_{\odot}$. Figure 5.13 shows these selected 54 stars with their T_{eff} - $\log L$ (with their error-bars) and sets of isochrones covering them.

By fitting the isochrones to each star, we estimated the age and intrinsic color of each star with the error-bars. We adopt the LMC distance modulus (DM) of 18.49 magnitude estimated by Pietrzyński et al. (2013) and is consistent with the value suggested by Gibson (2000) for LMC.

Table 5.3 shows the estimated age, initial and actual mass and extinction of these 54 spectroscopically known stars. The values of T_{eff} and $\log L/L_{\odot}$ in the second and third column are taken from Crowther et al. 2016. Figure 5.14 shows the generalized histogram of the age of these 54 sources. Note that, the age of each star has a Gaussian distribution with a given σ (error) in the histogram. Also note that the large errors on the age and extinction are coming from the large

Figure 5.9 Position errors in J (bottom) and K (top), estimated from the photometry.

spectroscopic uncertainties (errors on T_{eff} and $\log L/L_{\odot}$). We were also limited by the evolutionary tracks up to $350 M_{\odot}$, which explains the upper mass limit of $348 M_{\odot}$ for very massive stars like R136a1.

Figure 5.15 shows the histogram of the extinction in J and K and their color-excess.

The age of $1.8^{+1.2}_{-0.8}$ Myr is the most probable age range for these stars. Comparing Figure 5.14 with the Figure 11 of Crowther et al. (2016), the age estimation for these sample of stars is consistent within error-bars in both analysis.

The extinction in J and K is respectively 0.45 ± 0.5 and 0.2 ± 0.5 magnitude. The estimated extinction are consistent with the values derived in previous studies by Campbell et al. (2010) and De Marchi & Panagia 2014. The color excess of $E(J - K) = 0.25 \pm 0.1$ is also consistent with Tatton et al. (2013).

Figure 5.16 shows the color magnitude diagram (CMD) of detected sources in J and Ks band

Figure 5.10 Surface incompleteness map for magnitude 18 (left) and 19 (right) in J-band. The incompleteness increases toward the central crowded core of R136 and also close to the bright stars. The black pluses indicate the position of the stars which are almost as bright as the artificial star test.

IRDIS data with their error-bars. The CMD is plotted for the whole FoV (818 sources), in the very core of the cluster ($r < 3''$) and outside ($r > 3''$), from left to right respectively. The error-bars on each point are the combination of the PSF-fitting errors and the residual errors from the background image after removing the stellar sources signals from the images. The PARSEC isochrones at three different ages (0.6, 1 and 1.5 Myr) also are plotted in this Figure using $DM=18.49$ and central values of extinctions in J (0.45 mag) and K (0.2 mag).

Note that from CMD isochrone fitting, the age of 1 and 1.5 Myr for the inner ($r < 3''$) and outside core ($r > 3''$), fits best to our data. We can also see a young population with the age around 0.6 Myr in both regions. In the histogram of estimated age for 54 spectroscopically studies stars there is a peak at 0.6 Myr which shows a probable age for some stars. The uncertainties on the photometric analysis is less than those obtained from the spectroscopic analysis of the massive stars. We can clearly see the main sequence and pre-main sequence conjunction which is very sensitive to the age. The realistic age and extinction can be estimated using the precise

photometric analysis for the 818 stellar sources in the core of R136. Interestingly, the age of stars in the very core ($r < 3''$) is younger than its outer region ($r > 3''$). This result justifies the older population found outward the core of R 136, like the north-east clump observed by Sabbi et al. (2012) and in further distance ($3'$) the old cluster, Hodge 301, studied by Grebel & Chu (2000). Understanding this age discrete in R 136 and also 30 Dor region can be studied in future from the formation point of view. Moreover how the younger population in the center of the cluster can be explained by star cluster formation scenarios? Note that this age difference in two regions can also be explained by an observational bias as the central region of R 136 is very compact and bright so that incompleteness level is very low. Figure 5.10 shows the incompleteness map at J=18 (top) and J=19 (bottom). The incompleteness gets low in the very central regions which means that we have not detected true/actual number of stars. This might affect the CMD in this magnitude range which is sensitive to the age. Considering the errors on the estimated age and extinction, one can estimate the stellar mass range for each star. The histogram of mass, which is the mass function (MF), is plotted considering a Gaussian distribution for each stellar mass. Gaussian uncertainty in the mass of each star is accounted for, when constructing the MF. Figure 5.17 shows the generalized histogram of the mass (MF) at three different ages (0.6, 1 and 1.5 Myr). The MF slope for 1 and 1.5 Myr isochrone are $\Gamma_{1Myr} = -0.90 \pm 0.13$ and $\Gamma_{1.5Myr} = -0.98 \pm 0.18$, respectively, for the mass range of (3 - 300) M_{\odot} . These slopes are more flat than Kroupa ($\Gamma = -1.3$) and Salpeter value ($\Gamma = -1.35$). Note that the incompleteness correction is applied for the low mass bin considering number of stars in the inner ($r < 3''$) and outer ($r > 3''$) region of the cluster (see Figure 5.12). The derived MF is limited to the resolution of the instrument and also on the detection limit of the observation. In future, using higher angular resolution data, we may resolve binaries and low-mass stars which affects the shape of MF.

Considering these error-bars on the age and extinction, one can estimate the stellar mass range for each star. The histogram of mass (MF) can be plotted considering the Gaussian distribution

for each stellar mass in this histogram. Figure 5.17 shows the generalized histogram of the mass (MF) at three different ages (1, 2 and 3 Myr).

Table 5.2 Information on 54 spectroscopically known stars with T_{eff} and $\log L/L_{\odot}$ estimated by Crowther et al. 2016 (second and third columns). Using PARSEC evolutionary isochrones (0.1 to 8 Myr), the age, color excess, Ks and J magnitudes, initial and actual stellar masses are estimated (columns four to nine). N2 and N1 are the number of visual companions for each source in a radius of 0.2" and 0.1" respectively. The identifications (ID) of the sources are from Hunter et al. 1995. Note that we are also limited by the evolutionary tracks up to $350 M_{\odot}$ which explains zero error-bars for very bright stars.

ID	T_{eff} [kK]	$\log L/L_{\odot}$	age[Myr]	E(J-K)	Ks	J	$M_{initial}$	M_{act}	N2	N1
3	$53.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$6.94^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	$0.79^{+1.44}_{-0.00}$	$0.49^{+0.02}_{-0.00}$	11.07	11.33	$348.1^{+0.0}_{-80.1}$	$325.2^{+0.0}_{-147.0}$	3	1
5	$53.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$6.63^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	$0.56^{+0.00}_{-0.36}$	$0.46^{+0.00}_{-0.00}$	11.32	11.55	$201.5^{+48.5}_{-0.0}$	$195.5^{+51.7}_{-0.0}$	3	0
20	$50.00^{+4.0}_{-5.0}$	$6.32^{+0.16}_{-0.15}$	$1.26^{+2.29}_{-0.86}$	$0.27^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	12.73	12.75	$120.0^{+30.2}_{-47.9}$	$114.1^{+32.5}_{-72.6}$	2	0
24	$46.00^{+4.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.99^{+0.10}_{-0.08}$	$1.78^{+2.69}_{-0.78}$	$0.14^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	13.05	12.95	$75.4^{+14.6}_{-22.2}$	$72.2^{+15.1}_{-44.4}$	3	0
27	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$6.28^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$1.00^{+2.55}_{-0.90}$	$0.15^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	13.27	13.18	$120.0^{+30.0}_{-47.9}$	$115.6^{+33.8}_{-74.1}$	1	1
21	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$6.46^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$1.12^{+1.70}_{-1.02}$	$0.17^{+0.01}_{-0.03}$	13.09	13.00	$150.2^{+39.9}_{-29.3}$	$142.1^{+35.2}_{-61.0}$	1	1
86	$46.00^{+4.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.91^{+0.10}_{-0.08}$	$1.78^{+2.69}_{-0.98}$	$0.25^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$	14.80	14.80	$67.9^{+11.1}_{-14.8}$	$65.4^{+10.9}_{-37.7}$	2	0
66	$46.00^{+4.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.70^{+0.10}_{-0.08}$	$1.78^{+0.73}_{-1.68}$	$0.14^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	14.42	14.31	$53.7^{+10.2}_{-4.8}$	$52.4^{+10.7}_{-4.8}$	2	0
6	$53.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$6.58^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	$0.56^{+0.23}_{-0.00}$	$0.57^{+0.00}_{-0.00}$	11.44	11.77	$201.5^{+0.0}_{-24.4}$	$195.5^{+0.0}_{-25.5}$	2	1
58	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$5.93^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$0.79^{+3.67}_{-0.69}$	$0.12^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	13.91	13.78	$75.0^{+15.1}_{-21.7}$	$73.8^{+16.0}_{-46.5}$	0	0
70	$42.00^{+2.0}_{-2.0}$	$5.57^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$	$2.51^{+0.65}_{-0.27}$	$0.10^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	14.20	14.06	$44.2^{+1.7}_{-4.2}$	$43.1^{+1.5}_{-4.2}$	1	1
30	$38.00^{+2.0}_{-2.0}$	$5.67^{+0.05}_{-0.06}$	$3.55^{+0.00}_{-0.39}$	$0.21^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	13.65	13.62	$45.0^{+3.1}_{-0.4}$	$43.0^{+3.0}_{-0.3}$	2	0
89	$44.00^{+2.5}_{-2.5}$	$5.99^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	$4.47^{+0.00}_{-2.69}$	$0.18^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	14.69	14.62	$53.1^{+23.0}_{-0.0}$	$27.8^{+44.4}_{-0.0}$	2	0
62	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$5.84^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$0.20^{+1.80}_{-0.10}$	$0.16^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	14.35	14.28	$70.0^{+5.0}_{-16.3}$	$69.8^{+5.1}_{-17.4}$	4	0
19	$46.00^{+4.0}_{-2.0}$	$6.52^{+0.10}_{-0.05}$	$1.26^{+0.00}_{-0.26}$	$0.43^{+0.01}_{-0.00}$	13.05	13.24	$170.0^{+20.2}_{-1.8}$	$157.9^{+19.5}_{-0.0}$	2	1
50	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$6.02^{+0.15}_{-0.13}$	$4.47^{+0.00}_{-4.37}$	$0.10^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	13.96	13.82	$53.3^{+46.7}_{-0.0}$	$27.4^{+72.4}_{-0.0}$	2	0
90	$44.00^{+2.5}_{-2.5}$	$5.36^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	$0.79^{+1.72}_{-0.69}$	$0.29^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	14.83	14.88	$38.6^{+1.4}_{-4.6}$	$38.4^{+1.6}_{-4.9}$	1	0

ID	T_{eff} [kK]	$\log L/L_{\odot}$	age[Myr]	E(J-K)	Ks	J	$M_{initial}$	M_{act}	N2	N1
141	41.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	5.09 ^{+0.12} _{-0.12}	2.00 ^{+1.99} _{-1.90}	0.18 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	15.40	15.33	28.3 ^{+5.6} _{-3.4}	28.1 ^{+5.7} _{-3.4}	4	0
80	36.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	5.20 ^{+0.08} _{-0.10}	4.47 ^{+1.16} _{-0.00}	0.18 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.77	14.71	28.0 ^{+0.7} _{-3.5}	27.6 ^{+0.6} _{-3.4}	1	0
35	48.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	5.92 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	1.58 ^{+0.41} _{-1.19}	0.29 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	14.00	14.04	70.0 ^{+5.4} _{-8.3}	67.7 ^{+6.5} _{-8.3}	2	0
78	44.00 ^{+2.5} _{-2.5}	5.47 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	2.24 ^{+0.58} _{-1.68}	0.32 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.68	14.76	40.0 ^{+5.0} _{-2.2}	39.3 ^{+5.5} _{-2.3}	0	0
73	33.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	5.21 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	6.31 ^{+0.00} _{-0.69}	0.09 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.38	14.24	25.4 ^{+2.6} _{-1.4}	24.9 ^{+2.5} _{-1.3}	2	0
92	40.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	5.20 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}	2.82 ^{+1.16} _{-1.56}	0.33 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	14.87	14.96	30.0 ^{+2.1} _{-2.4}	29.7 ^{+2.2} _{-2.4}	1	0
143	39.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	4.99 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}	3.16 ^{+1.85} _{-3.06}	0.06 ^{+0.02} _{-0.01}	15.11	14.93	24.9 ^{+5.1} _{-3.3}	24.7 ^{+5.2} _{-3.3}	4	0
112	36.00 ^{+4.0} _{-4.0}	5.01 ^{+0.10} _{-0.11}	4.47 ^{+2.61} _{-3.47}	0.06 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.78	14.61	24.0 ^{+4.0} _{-4.0}	23.8 ^{+4.0} _{-4.0}	3	1
135	33.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	4.86 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	7.08 ^{+0.86} _{-2.07}	0.09 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	15.32	15.17	19.4 ^{+1.9} _{-1.4}	19.3 ^{+1.8} _{-1.4}	3	1
69	42.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	5.49 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}	2.82 ^{+0.34} _{-0.82}	0.14 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.39	14.29	40.0 ^{+1.4} _{-2.2}	39.1 ^{+1.6} _{-2.1}	3	0
52	46.00 ^{+4.0} _{-3.0}	5.74 ^{+0.10} _{-0.08}	2.00 ^{+0.52} _{-1.80}	0.14 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.20	14.10	55.0 ^{+10.0} _{-5.0}	53.4 ^{+11.1} _{-5.0}	2	0
48	51.00 ^{+6.0} _{-6.0}	5.97 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	1.26 ^{+3.21} _{-1.16}	0.08 ^{+0.00} _{-0.02}	13.58	13.41	75.0 ^{+20.0} _{-21.7}	73.0 ^{+21.8} _{-45.6}	3	0
94	43.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	5.31 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	2.00 ^{+1.17} _{-1.90}	0.08 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.85	14.69	34.8 ^{+5.2} _{-3.5}	34.5 ^{+5.5} _{-3.4}	2	0
115	33.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	4.82 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	7.08 ^{+0.86} _{-2.07}	0.30 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	15.46	15.53	18.8 ^{+1.5} _{-1.0}	18.7 ^{+1.5} _{-1.0}	1	0
132	33.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	4.76 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	7.08 ^{+0.86} _{-2.61}	0.25 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	15.36	15.38	18.1 ^{+2.2} _{-0.9}	18.0 ^{+2.1} _{-0.8}	2	0
36	46.00 ^{+4.0} _{-2.0}	5.94 ^{+0.10} _{-0.05}	1.78 ^{+0.22} _{-0.78}	0.14 ^{+0.00} _{-0.00}	12.96	12.86	70.0 ^{+12.9} _{-2.1}	67.3 ^{+13.0} _{-2.1}	1	0
173	33.00 ^{+2.0} _{-2.0}	4.78 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	6.31 ^{+1.63} _{-1.84}	0.30 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	15.63	15.70	19.2 ^{+1.1} _{-1.9}	19.1 ^{+1.1} _{-1.9}	3	0
75	44.00 ^{+2.5} _{-2.5}	5.54 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	1.58 ^{+1.23} _{-1.02}	0.31 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	14.78	14.84	45.0 ^{+1.7} _{-5.0}	44.4 ^{+1.5} _{-5.3}	2	0
114	37.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	4.99 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}	3.98 ^{+1.64} _{-3.19}	0.30 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	15.26	15.33	24.0 ^{+4.0} _{-2.7}	23.8 ^{+4.0} _{-2.7}	1	0
108	37.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	5.15 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}	3.98 ^{+1.64} _{-1.47}	0.35 ^{+0.02} _{-0.01}	15.59	15.71	27.6 ^{+2.6} _{-4.5}	27.3 ^{+2.6} _{-4.4}	2	0
31	51.00 ^{+6.0} _{-6.0}	6.19 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	1.26 ^{+2.72} _{-1.16}	0.32 ^{+0.00} _{-0.02}	13.62	13.69	100.0 ^{+21.1} _{-38.8}	96.0 ^{+23.6} _{-61.7}	1	0
49	43.00 ^{+3.0} _{-3.0}	5.60 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	2.51 ^{+0.65} _{-1.39}	0.20 ^{+0.01} _{-0.00}	13.98	13.94	45.0 ^{+5.0} _{-5.0}	43.8 ^{+5.1} _{-4.9}	1	0
46	48.00 ^{+4.0} _{-4.0}	6.02 ^{+0.12} _{-0.09}	1.26 ^{+3.21} _{-0.70}	0.07 ^{+0.00} _{-0.02}	13.29	13.11	82.9 ^{+12.1} _{-29.6}	80.3 ^{+12.6} _{-53.0}	3	0
47	48.00 ^{+4.0} _{-4.0}	5.95 ^{+0.14} _{-0.13}	1.41 ^{+3.05} _{-1.31}	0.09 ^{+0.00} _{-0.02}	13.32	13.17	73.5 ^{+16.6} _{-20.2}	71.3 ^{+17.6} _{-43.9}	3	0

ID	T_{eff} [kK]	$\log L/L_{\odot}$	age[Myr]	E(J-K)	Ks	J	$M_{initial}$	M_{act}	N2	N1
40	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$5.97^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$1.26^{+3.21}_{-1.16}$	$0.13^{+0.00}_{-0.02}$	13.72	13.61	$75.0^{+20.0}_{-21.7}$	$73.0^{+21.8}_{-45.6}$	1	0
116	$37.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$4.97^{+0.12}_{-0.14}$	$3.55^{+2.08}_{-3.45}$	$0.65^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	15.45	15.86	$24.0^{+3.1}_{-3.8}$	$23.9^{+3.1}_{-3.7}$	1	1
118	$39.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.07^{+0.12}_{-0.14}$	$3.16^{+1.85}_{-3.06}$	$0.02^{+0.01}_{-0.00}$	14.64	14.42	$26.5^{+4.0}_{-3.3}$	$26.3^{+4.1}_{-3.2}$	2	0
42	$46.00^{+4.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.64^{+0.10}_{-0.08}$	$1.58^{+0.93}_{-1.48}$	$0.44^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	14.11	14.30	$50.0^{+10.0}_{-5.8}$	$49.1^{+10.7}_{-6.0}$	0	0
55	$51.00^{+6.0}_{-6.0}$	$5.93^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$0.79^{+3.67}_{-0.69}$	$0.24^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	14.15	14.15	$75.0^{+15.1}_{-21.7}$	$73.8^{+16.0}_{-46.5}$	0	0
71	$44.00^{+2.5}_{-2.5}$	$5.49^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	$1.78^{+1.04}_{-1.22}$	$0.35^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	14.70	14.80	$42.3^{+2.7}_{-4.5}$	$41.7^{+3.1}_{-4.6}$	1	0
121	$33.00^{+1.5}_{-1.5}$	$4.84^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	$7.08^{+0.86}_{-1.46}$	$0.27^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	15.47	15.50	$19.4^{+0.6}_{-1.4}$	$19.3^{+0.6}_{-1.4}$	1	0
9	$41.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$6.30^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$	$1.78^{+0.22}_{-0.19}$	$0.26^{+0.00}_{-0.01}$	11.66	11.67	$119.6^{+17.7}_{-24.6}$	$109.9^{+16.4}_{-21.7}$	1	0
65	$44.00^{+2.5}_{-2.5}$	$5.56^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	$2.00^{+0.82}_{-1.20}$	$0.06^{+0.00}_{-0.01}$	13.85	13.67	$45.0^{+5.0}_{-5.0}$	$44.2^{+5.1}_{-5.1}$	1	0
134	$38.00^{+2.0}_{-2.0}$	$4.91^{+0.05}_{-0.06}$	$2.24^{+2.23}_{-1.44}$	$0.42^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	15.71	15.90	$24.0^{+1.9}_{-2.5}$	$23.9^{+1.9}_{-2.5}$	1	0
64	$42.00^{+2.0}_{-2.0}$	$5.60^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$	$2.51^{+0.65}_{-0.27}$	$0.09^{+0.00}_{-0.00}$	13.84	13.69	$45.0^{+1.6}_{-5.0}$	$43.8^{+1.2}_{-4.9}$	0	0
45	$43.00^{+3.0}_{-3.0}$	$5.76^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	$2.24^{+0.58}_{-0.46}$	$-0.02^{+0.00}_{-0.00}$	13.63	13.37	$55.0^{+5.0}_{-5.0}$	$53.1^{+4.8}_{-5.1}$	1	0
123	$40.00^{+2.0}_{-2.0}$	$5.04^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$	$1.12^{+2.43}_{-1.02}$	$0.51^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	15.61	15.88	$28.0^{+2.0}_{-3.2}$	$27.9^{+2.0}_{-3.2}$	0	0

5.4 Visual companions

For each star, detected in both J and K, we determined a distance between the star and its closest neighbor. Figure 5.18-top shows the number of visual close stars, detected both in Ks and J vs their separation in arc-second. More than 250 (pair of) stars have a closest neighbor at the separation less than 0.2". Over 90% of massive objects (brighter than 17 mag in K and 16 mag in J) have a closest neighbor with a separation of less than 0.2". Figure 5.18-bottom shows the separation between the visual close stars versus their distance from R136a1 in the core. This figure indicates that even the sources at larger radii have close visual companions, so that the large number of close visual companions is not just an effect of 2D projection on the sky across the FoV. For the sake

of simplicity, regardless of physically bound or not, we call these closely stars **visual companions** hereafter.

The most massive stars R136a1, R136a3 and R136c have visual companions which are detected for the first time. R136a3 is also resolved as two stars with the PSF fitting. Both stars have high correlation coefficient (above 70%) with the input PSF. The separation between R136a3 primary and secondary is about 58.9 ± 2.14 which is larger than the FWHM of the PSF. Note that even the closest visual companions (like R136a3) are physically far from each other ($0.059''$ is 2890 AU). This visual separation produces a period over $P = 10^4 \text{yr}$, so probably these sources are not gravitationally bound to each other. Table 5.3 shows the list of the 20 stars, detected in both J and K data, which have companions closer than $0.8''$. The flux ratio between two companions in Ks and J band are given in the third and fourth column, respectively. Their separation [in mas] also is given in the last column. Among these stars, we identified visual companions for R136a1 and R136a3, for the first time.

5.5 Density and Surface Brightness Profile

The unexpected number of detected sources in a small FoV and of new resolved companions in R136 indicates that this compact cluster is more crowded than thought before. The error-bars on the stellar masses and also on the age and extinction of the cluster itself are large enough to make it difficult to study the density profile of R136. Instead, one can scrutinize the surface brightness profile (SBP) of this cluster which is less affected by the confusion and crowding. The SBP informs us on the average magnitude per pixel at different radii. Figure 5.19 depicts the SBP of the core of R136 in J and K, centered at R136a1. On average the SBP in Ks is brighter than J, which can be caused by the extinction or the brightness of the stars in Ks. One can notice a number of bumps on the SBP at 0.08, 0.15, 0.46, 1.17 pc radii roughly. These radial distances are the locations of

Table 5.3 List of 20 stars which have a companion closer than 0.08". These stars detected in both J- and Ks- band data.

ID1	ID2	$FluxRatio_K$	$FluxRatio_J$	Separation[m _{as}]
59	3(a3)	0.044 ± 0.004	0.124 ± 0.032	58.88 ± 2.14
357	272	0.699 ± 0.032	0.577 ± 0.023	59.87 ± 0.17
760	519	0.567 ± 0.095	0.896 ± 0.230	62.62 ± 5.71
643	214	0.208 ± 0.020	0.139 ± 0.036	63.67 ± 0.31
319	79	0.166 ± 0.018	0.177 ± 0.045	64.11 ± 4.23
804	517	0.512 ± 0.081	0.365 ± 0.094	65.06 ± 1.40
380	265	0.630 ± 0.140	0.324 ± 0.087	66.29 ± 1.61
807	565	0.571 ± 0.072	0.830 ± 0.228	67.12 ± 3.18
11(a9)	8(a6)	0.878 ± 0.075	0.959 ± 0.245	70.07 ± 0.88
25	4(c)	0.114 ± 0.010	0.095 ± 0.024	70.27 ± 0.07
396	56	0.079 ± 0.010	0.065 ± 0.017	71.25 ± 2.45
635	589	0.870 ± 0.126	0.730 ± 0.192	72.21 ± 2.30
541	489	0.867 ± 0.079	0.964 ± 0.247	73.65 ± 4.21
637	539	0.774 ± 0.067	1.002 ± 0.258	73.84 ± 1.08
312	87	0.197 ± 0.019	0.188 ± 0.048	74.13 ± 2.37
72	54	0.686 ± 0.066	0.714 ± 0.183	74.47 ± 0.45
16	1(a1)	0.112 ± 0.010	0.152 ± 0.039	75.32 ± 2.33
761	655	0.796 ± 0.164	0.689 ± 0.180	75.65 ± 0.61
353	305	0.819 ± 0.096	0.450 ± 0.115	75.91 ± 0.94
317	262	0.766 ± 0.085	0.413 ± 0.106	79.30 ± 0.09

known WR stars. The position of 5 WRs in the FoV is shown in the SBP plot. These stars have extensive emissions in the Ks band because of their wind and mass loss.

Using the stellar masses estimated at the age of 1 Myr and extinction values in J and K, $A_J = (0.45 \pm 0.5) \text{ mag}$ and $A_K = (0.2 \pm 0.5) \text{ mag}$, we plotted the two-dimensional (projected) density profile (Figure 5.20). We used an Elson-Fall-Freeman (EFF) profile [Elson et al. (1987)] to fit the projected mass density in the core of R136 (Eq. 5.1). We also fitted another function to the projected number density, given in Eq. 5.2 since this function provides better fitting parameters than Elson-Fall-Freeman profile.

$$\rho[M_{\odot}/pc^2] = \frac{\rho_0}{\left(1 + \frac{r^2}{a^2}\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2}}} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\rho[\text{stars}/pc^2] = \frac{\rho_0}{1 + \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^b} \quad (5.2)$$

We estimate the central mass density of $\rho_0 = (2.82_{0.82}^{1.16}) \times 10^4 [M_{\odot}/pc^2]$ and the parameters $\gamma = 1.23 \pm 0.24$ and $a = 0.17 \pm 0.06$. For the number density, we found $\rho_0 = 288 \pm 27 [\text{stars}/pc^2]$ and the parameters $a = 0.87 \pm 0.04$ and $b = 4.55 \pm 0.37$. Total observed mass of the clusters for $r < 1.4 pc$ is $M_{obs} = (1.33_{0.22}^{0.30}) \times 10^4 M_{\odot}$. We could detect stellar masses down to $2 M_{\odot}$, so total mass of the cluster depends on the shape of MF and the lowest mass limit. The real stellar masses remain open as we are limited to the angular resolution of SPHERE/IRDIS, so the estimated central projected density is a lower limit to the real central density.

Note that the estimated density is projected in two-dimension (2D). In order to estimate the three dimensional (3D) density approximately, we consider R136 is spherically symmetric and has a radius of $R_{cluster}$. The density profiles are estimated for different $R_{cluster}$ values, from 2 pc to 6pc. Hence, 3D central densities, γ and a are computed by fitting EFF profile (Eq. 5.1). Table 5.4, shows the fitting (3D) parameters for R136 considering different values of $R_{cluster}$. Figure 5.22 depicts the 3D density profiles for different values of $R_{cluster}$.

Table 5.4 Estimation of central density of R136 in three-dimension considering different $R_{cluster}$. First column gives the hypothetical radius of the cluster. The second column is the three-dimensional central mass density. Third and fourth columns are the fitting parameters, γ and a , in the Eq. 5.1. Finally the last column is the ratio of observed mass which is limited by $r < 1.4 pc$, to the total mass estimated of the cluster, within a given radius. $M_{obs} = (1.33_{0.22}^{0.30}) \times 10^4 M_{\odot}$.

$R_{cluster}$ [pc]	$\log(\rho_0)$ [M_{\odot}/pc^3]	γ	a	M_{obs}/M_{total}
2	3.86 ± 0.16	1.24 ± 0.23	0.18 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.02
3	3.68 ± 0.15	1.39 ± 0.26	0.20 ± 0.06	0.82 ± 0.03
4	3.55 ± 0.15	1.45 ± 0.27	0.21 ± 0.06	0.77 ± 0.04
5	3.46 ± 0.16	1.49 ± 0.28	0.22 ± 0.07	0.74 ± 0.04
6	3.38 ± 0.16	1.51 ± 0.28	0.23 ± 0.07	0.72 ± 0.04

The total mass of the cluster can be estimated by extrapolating to the considered $R_{cluster}$. Figure 5.21 shows the cumulative total mass of the cluster within 6pc. The estimated half-mass radius is $(0.57 \pm 0.04) pc$. The ratio of the observed total mass within $r < 1.4 pc$ to the total mass estimated of the cluster, within a given radius ($R_{cluster}$) also is given in the last column of Table 5.4.

Estimated value of γ and a in 2D and 3D are consistent and the shape of the densities are flatter than Plummer model (close to King model). All the 3D central densities, γ and a are smaller than the previous values given by Mackey & Gilmore (2003) and Selman & Melnick (2013).

5.6 Discussion and conclusion

In this study we presented photometric analysis of the core of R136 using the VLT/SPHERE instrument in the near-IR. The high quality and resolution of these data open a new perspective on our understandings on R136. For the first time, more than thousand sources have been detected

in K and J-band data in the small FoV of IRDIS ($10.9'' \times 12.3''$) covering almost 2.7×3.1 pc of R136's core. HST WFPC2 and WFC3 data, due to a lower resolution and pixel sampling, did not detect such a number of sources in the R136's core. For the ground-based telescopes, the best data comes from VLT/MAD, where the AO quality (Strehl ratios of 15-30% in Ks) is not as good as with SPHERE (Strehl ratios of 75% in Ks). So the confusion, especially in the core remains large enough for the sources being undetectable in its core.

In SPHERE/IRDIS data, more than 60% of stars have companions closer than $0.2''$ (0.05 pc). 90% of the very massive bright stars which already have been studied spectroscopically by Crowther et al. (2016), have visual companions. The large error-bars on the spectroscopic parameters (T_{eff} and $\log L$) prevent us to estimate the age, extinction and stellar masses accurately. Using the stellar parameters by Crowther et al. (2016) from the UV spectroscopically analysis, the most probable age of the core is about $1.8_{-0.8}^{+1.2}$ Myr (Figure 5.14) which is consistent with the Crowther et al. (2016) values. But we find the best age estimation about 1 and 1.5 Myr for the very core ($r < 3''$) and outside ($r > 3''$) of R 136, from fitting isochrones with CMD. We clearly see the conjunction of pre-main-sequence and main-sequence, which is very sensitive to the age. The extinction in J and K are 0.45 ± 0.5 and 0.2 ± 0.5 magnitude, respectively. The extinction is estimated from stellar parameters of 54 spectroscopically studied stars by Crowther et al. (2016). So the large errors on the extinction values comes from the large errors on the spectroscopically analysis on $\log L$ and T_{eff} . Considering the photometric errors, the stellar masses are estimated at different ages with a broad extinction range. The MF slope for 1 and 1.5 Myr isochrone are $\Gamma_{1Myr} = -0.90 \pm 0.13$ and $\Gamma_{1.5Myr} = -0.98 \pm 0.18$, respectively, for the mass range of (3 - 300) M_{\odot} .

As the core gets better resolved, more stars are detected. The MF slope is more flat than Kroupa ($\Gamma = -1.3$) and Salpeter ($\Gamma = -1.35$) values. Thanks to the SPHERE's high contrast data we estimated the MF from $3.0 M_{\odot}$ up to $300 M_{\odot}$ at different ages. The estimated MF slopes are consistent with the values estimated by Malumuth & Heap (1994), Hunter et al. (1996) and

Selman et al (1999) for the core of R 136. These values are more flat than the values estimated by Massey & Hunter (1998) and Brandl et al. (1996). Table 2.7 shows the MF slopes estimated for R 136 in previous works, for different mass range and regions. The direct comparison is not logical since 1) None of the previous observations, within the IRDIS FoV, covers the mass range of this study. 2) Our MF slopes are estimated considering the errors on each stellar masses (see sec. 4) while the previous studies did not apply the stellar masses errors in the MF. The derived MF is limited to the resolution of the instrument and also on the detection limit of the observation. Higher angular resolution data may resolve binaries and low-mass stars which affects the shape of MF. Figure 5.20 shows the density profile of the R136's core at 1 Myr ($0.1 pc < r < 1.4 pc$). The lower limit of the central density of R136 is $\rho_0 = (2.82_{0.82}^{1.16}) \times 10^4 [M_\odot / pc^2]$ at 1 Myr which is about $\rho_0 = 288 [stars / pc^2]$. As the mass estimation in the very core of R136 is biased by crowding and also for massive WR stars, we exclude the first point from fitting the density profile. The observed total mass of R 136 for $r < 1.4 pc$ is $M_{obs} = (1.33_{0.22}^{0.30}) \times 10^4 M_\odot$ which covers the mass range of (2 - 300) M_\odot . This mass is about 51% of the whole mass range of (0.01 - 300) M_\odot using Chabrier MF [Chabrier (2003), Chabrier (2005)].

Considering R136 is a spherically symmetric cluster with Radius $R_{cluster}$ (Table 5.4), we estimated 3D density profile. The 3D central densities are smaller than the values estimated in previous studies. Computed values of γ and a (Eq. 5.1) are consistent in 2D and 3D considering different $R_{cluster}$. All density profiles are flatter than Plummer model ($\gamma = 4.0$).

Very massive stars in R136 have similar characteristics as the galactic WR stars in the core of NGC3603. NGC3603 is almost 8 times closer than R136. One can see the effect of confusion in Figure 5.23 in which we visualize NGC3603 at the distance of R136 (Figure 5.23 Middle). Using Starfinder we detected 408 and 288 stars in J and Ks images respectively [Khorrami et al. 2016]. Using the same criteria for Starfinder, we only detect 109 and 52 sources in J and Ks images of NGC3603 at the distance of R136, which means that more than 70% of the stars cannot be

detected. This implies that about 1000 detected stars in the R136's core ($r < 6''$) are possibly 30% of the real number. The average density in this region ($r < 6''$) would increase from 71 [star/pc²] to 230 [star/pc²]. The lack of resolution prevents us to accurately estimate stellar masses, core density and density profile, whilst SBP turns out to be less affected. Figure 5.24 shows the SBP of NGC3603 both from IRDIS data in J and Ks band, directly and simulated as would be located at a distance of R136. The general trend is not affected.

Using SPHERE data, we have gone one step further and partially resolved and understood the core of R136 but this is certainly not the final step. R136 needs to be observed in the future with higher resolution (E-ELT) and/or a more stable PSF (JWST), therefore deeper field imaging. The cluster would then be better characterized for its age, individual and multiple stars and ultimately its kinematics on a long enough temporal baseline of observation.

Figure 5.11 Top: map of the PSF fitting errors (outcome of the SExtractor photometry) along the IRDIS FoV. Middle: map of the residual errors, outcome of the background analysis after removing the stellar sources signals from the image. Bottom: map of the total error, combination of the PSF-fitting errors and the residuals background errors. Left: J; Right: K

Figure 5.12 Top: r136 in K (left) and J (right) with the circle of 3'' radii. Bottom: Incompleteness test in J (red pluses) and Ks (blue crosses) for two regions: Very core of R136 ($r < 3''$) in the left and outside of the core ($r > 3''$) in the right.

Figure 5.13 The top image corresponds to the IRDIS/Ks on which the 54 spectroscopically known stars from [Crowther et al. (2016)] have been added as red circles. The bottom plot depicts the T_{eff} , $\log L/L_{\odot}$ and corresponding error-bars on these 54 sources taken from Crowther et al. 2016 in blue. The solid red lines indicate the PARSEC isochrones covering ages from 0.1 to 8 Myr.

Figure 5.14 Generalized histogram of the age of 54 known stars from Crowther et al. 2016. (shown in Figure 5.13). We used PARSEC isochrones at different ages to estimate the age-range for each spectroscopically known stars. This result can be compared with the age distribution of this sample which was observed in UV, by Crowther et al. 2016 (their Fig. 11).

Figure 5.15 Generalized histogram of the extinction of 54 spectroscopically known stars from Crowther et al. 2016. (shown in Figure 5.13). We used PARSEC models to estimate the extinction for each of these stars according to its age-range.

Figure 5.16 Top: CMD of 818 detected sources in J and Ks band images of SPHERE/IRDIS from the core of R136. Solid black, green and blue lines show the PARSEC isochrones at the ages of 0.6, 1 and 1.5 Myr (corrected for distance modulus of 18.49 and central values of extinctions, $A_J = 0.45$ mag and $A_K = 0.2$ mag). The horizontal dashed grey line depicts the incompleteness of 70%. The CMD is plotted for the whole FoV (818 sources), in the very core of the cluster ($r < 3''$) and outside ($r > 3''$), from left to right respectively. The error-bars on each point is the combination of the PSF-fitting errors and the residual errors from the background image after removing the stellar sources signals from the images. The 54 spectroscopically studied stars by Crowther et al. 2016 is shown in black dots in the middle plot. Bottom: Same as top CMD but in 3D to show the number density of stars in the CMD. Solid red, black, blue and pink lines depict PARSEC isochrones at the age of 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 Myr, respectively.

Figure 5.17 Generalized histogram of the stellar masses (MF) at 0.6, 1 and 1.5 Myr. PARSEC models used to estimate the stellar-mass range for each source using extinction-range.

Figure 5.18 Top: Histogram of the separation of the close detected sources. For each star which is detected in both J and K data, we determined a distance between the star and its closest neighbor. Bottom: Separation of the visual close detected sources versus their distance from the core of R136.

Figure 5.19 Left: Surface brightness profile (mag/pixel) of R136 in IRDIS FoV centered on R136a1. Right: same as Left, but the differences in the Kmag/pixel and Jmag/pixel is shown.

Figure 5.20 Projected density profile of R136 in IRDIS FoV centered on R136a1. Up: number density [stars/pc^2]. Number of stars is taken from the catalog of common stars between IRDIS, J and Ks data. Bottom: mass density [M_{\odot}/pc^2]. The stellar masses are estimated at the age of 2 Myr with extinction values of $A_J = 0.45 \pm 0.5$ and $A_K = 0.2 \pm 0.5$ in J and Ks band. Eq. 5.1 and Eq. 5.2 are used to fit the blue solid line to the data in upper and bottom plots, respectively.

Figure 5.21 Cumulative total mass of R136 using extrapolation in 2D.

Figure 5.22 The 3D mass density profiles for different values of R_{cluster} . I used Eq. 5.1 for fitting. The fitting parameters, γ and a , are given in Table 5.4.

Figure 5.23 Comparison of NGC3603 and R136 images from VLT/SPHERE. Left: Core of R136 ($1.56'' \times 1.56''$) at its real distance. Right: Core of NGC3603 ($12.5'' \times 12.5''$) at its real distance. Middle: NGC3603 as it would appear at the same distance as R136. Upper and bottom panels are in IRDIS Ks and J band bands images, respectively.

Figure 5.24 Top: SBP of NGC3603 in SPHERE/IRDIS J and K band data. Bottom: the difference of $K_{\text{mag}}/\text{pixel} - J_{\text{mag}}/\text{pixel}$. Left: NGC3603 real images. Right: NGC3603 in the distance of R136.

Figure 5.25 Reconstructed image of the R136 taken by IRDIS/Ks. The position and flux of stellar sources is estimated by Starfinder.

Figure 5.26 FoV: $1.225'' \times 1.225''$ of the core of R136 taken by HST in V-band at the top (Left:WFC2 and Right: WFC3). At Bottom is the reconstructed images of IRDIS/Ks (left) and E-ELT/MICADO/Ks (right), with the same FoV as top images.

Good-bye to Supermassive Stars

THE CASE for supermassive and superluminous stars received a series of body blows recently. For several years astronomers have suspected that stars several thousand times more massive than the Sun might be lurking in giant nebulae. However, new observations have shown that there is no supermassive star in one of the most likely locations for such an object, the mysterious heart of the 30 Doradus nebula in the Large Magellanic Cloud. This nebula, also called the Tarantula or NGC 2070, is a giant cloud of ionized hydrogen (H II), luminous enough to be visible with the unaided eye even though it lies some 180,000 light-years away. At the nebula's center is a cluster of very hot blue stars, with a fuzzy, 10th-magnitude core about 5 arc seconds across. This central patch of light is named R136 (HD 38268), and its brightest part, R136a, is itself a multiple object (see page 134 of the February, 1984, issue).

The 30 Doradus nebula is a relatively nearby example of giant H II regions; one in our own Milky Way galaxy is NGC 3603 in Carina. In the centers of these massive clouds lie bizarre objects indeed. For example, R136a is only a few light-years across, but emits as much energy as 50 to 100 million Suns, or several dozen of the hottest known O-type supergiants.

Clearly something unusual is going on in the centers of 30 Doradus and its kin, but just what kind of objects release energy at such prodigious rates in such small volumes of space? There have been two popular explanations: supermassive objects with masses 1,000 or more times that

of the Sun, or extremely dense clusters of otherwise normal stars. To decide between the different possibilities requires observations with resolution much better than an arc second.

Anthony Moffat of the University of Montreal and collaborators from West Germany and the United States report on CCD (charge-coupled device) direct images and spectra in the August 1, 1985, *Astrophysical Journal*. They found no evidence indicating the presence of a single supermassive body in R136a. Instead, it appears to consist of several stars with absolute visual magnitudes no brighter than -7 or -8 , within the range of previously known stars. The observations are best fitted by the presence of a compact group of O and B stars together with a few — four or five — Wolf-Rayet stars. (These objects are rare but among the hottest and most luminous known. Surrounded by expanding plasma, they are presumably evolved O stars.) Spectra showing a combination of O and Wolf-Rayet features confirm this interpretation.

The central density of stars in this compact grouping is just below the maximum found for globular clusters in our galaxy. After 10 to 100 million years, when all the massive blue-white stars have burned out, the center of the Tarantula should resemble the so-called blue globular clusters found in the Large Magellanic Cloud.

A complementary spectroscopic study carried out in Chile by Jorge Melnich reached similar conclusions. His report, to be published in *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, concludes: "There is no need for

the presence of an exotic object in the core of the cluster. . . ."

Moffat and his co-workers find similar results for NGC 3603, whose core is known as HD 97950. While this is the most massive H II region in the Milky Way that can be studied at visible wavelengths, its stellar mass is only about one third that of the 30 Doradus complex. Here there are only two or three Wolf-Rayet stars, but the activity is concentrated in a much smaller volume. As a result, the central star density in NGC 3603 may be some 300 times greater than in 30 Doradus — possibly due to the greater efficiency of star formation in our galaxy. As Moffat told *Sky & Telescope*, "If you think R136 in 30 Doradus is exotic, then NGC 3603 is beyond this." It is a rare type of object in the Milky Way and may not survive in its present form for long. What it will turn into is uncertain.

The central objects in 30 Doradus and NGC 3603 have been directly resolved by Gerd Weigelt and collaborators from the Physical Institute in Erlangen, West Germany. Their speckle interferometry confirmed that R136a is a dense cluster and showed eight stars within an apparent diameter of 1 arc second. As the illustration below, center, shows, the grouping is dominated by three objects with almost the same brightness: R136a1, a2, and a3. Similarly, the core of NGC 3603 was revealed as a cluster of four stars. Details can be found in the September (I) and October (I), 1985, issues of *Astronomy and Astrophysics*.

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Left: R136a and the central area of the 30 Doradus nebula as imaged in blue light at the prime focus of the 4-meter reflector of Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory. The small circle shows a region 5.5 light-years across at the distance of the nebula — the same physical size as the circle on the image of NGC 3603. Unless otherwise credited, the illustrations in this article were provided by A. Moffat and first appeared in the *Astrophysical Journal*. Right: The core of NGC 3603, a giant H II region in the Milky Way, is seen here in blue light. The circle has a diameter of 59 arc seconds, corresponding to the same 5.5-light-year circle in the image of 30 Doradus. Note that the central-star density in NGC 3603 far exceeds that of 30 Doradus. Center: R136a, the mysterious object at the center of 30 Doradus, is actually a dense cluster of at least eight stars, as shown in this reconstructed speckle-interferometer image. The three bright objects are, from left to right, R136a2, a1, and a3. Some 4,000 speckle interferograms were taken with the 1.5-meter Danish telescope at the European Southern Observatory by G. Weigelt and G. Baier, and combined to form this image, which was published in *Astronomy and Astrophysics*.

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Chapter 6

Summary and prospects

In this chapter we are going to summarize our main results, both from the photometric analysis and Nbody simulations.

6.1 Main results

In this thesis, we carried out a comprehensive photometric study of the core of two young massive star clusters: NGC3603 and R136, located in most massive HII regions. Series of numerical Nbody6 simulations were done in order to study the effect of initial parameters on the evolution of R136-like clusters.

6.1.1 NGC3603

We analyzed the imaging data of the core of NGC3603 using HST/WFPC2 (F547M, F675W, F814W), HST/ACS/HRC (F250W, F330W, F435W, F550M, F658N, F850LP) and VLT/SPHERE/IRDIS (B-J, B-Ks). In each sets of data, we corrected the extinction for O-type stars (class V) in each field for each filter. Then we used Geneva (for HST data) and PARSEC (for SPHERE data) evolutionary

models and proper atmosphere models (TLUSTY for O and B stars and KURUCZ for others), in order to estimate the stellar masses in each image. The mass function and its slope derived for each data in different radial distances from the core of the cluster. HST analysis of the core of NGC3603, shows the effect of mass segregation as the slope in the core is much flatter than the outer regions. This flatten slope of the core is more in WFPC2 data compared to HRC. HRC data have better angular resolution and pixel sampling than WFPC2 data. So the flatten slope of the core can be a signature of the observational confusion. In the Chapter 4 we presented the results of the SPHERE data analysis of the very core of NGC36303 (F0) and the next radial bin (F1 and F2) in J and K band. SPHERE/IRDIS has better resolution and higher pixel sampling. Also the observation were done in near Infrared which the problem of extinction is much less than in the visible. In SPHERE data, we could detect more faint low-mass stars leading to have steeper MF slope for the core. The MF study of the core of NGC3603 with SPHERE/IRDIS data shows no signature of mass segregation for two main reasons: First, MF slope in the very core is not flatter than the next radial bin. Second, both slopes are similar to the MF values found in the previous works for the outer regions. Comparing results of the WFPC2, HRC and SPHERE data, we conclude that the flatten MF slope in the core of NGC3603 can be explain by the observational confusion rather than segregation, as the slope become steeper as the resolution improves.

6.1.2 R136

For R136, we analyzed the HST/WFPC2 data in visible (F555W, F814W) and VLT/SPHERE data in near infrared (B-J and B-Ks). For the HST analysis of the core of R136, we used Geneva with normal and high mass-loss rates and PARSEC evolutionary models. To correct the extinction for the O type stars (class V) we used the TLUSTY atmosphere model. The mass function derived in different color at 1, 1.5 and 2 Myr. Although MF slope in the core is flatter than the outer radii but it is difficult to suggest the mass segregation as an explanation because of the uncertainties due to

the lower resolution from the large distance and due to the extinction.

The resolution of SPHERE data is much better than the HST and we detected over thousands of sources in J and K band data. The majority (above 90%) of massive stars (brighter than 17 mag in K and 16 mag in J) have visual companions closer than 0.2". Among them, R136a1 (most massive star in the Local universe) and r136C have visual companions which are detected for the first time. R136a3 was resolved as two stars (PSF fitting). Considering the spectroscopic and photometric errors on the extinction ($A(J) = 1.3 \pm 0.5$ and $A(K) = 0.4 \pm 0.5$) and the age ($1.8_{-0.8}^{+1.2}$ Myr) of the cluster members, we estimate a mass range for each detected star. The generalized histogram of stellar masses (MF) was plotted at different ages with a given error on each stellar mass. The MF slopes (from generalized histogram of mass) at 1, 1.7 and 2 Myr is steeper than the HST/WFPC2 studies. This gives us a clue that the observed segregation in previous studies might be an observational confusion again. Future instruments with better resolution will clarify this.

In parallel to photometric analysis of R136, we made a series of Nbody6 simulations of young massive R136-like clusters. These clusters have different initial binaries and segregation degree and each cluster is simulated with and without stellar evolution of member stars. In this way we could see the effect of these parameters on the dynamical evolution of R136-like clusters at the early stages of their life (4 Myr). Segregated clusters with stellar evolution expand more. Total mass loss of the clusters with stellar evolution is much higher than the clusters which evolve purely dynamically. Low-mass binaries dissolve very fast (less than 1 Myr) and massive binary systems dissolve because of the stellar evolution. In all the simulations, binaries keep the memory of initial eccentricity distribution during the 4 Myr and only the massive binaries keep the memory of the initial period distribution. To compare the results of the Nbody6 simulations to the HST/WFPC2 images, we wrote a code (ZSCENE) in IDL which calculated the flux of the stars (mass and position is given by Nbody6) in each HST filter using TLUSTY and KURUCZ atmosphere models in combination to the Geneva evolutionary models. The resolution and pixel scale of the synthetic

images are the same as HST/WFPC2. To compare these synthetic images to HST data, we used four methods: SBP, R_{hl} , $R_{neighbor}$ and MF comparison. Using 4 criteria all together, even though they are not completely independent, we conclude that R136 is best represented by non-segregated clusters (in $r < 4\text{pc}$).

6.2 Prospects

We are going to analyze the SPHERE/ZIMPOL data on the core of both clusters which in principle have better resolution and higher pixel sampling. The ZIMPOL observations provide high-contrast polarized imaging to study the structures around these bright targets and detect the presence of dust in polarized light. The asymmetries of objects due to multiplicities and extended atmosphere and winds, can be investigated using ZIMPOL data.

We are going to compare the HST/WFC3 data with VLT/SPHERE as they are complementary in covering visible and infrared wavelengths. For R136, the proper motion of some stars can be estimated by comparing HST data in 1995 and SPHERE data in 2015. In 20 Years, stars with velocity of 200 Km/s will move about 16 mas. So it is feasible to detect the movement of some stars with velocities higher than 200 km/s by comparing HST and SPHERE data. The numerical analysis of R136 will be completed by making the synthetic images with SPHERE/IRDIS resolution to be compared with IRDIS data in J and K band.

6.3 Look into the future

Lack of high-angular-resolution brings confusion and most of the models we actually use are based on the observational data which suffer from this confusion. To overcome this problem, we can either:

- 1) increase the angular resolution of the instruments: switch to bigger telescopes with better

AO systems or use interferometry with longer base-lines.

2) decrease the output of the model's resolution to be compared with the observational data. The method we used to compare the results of the Nbody6 code with HST data, can be applied to any other instrument.

The comprehensive study of R136-like clusters can be done with the imaging and spectroscopic analysis of the future higher angular resolution instruments. Two first-light instruments of E-ELT, a diffraction-limited near-infrared imager (ELT-CAM or MICADO) and a single-field near-infrared wide-band integral field spectrograph (ELT-IFU or HARMONI), can provide a unique data to understand the kinematics and resolve the stellar members of R136-like clusters. With 3mas angular resolution, we can detect the stellar movements with 36 km/s within one month observation using MICADO (see Table 1.2). Using 8000 spectral resolution, we can detect the radial velocity of the stellar objects with 37.5 km/s using HARMONI. Putting these information together, one can find the stellar masses, positions and 3D velocities using MICADO and HARMONI within a month for 50-60 arcsec foV, which perfectly covers the core of R136 cluster. JWST (see Table 1.2) has wider FoV, 2.2-4.4 arcmin which can cover the whole 30Doradus region. But the imaging and spectroscopic data will not have the resolution of E-ELT instruments. For example, Near Infrared Camera (NIRcam) has 22 mas resolution and the Near Infrared Spectrograph (NIRSpec) has 1000 spectral resolution, in the same wavelength bands as E-ELT. So we can detect stars with high radial velocities (more than 300 km/s) using NIRSpec and unfortunately the pixel sampling of NIRcam (32mas/pix) is not as good as E-ELT (3mas/pix). So a star with 300 km/s will move one pixel in the NIRcam within almost 26 years. To sum up, It seems that using E-ELT we can find achieve to the higher angular resolution than JWST and can understand the kinematics of the R136, even the velocity dispersion of the stars within a month. This is not comparable to the all works which have been done on R136!

Appendix A

SPHERE/IRDIS catalog of NGC3603

The SPHERE/IRDIS catalog of the common sources between J and K-band data of NGC3603 in F0, F1 and F2. The IDk, Xpix and Ypix are the identification and pixel position in the IRDIS K-band image. CorrK and CorrJ are the Correlation coefficient between the input PSF and detected star.

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
F0							F0						
1	419.67	527.30	6.91	0.98	8.15	0.72	2	481.42	541.53	7.01	0.95	8.11	0.75
3	313.34	571.16	7.76	0.98	8.31	0.86	4	477.77	511.51	8.82	0.96	9.27	0.94
5	755.70	777.97	9.31	0.99	10.48	0.99	6	627.76	474.92	9.34	0.99	10.08	0.99
7	453.80	538.79	9.36	0.99	9.77	1.00	8	488.01	826.72	9.44	0.99	10.11	0.96
9	707.11	502.78	9.58	0.99	10.49	0.93	10	143.49	360.65	9.61	0.95	11.76	0.91
11	174.40	581.22	9.72	0.97	10.10	0.86	12	589.55	490.92	9.73	0.97	10.35	0.98
13	704.56	484.47	9.82	0.94	11.23	0.84	14	705.09	697.66	9.87	0.98	10.69	0.91
15	511.37	648.01	9.88	0.98	10.34	0.91	16	449.61	449.66	10.28	0.92	10.70	0.96
17	207.43	799.27	10.31	0.96	10.84	0.86	18	380.56	513.76	10.37	0.96	12.14	0.97
19	305.87	738.34	10.46	0.98	10.89	0.89	20	231.86	313.99	10.58	1.00	11.12	1.00
21	521.73	641.20	10.68	0.99	11.15	0.93	22	634.89	503.61	10.69	0.98	11.34	0.95
23	693.88	558.52	10.75	0.96	11.59	0.91	24	818.88	224.83	10.76	0.99	11.94	0.93
25	656.55	626.50	10.78	0.94	11.46	0.93	26	908.41	393.61	10.79	0.94	12.20	0.85

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
27	523.39	519.68	10.79	0.97	12.52	0.90	28	455.34	452.22	10.87	0.98	11.29	0.86
29	544.44	292.18	10.88	0.97	11.58	0.92	30	806.73	779.12	10.90	0.99	11.91	0.96
31	207.46	788.39	10.93	0.95	12.75	0.87	32	872.39	476.95	10.96	0.96	12.25	0.97
33	723.17	473.54	11.04	0.97	11.87	0.86	34	578.20	874.90	11.04	0.99	11.84	0.89
35	612.83	616.86	11.06	0.99	11.68	0.99	36	386.92	392.65	11.09	0.98	11.54	0.96
37	275.47	548.72	11.27	0.96	12.62	0.93	38	510.41	630.33	11.31	0.96	13.23	0.85
39	569.86	386.66	11.33	0.98	11.94	0.95	40	759.48	915.64	11.39	0.95	12.48	0.95
41	521.76	624.02	11.44	0.99	11.90	0.98	42	244.60	844.25	11.45	0.97	12.06	0.91
43	376.76	568.11	11.46	0.99	11.77	0.97	44	299.43	1009.87	11.47	0.97	12.33	0.96
45	847.81	518.25	11.47	0.99	12.57	0.92	46	742.72	752.43	11.50	0.96	12.55	0.81
47	587.42	863.76	11.53	0.97	12.31	0.96	48	717.72	460.41	11.59	0.97	12.44	0.88
49	226.92	297.54	11.73	0.97	12.35	0.92	50	824.54	483.86	11.76	0.97	12.72	0.95
51	272.27	100.67	11.80	0.98	12.71	0.89	52	852.41	492.93	11.86	0.98	14.16	0.95
53	731.53	511.48	11.89	0.94	13.48	0.88	54	690.67	409.06	11.91	0.99	12.71	0.98
55	568.57	365.83	11.91	0.97	12.55	0.96	56	420.94	137.43	12.08	0.97	12.97	0.92
57	443.19	264.65	12.16	0.98	14.57	0.81	58	649.64	374.53	12.26	0.95	13.22	0.87
59	684.99	746.61	12.33	0.98	14.74	0.91	60	648.02	558.71	12.35	0.99	13.01	0.95
61	262.65	982.73	12.38	0.97	13.29	0.99	62	498.36	387.30	12.38	0.97	12.91	0.90
63	371.86	480.98	12.39	1.00	13.53	0.99	64	639.72	602.94	12.46	0.99	13.22	0.99
65	469.86	388.36	12.52	0.98	13.16	0.93	66	109.47	423.11	12.60	0.97	13.10	0.91
67	761.40	627.71	12.62	0.96	13.67	0.95	68	768.33	621.12	12.63	0.98	13.89	0.93
69	729.17	1008.02	12.64	0.99	13.93	0.89	70	182.27	161.99	12.64	0.99	14.91	0.91
71	520.53	189.05	12.65	0.97	13.50	0.94	73	769.99	803.47	12.74	0.97	13.76	0.85
74	619.96	451.24	12.75	0.99	14.73	0.88	75	222.85	499.66	12.77	0.97	13.83	0.97
76	516.78	65.10	12.88	0.99	14.71	0.98	77	296.37	387.44	12.89	0.95	13.31	0.82
78	569.12	486.69	12.90	0.99	14.17	0.93	79	515.83	732.76	12.93	0.99	13.49	0.99
80	357.35	670.43	13.04	0.95	13.56	0.84	81	607.34	840.35	13.05	0.97	13.84	0.85
82	596.97	447.85	13.05	0.99	14.11	0.96	83	744.77	767.45	13.06	0.95	14.51	0.89
84	72.33	834.01	13.09	0.98	14.35	0.88	85	449.41	434.44	13.09	0.95	13.54	0.85

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
86	225.18	332.69	13.10	0.98	13.61	0.92	87	292.62	107.14	13.14	0.97	14.06	0.95
88	366.26	392.07	13.18	0.99	13.62	0.92	89	137.47	321.62	13.23	0.95	14.45	0.92
90	478.22	712.41	13.24	0.97	13.99	0.81	91	781.48	343.84	13.25	0.96	14.41	0.93
92	177.67	507.16	13.27	0.98	13.68	0.97	93	926.57	772.83	13.29	0.97	14.92	0.98
94	682.94	554.88	13.33	0.99	14.07	0.98	95	353.01	571.48	13.33	0.96	14.22	0.88
96	895.05	364.94	13.34	1.00	15.17	0.94	97	682.02	394.52	13.37	0.96	16.38	0.89
98	545.91	563.76	13.38	0.99	14.46	0.97	100	328.02	66.97	13.41	0.99	14.47	0.99
101	344.86	806.58	13.49	0.97	14.89	0.96	103	601.33	474.02	13.50	0.97	14.55	0.95
104	664.55	892.56	13.52	0.94	14.49	0.93	105	911.57	916.34	13.59	0.96	14.92	0.93
106	670.04	533.67	13.62	0.97	16.46	0.93	107	363.67	486.38	13.64	0.95	14.07	0.93
108	407.61	228.09	13.65	0.97	14.60	0.96	109	424.58	445.84	13.66	0.97	14.38	0.96
111	135.99	199.96	13.68	0.99	15.09	0.98	112	874.67	475.63	13.70	0.81	13.10	0.82
113	698.41	209.37	13.72	0.95	15.47	0.88	114	172.55	780.39	13.77	0.94	14.35	0.85
115	615.11	170.25	13.77	0.98	14.97	0.94	116	154.72	597.76	13.77	0.97	14.26	0.93
117	276.29	312.89	13.79	0.98	15.01	0.91	118	273.24	787.39	13.80	0.96	15.16	0.85
119	534.09	658.38	13.81	0.96	15.25	0.81	121	692.46	406.81	13.81	0.89	14.21	0.90
122	251.11	170.16	13.85	0.98	14.73	0.96	123	401.22	182.46	13.87	0.95	14.67	0.89
124	480.83	344.83	13.89	0.98	14.70	0.97	125	131.38	462.33	13.90	0.95	14.97	0.86
126	534.12	655.41	13.91	0.85	15.64	0.83	128	813.55	150.64	13.97	0.94	16.07	0.83
129	826.73	247.49	13.97	0.95	15.16	0.93	130	560.72	964.11	13.99	0.98	14.92	0.96
132	474.57	731.97	14.02	0.96	14.78	0.98	133	160.72	491.51	14.04	0.95	14.45	0.87
134	318.05	76.46	14.04	0.96	14.96	0.94	136	675.62	287.07	14.10	0.97	15.13	0.97
137	434.29	54.47	14.10	0.95	15.93	0.83	138	845.47	348.77	14.12	0.95	15.87	0.94
139	820.17	545.11	14.12	0.98	15.75	0.90	140	580.94	453.57	14.13	0.97	15.75	0.92
141	181.45	734.38	14.13	0.92	15.44	0.87	142	533.79	505.96	14.16	0.98	14.78	0.99
143	514.14	695.42	14.19	0.97	15.12	0.85	144	883.53	614.47	14.19	0.93	15.68	0.83
145	353.32	185.71	14.20	0.96	15.09	0.92	146	867.20	735.66	14.20	0.95	16.08	0.89
147	920.25	131.36	14.20	0.95	15.81	0.88	148	659.68	430.21	14.24	0.96	14.95	0.94
149	170.78	528.98	14.25	0.97	15.40	0.97	150	610.53	999.22	14.26	0.95	16.02	0.84

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
151	484.61	490.31	14.27	0.92	15.56	0.84	152	615.96	514.91	14.30	0.97	14.96	0.93
153	462.11	440.63	14.30	0.96	15.60	0.86	154	654.22	671.22	14.31	0.97	15.90	0.92
155	272.60	399.78	14.33	0.95	15.62	0.90	156	217.44	811.06	14.33	0.95	15.74	0.92
157	519.70	584.11	14.33	0.96	15.60	0.98	158	844.48	335.70	14.34	0.94	16.03	0.91
159	858.51	419.58	14.37	0.93	15.96	0.87	160	557.52	708.42	14.37	0.93	15.09	0.91
161	287.39	447.81	14.39	0.95	15.61	0.88	162	616.61	148.20	14.42	0.94	15.60	0.95
163	451.24	748.19	14.43	0.95	15.00	0.93	164	338.40	522.89	14.44	0.95	15.65	0.89
165	838.44	780.12	14.46	0.95	16.14	0.91	166	295.91	600.77	14.48	0.96	15.70	0.83
167	145.74	915.00	14.49	0.96	15.42	0.97	168	218.94	985.75	14.49	0.94	16.88	0.88
169	899.32	677.87	14.49	0.95	16.42	0.92	170	325.49	657.27	14.49	0.93	14.91	0.85
171	280.24	386.12	14.51	0.97	15.77	0.89	172	78.24	371.64	14.52	0.96	15.98	0.85
173	853.15	400.85	14.53	0.98	16.45	0.87	174	121.97	971.66	14.56	0.91	16.37	0.93
175	597.74	565.09	14.56	0.96	16.15	0.88	176	260.78	602.32	14.57	0.95	15.91	0.98
177	458.19	491.59	14.59	0.94	15.04	0.88	178	73.48	656.23	14.59	0.94	18.02	0.82
179	272.39	451.83	14.60	0.93	15.84	0.90	180	368.08	637.73	14.65	0.94	15.81	0.91
181	202.45	234.54	14.67	0.90	16.09	0.90	182	104.33	899.43	14.69	0.90	16.35	0.85
183	744.47	497.84	14.72	0.95	16.24	0.88	185	630.74	564.32	14.73	0.92	16.29	0.97
186	249.63	177.06	14.75	0.92	16.49	0.94	187	430.63	752.95	14.78	0.93	16.11	0.91
189	319.28	42.00	14.79	0.88	16.66	0.85	190	107.84	932.93	14.81	0.94	16.54	0.98
191	203.65	763.82	14.83	0.93	16.34	0.90	192	373.07	470.28	14.86	0.93	16.27	0.86
193	529.28	335.34	14.89	0.88	16.52	0.85	194	209.25	467.34	14.91	0.93	16.24	0.83
196	593.98	206.86	14.92	0.96	15.70	0.96	197	665.35	547.00	14.93	0.92	16.63	0.92
198	85.75	620.67	14.98	0.91	16.27	0.91	199	369.73	776.37	14.98	0.91	16.20	0.85
200	215.05	197.78	15.01	0.91	16.31	0.88	201	246.70	403.63	15.02	0.91	16.48	0.87
202	678.71	795.58	15.02	0.91	16.69	0.93	203	359.98	146.18	15.03	0.93	16.76	0.83
204	746.24	650.66	15.04	0.90	16.53	0.89	205	529.14	561.94	15.04	0.93	16.46	0.90
206	76.78	582.14	15.05	0.93	16.44	0.91	207	358.98	369.49	15.06	0.89	16.41	0.93
209	359.55	570.56	15.14	0.87	16.04	0.95	210	902.06	536.83	15.14	0.94	16.57	0.88
212	232.08	404.60	15.19	0.92	16.77	0.86	213	344.80	610.90	15.21	0.93	16.36	0.91

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
215	87.27	703.54	15.22	0.90	16.83	0.90	216	580.59	944.23	15.23	0.88	17.12	0.86
217	146.40	823.34	15.25	0.84	16.94	0.84	218	231.25	699.80	15.26	0.89	16.71	0.96
219	590.18	975.77	15.26	0.90	16.87	0.87	220	518.09	473.83	15.29	0.94	16.64	0.94
221	279.36	643.81	15.30	0.87	16.65	0.92	222	217.07	497.57	15.32	0.86	16.32	0.91
223	729.81	599.43	15.32	0.86	17.67	0.85	224	564.60	465.58	15.32	0.90	16.71	0.88
227	803.10	645.33	15.36	0.91	17.50	0.87	228	595.32	628.04	15.38	0.87	16.86	0.84
229	625.04	771.09	15.38	0.94	17.17	0.88	231	341.03	598.19	15.40	0.93	17.26	0.88
232	250.06	755.61	15.41	0.85	17.04	0.90	234	460.07	688.21	15.41	0.91	16.84	0.84
235	530.94	127.66	15.42	0.86	17.19	0.93	236	876.18	173.81	15.44	0.92	17.29	0.84
237	262.29	671.08	15.45	0.83	17.27	0.82	240	558.39	601.96	15.46	0.89	17.22	0.81
243	601.00	739.18	15.53	0.85	17.15	0.87	247	524.35	466.89	15.53	0.81	16.95	0.83
248	141.08	607.42	15.54	0.83	16.46	0.89	249	655.00	685.66	15.54	0.83	17.24	0.83
251	486.96	763.56	15.57	0.90	16.80	0.93	252	67.12	430.56	15.59	0.83	17.16	0.81
253	693.63	276.02	15.59	0.84	17.29	0.90	254	110.26	963.02	15.59	0.85	17.13	0.85
255	64.27	801.09	15.60	0.82	17.66	0.83	256	419.32	564.51	15.61	0.82	17.12	0.85
260	434.75	741.08	15.67	0.84	16.66	0.90	262	206.62	571.89	15.67	0.83	16.71	0.88
263	421.26	66.49	15.69	0.87	16.60	0.83	267	675.53	469.16	15.76	0.83	17.24	0.82
272	349.80	203.37	15.82	0.82	17.75	0.88	283	666.83	152.54	16.12	0.81	17.70	0.81
284	606.74	754.32	16.14	0.82	16.66	0.91							
F1							F1						
1	127.09	581.55	9.27	0.97	9.92	0.95	2	78.50	306.48	9.71	0.94	10.32	0.87
3	477.34	514.44	9.81	0.96	10.46	0.88	4	75.96	288.15	9.94	1.00	10.62	0.95
5	76.41	501.33	9.94	0.96	10.49	0.83	6	178.19	582.66	10.54	0.98	11.12	0.96
7	280.28	197.16	10.59	0.99	11.25	0.88	8	244.21	280.51	10.81	0.96	11.42	0.85
9	367.80	524.52	10.82	0.96	11.72	0.92	10	65.28	362.21	10.88	0.98	11.58	0.91
11	190.52	846.46	10.89	0.94	11.57	0.90	12	551.82	559.18	11.11	0.99	12.96	0.91
13	94.60	277.19	11.12	0.97	11.74	0.97	14	130.78	719.18	11.24	0.99	11.85	0.90
15	219.45	321.87	11.40	0.97	12.02	0.93	16	114.11	556.03	11.47	1.00	12.03	0.97
17	89.16	264.08	11.68	1.00	12.32	0.91	18	196.16	287.50	11.71	0.96	12.31	0.85

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
19	224.05	296.55	11.77	0.97	13.67	0.87	20	90.42	862.66	11.93	0.96	12.94	0.95
21	102.98	315.17	11.96	1.00	13.38	0.96	22	62.21	212.65	11.98	0.95	12.63	0.84
23	503.50	614.70	12.06	0.95	12.76	0.94	24	344.60	582.63	12.27	0.96	12.85	0.89
25	532.93	261.70	12.33	0.94	14.30	0.87	26	56.31	550.25	12.35	0.98	14.65	0.84
27	100.41	811.59	12.43	0.95	13.21	0.95	28	132.87	431.37	12.63	0.98	13.23	0.91
29	141.43	607.00	12.64	0.97	13.27	0.87	30	139.83	424.70	12.65	0.98	13.60	0.98
31	440.52	957.54	12.73	0.94	13.58	0.98	32	574.65	728.64	12.73	0.96	13.56	0.93
33	116.15	570.94	12.92	0.99	14.06	0.94	34	533.51	257.59	13.07	0.90	14.25	0.82
35	298.20	576.30	13.08	0.98	14.02	0.90	36	266.75	168.58	13.14	0.97	14.48	0.91
37	153.04	147.44	13.19	0.97	13.98	0.87	38	283.02	719.72	13.25	0.99	13.89	1.00
39	706.85	453.53	13.27	0.97	14.95	0.85	40	511.72	110.98	13.28	0.99	14.64	0.97
41	205.38	867.68	13.29	0.97	14.36	1.00	42	316.67	836.62	13.32	0.96	14.20	0.92
43	54.28	358.50	13.46	0.96	14.09	0.84	44	53.47	198.19	13.46	0.96	14.24	0.96
46	911.26	311.24	13.55	0.98	14.74	0.95	47	587.99	94.84	13.58	1.00	14.75	0.96
48	144.06	848.92	13.61	1.00	15.02	0.96	49	435.18	413.69	13.65	0.98	15.08	0.96
50	615.48	679.18	13.67	0.96	14.76	0.94	51	295.14	885.86	13.69	0.99	14.85	0.97
52	198.34	51.07	13.82	0.99	14.60	0.93	53	102.59	869.49	13.84	0.95	14.66	0.88
54	798.78	314.84	13.93	0.99	15.19	0.89	55	273.76	827.97	13.94	0.99	15.44	0.86
56	238.83	539.09	13.96	1.00	15.41	0.97	57	709.31	869.47	13.96	0.95	14.96	0.92
58	217.17	152.51	13.98	0.96	15.44	0.82	59	501.08	179.08	14.02	1.00	15.38	0.96
60	610.05	922.00	14.05	1.00	15.04	0.90	61	127.67	973.83	14.07	0.98	15.66	0.83
62	191.69	348.60	14.10	0.96	15.16	0.95	63	47.32	90.75	14.10	0.95	14.85	0.89
64	630.56	644.62	14.13	0.94	15.71	0.91	65	230.19	223.15	14.13	0.99	15.59	0.89
66	444.19	837.70	14.17	0.98	15.22	0.97	67	255.17	418.13	14.18	0.99	14.79	0.94
68	216.07	139.54	14.20	0.97	15.59	0.83	69	310.35	115.35	14.24	0.97	15.88	0.88
70	630.11	610.31	14.25	0.98	15.14	0.89	71	914.40	909.04	14.25	0.98	16.12	0.95
72	209.85	583.68	14.27	0.98	15.56	0.97	73	334.90	407.66	14.28	0.98	15.85	0.96
74	271.04	481.26	14.30	0.99	15.66	0.90	75	311.56	901.56	14.31	0.94	16.01	0.95
76	577.57	355.12	14.35	0.97	15.25	0.89	77	460.44	762.38	14.38	0.95	15.21	0.89

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
78	63.59	210.11	14.42	0.86	14.99	0.90	79	224.87	204.38	14.43	0.98	16.04	0.93
80	534.01	453.02	14.50	1.00	15.84	0.98	82	385.59	803.59	14.55	0.95	16.11	0.86
83	306.10	99.96	14.60	1.00	15.97	0.93	84	139.21	985.66	14.73	0.98	16.44	0.91
85	359.55	391.04	14.74	0.97	16.33	0.92	86	115.80	301.47	14.78	0.95	16.13	0.92
87	588.17	565.91	14.81	0.99	15.67	0.99	88	475.65	743.28	14.85	0.97	16.42	0.83
90	803.18	102.02	14.92	0.99	16.29	0.92	91	505.44	166.41	14.95	0.95	16.63	0.84
92	117.50	454.55	15.02	0.94	16.56	0.87	93	49.84	599.21	15.02	0.99	16.68	0.91
94	274.14	340.52	15.09	0.97	15.97	0.87	95	436.75	238.77	15.09	0.98	16.65	0.90
98	360.53	338.77	15.15	0.96	16.65	0.84	99	365.26	378.99	15.16	0.99	16.57	0.81
100	286.79	87.99	15.17	0.94	16.90	0.94	101	515.26	593.14	15.24	0.98	16.24	0.92
102	561.44	633.12	15.25	0.97	17.18	0.82	105	101.35	403.44	15.38	0.96	17.73	0.83
106	129.88	139.57	15.40	0.97	17.13	0.86	108	206.99	293.07	15.43	0.97	17.14	0.87
109	684.62	103.44	15.43	0.95	17.29	0.86	110	243.93	724.05	15.46	1.00	17.10	0.83
116	65.33	79.52	15.55	0.95	17.26	0.86	119	175.11	448.60	15.58	0.97	17.14	0.84
120	520.60	741.91	15.58	0.97	17.17	0.85	121	744.22	692.79	15.58	0.98	17.39	0.85
123	452.41	120.97	15.62	0.97	17.45	0.82	125	151.09	485.12	15.66	0.99	17.10	0.86
129	180.40	755.53	15.73	0.92	17.31	0.86	145	643.81	242.88	15.89	0.98	17.55	0.86
150	144.82	87.71	15.96	0.98	17.84	0.87	156	435.25	310.82	16.04	0.98	17.68	0.82
162	113.57	444.49	16.13	0.93	17.66	0.81	173	145.82	934.98	16.24	0.99	17.45	0.82
182	498.24	132.31	16.36	0.96	17.52	0.82	195	200.26	455.06	16.46	0.97	17.76	0.88
F2							F2						
1	67.68	422.60	9.21	0.94	9.64	0.99	2	233.40	983.67	9.48	0.94	11.68	0.92
3	477.27	514.61	9.52	0.95	10.04	0.93	4	859.03	662.54	9.66	0.94	10.54	0.95
5	728.12	606.59	10.23	0.95	11.01	0.97	6	909.23	848.57	10.33	0.94	11.29	0.96
7	321.76	937.08	10.42	0.99	10.97	0.86	8	634.57	915.64	10.68	0.93	11.42	0.95
9	104.49	998.74	11.03	0.93	11.54	0.82	10	248.14	149.36	11.13	0.96	11.58	0.83
11	362.24	723.45	11.34	0.94	11.82	0.93	12	316.36	496.84	11.48	0.97	11.90	0.92
13	601.75	518.38	11.51	0.95	13.62	0.88	14	316.79	920.57	11.54	0.94	12.16	0.97
15	83.83	929.79	11.55	0.98	12.09	0.90	16	510.94	760.43	11.68	0.95	12.25	0.95

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
17	405.02	371.11	11.75	1.00	12.19	0.92	18	658.75	989.50	11.79	0.93	12.57	0.90
19	533.24	887.93	11.93	0.99	14.32	0.96	20	660.02	1010.49	12.03	0.95	12.00	0.91
21	476.88	1015.22	12.11	0.93	12.28	0.86	22	779.87	648.23	12.16	0.99	13.07	0.88
23	272.29	784.75	12.20	0.97	14.10	0.92	24	610.62	812.33	12.31	0.95	12.99	0.85
25	606.91	688.19	12.34	0.99	13.76	0.90	26	739.89	998.28	12.48	0.98	13.39	0.83
27	382.60	729.89	12.65	0.96	13.19	0.93	28	372.68	418.71	12.68	0.92	13.14	0.96
29	747.10	444.08	12.70	1.00	13.58	0.96	30	685.11	298.79	12.77	0.99	14.29	0.98
31	315.03	955.72	12.84	0.98	13.48	0.96	32	418.06	689.77	12.91	0.99	13.50	0.99
33	871.68	967.66	12.93	0.95	13.98	0.92	34	227.46	944.58	13.04	0.91	14.30	0.91
35	588.43	1010.99	13.08	0.96	13.03	0.95	36	263.51	578.76	13.11	0.93	13.56	0.97
37	559.89	1012.04	13.23	1.00	13.13	0.92	38	373.75	414.83	13.27	0.90	13.79	1.00
39	225.92	822.67	13.30	0.97	14.51	0.99	40	788.62	832.94	13.37	0.97	14.40	0.91
41	705.30	793.58	13.38	0.94	14.42	0.97	42	497.58	851.21	13.39	0.95	14.27	0.83
43	903.81	774.30	13.44	0.97	15.22	0.84	44	341.11	793.00	13.47	1.00	14.12	0.92
45	408.04	699.18	13.47	0.99	14.08	0.89	46	402.73	183.44	13.48	0.94	14.80	0.90
47	491.23	805.42	13.51	0.95	14.16	0.96	48	696.59	981.96	13.51	0.96	15.33	0.93
49	917.01	871.20	13.52	0.99	14.58	0.88	50	524.41	677.33	13.58	0.94	15.01	0.86
52	386.23	1010.80	13.61	0.97	13.42	0.98	53	885.64	403.62	13.61	0.94	15.26	0.88
54	366.16	936.02	13.64	0.99	14.94	0.89	55	530.18	139.37	13.66	0.96	14.87	0.81
56	645.33	109.90	13.66	0.97	14.55	0.90	57	825.49	55.52	13.73	0.89	14.73	0.86
58	570.85	968.25	13.74	0.98	14.73	0.84	59	765.88	910.76	13.81	0.98	14.75	0.94
60	443.14	808.63	13.85	0.96	14.61	0.99	61	359.32	224.76	13.90	0.96	15.18	0.94
62	579.92	348.05	13.90	1.00	14.61	0.97	64	456.21	1014.79	14.03	0.94	14.22	0.94
65	706.83	771.58	14.07	0.95	15.00	0.93	66	598.18	537.39	14.17	0.95	16.23	0.88
67	604.28	442.87	14.19	0.98	15.77	0.94	68	409.21	664.19	14.26	0.98	15.78	0.87
69	68.76	234.57	14.34	0.94	14.84	0.96	72	123.33	49.70	14.44	0.95	16.55	0.98
73	168.12	994.33	14.44	0.97	15.99	0.98	74	292.47	857.26	14.44	0.94	15.81	0.87
75	684.13	830.25	14.46	0.98	15.28	0.88	76	247.00	169.57	14.51	0.95	15.99	0.88
77	602.80	586.68	14.51	0.97	16.03	0.95	78	335.56	566.45	14.51	0.91	15.92	0.93

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
79	339.62	799.92	14.54	0.96	16.09	0.85	80	304.96	820.40	14.54	0.96	15.88	0.98
81	88.67	923.15	14.55	0.96	15.88	0.92	82	146.96	555.34	14.55	0.97	15.84	0.91
83	142.31	728.85	14.56	0.97	15.90	0.90	84	233.97	261.29	14.57	0.97	16.10	0.84
85	70.68	908.75	14.58	0.96	15.23	0.94	86	302.77	191.61	14.58	0.95	16.13	0.95
87	492.45	960.57	14.58	0.91	16.20	0.96	88	807.15	413.36	14.61	0.96	16.45	0.85
89	808.61	49.02	14.65	0.97	16.57	0.95	90	605.15	650.46	14.72	0.94	16.48	0.97
91	119.22	166.49	14.75	0.95	16.18	0.85	92	450.34	768.73	14.75	0.96	16.17	0.95
93	517.40	338.61	14.77	0.93	16.38	0.88	94	321.58	390.69	14.77	0.94	16.16	0.97
96	252.71	752.52	14.80	0.92	16.23	0.95	98	619.30	958.73	14.85	0.96	16.73	0.96
99	59.44	811.19	14.87	0.95	16.15	0.87	101	511.41	689.38	14.96	0.93	15.73	0.83
102	449.13	992.46	14.97	0.94	16.45	0.98	103	530.36	855.89	14.98	0.97	16.66	0.93
104	137.35	775.16	14.98	0.97	17.19	0.82	105	637.61	816.14	15.05	0.96	16.60	0.80
106	820.01	807.17	15.05	0.99	17.03	0.82	107	620.97	750.50	15.06	0.94	16.69	0.97
108	761.25	500.51	15.08	0.93	16.62	0.89	110	619.45	310.46	15.10	0.90	17.64	0.85
111	509.32	111.15	15.11	0.97	16.89	0.85	112	848.65	959.72	15.12	0.95	17.14	0.87
114	552.87	311.04	15.18	0.99	16.20	0.96	115	784.17	899.50	15.22	0.93	17.22	0.90
116	665.57	850.91	15.23	0.96	16.86	0.87	117	786.64	515.85	15.24	0.95	17.13	0.87
118	125.09	791.50	15.25	0.94	16.59	0.96	119	371.62	849.97	15.28	0.97	16.87	0.87
120	762.89	838.09	15.32	0.99	17.01	0.87	121	208.65	747.58	15.34	0.93	16.81	0.96
122	370.13	1009.19	15.35	0.86	15.99	0.88	123	510.75	833.82	15.35	0.98	16.33	0.92
125	756.54	776.37	15.42	0.92	17.10	0.82	127	199.05	906.32	15.42	0.97	16.96	0.97
128	98.32	564.55	15.44	0.93	16.72	0.90	129	609.22	166.71	15.45	0.97	17.17	0.89
130	625.61	929.95	15.45	0.96	17.13	0.84	131	466.08	746.24	15.50	0.98	17.03	0.90
132	590.65	817.64	15.52	0.94	17.12	0.96	133	795.77	797.56	15.52	0.95	17.42	0.89
134	281.38	635.46	15.53	0.92	16.98	0.83	135	715.78	370.80	15.55	0.98	17.54	0.87
136	599.28	748.27	15.55	0.96	17.33	0.85	137	375.91	911.72	15.55	0.98	17.19	0.93
139	909.84	946.90	15.58	0.99	17.82	0.81	140	192.44	463.59	15.59	0.92	16.97	0.88
141	449.92	802.58	15.60	0.96	17.09	0.94	142	167.88	283.72	15.61	0.97	16.88	0.92
143	177.47	128.77	15.62	0.93	17.05	0.94	144	423.64	801.50	15.66	0.91	16.95	0.88

IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ	IDk	Xpix	Ypix	Kmag	CorrK	Jmag	CorrJ
145	496.97	315.56	15.67	0.95	16.92	0.92	147	55.95	985.40	15.67	0.96	16.95	0.95
148	863.42	907.83	15.69	0.96	17.54	0.89	149	290.17	655.49	15.69	0.94	16.97	0.87
150	932.69	323.67	15.70	0.89	17.53	0.88	151	888.26	510.22	15.71	0.97	16.89	0.89
152	411.77	534.08	15.72	0.99	17.23	0.81	153	289.30	925.80	15.73	0.96	17.10	0.83
156	905.46	803.83	15.75	0.95	17.34	0.87	157	298.23	629.53	15.76	0.94	17.27	0.83
160	440.11	825.69	15.79	0.97	17.56	0.83	162	452.03	434.11	15.81	1.00	17.04	0.87
163	507.49	584.06	15.81	0.95	17.15	0.89	164	136.40	359.14	15.82	0.96	16.88	0.84
165	880.81	588.62	15.82	0.95	17.62	0.83	166	136.18	596.04	15.82	0.99	16.93	0.83
169	726.59	254.13	15.91	0.96	17.82	0.82	170	99.40	974.80	15.93	0.95	17.64	0.81
171	615.69	656.86	15.93	0.97	17.50	0.82	172	914.10	358.89	15.93	0.99	17.87	0.89
175	172.16	726.38	15.94	0.96	17.61	0.86	176	426.54	625.12	15.96	0.95	17.79	0.88
177	97.95	611.69	15.97	0.97	17.50	0.97	180	371.13	609.29	15.98	0.98	17.56	0.86
181	225.50	486.86	15.99	0.94	17.48	0.87	182	237.65	624.58	16.00	0.93	17.49	0.92
184	226.43	841.45	16.00	0.90	17.53	0.82	185	316.21	709.87	16.01	0.98	17.43	0.82
188	834.77	510.20	16.04	0.98	17.83	0.83	189	864.44	477.88	16.04	0.95	17.73	0.84
194	341.96	895.09	16.08	0.99	17.53	0.85	198	625.95	771.25	16.11	0.98	17.61	0.86
199	555.10	478.89	16.13	0.99	17.82	0.95	203	773.49	980.88	16.16	0.95	17.37	0.88
204	783.22	647.38	16.16	0.87	15.25	0.88	205	460.20	298.69	16.17	0.97	17.54	0.83
209	275.55	491.39	16.21	0.93	17.63	0.85	210	110.45	773.76	16.21	0.94	17.36	0.91
217	204.03	880.35	16.30	0.97	17.72	0.88	221	324.41	868.35	16.32	0.93	17.59	0.91
223	568.09	882.03	16.33	0.99	18.05	0.85	225	534.15	58.21	16.35	0.98	17.92	0.81
228	895.01	768.80	16.45	0.98	18.08	0.81	246	74.56	877.57	16.59	0.91	17.77	0.85
252	295.26	1007.87	16.64	0.86	17.38	0.91	255	814.44	612.61	16.67	0.91	17.90	0.87
258	480.31	467.28	16.69	0.94	18.51	0.80	260	286.13	1008.73	16.69	0.87	17.11	0.81
261	177.84	657.19	16.69	0.97	17.79	0.82	263	535.22	400.48	16.70	0.93	18.52	0.85
275	495.42	842.39	16.76	0.93	17.95	0.83	278	188.87	414.46	16.80	0.93	17.89	0.83
281	289.96	594.45	16.82	0.94	18.21	0.91	311	922.25	592.01	17.05	0.98	18.52	0.86
314	382.80	232.04	17.07	0.97	18.02	0.82	367	771.28	430.94	17.33	0.97	18.08	0.82
464	708.48	793.77	17.86	0.81	17.04	0.81							

Appendix B

SPHERE/IRDIS catalog of R136

The SPHERE/IRDIS catalog of the common sources between J and Ks-band data on R136. The ID, Xpix and Ypix are the identification and pixel position in the IRDIS K and J image. σ_K and σ_J are the total error (combination of PSF-fitting error, residual errors and the calibration error) in Ks and J images. C_K and C_J are the Correlation coefficients between the input PSF and the star, in Ks and J data.

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	Ks	σ_K	C_K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C_J
1	478.27	522.47	11.07	0.04	0.96	1	478.12	522.39	11.33	0.13	0.96
2	470.11	526.34	11.32	0.04	0.98	2	469.99	526.19	11.55	0.13	0.97
3	504.48	494.60	11.44	0.04	0.95	4	504.33	494.55	11.77	0.13	0.92
4	257.55	359.91	11.48	0.04	0.97	5	257.38	359.75	11.78	0.13	0.95
5	327.12	448.15	11.66	0.04	0.99	3	326.94	447.93	11.67	0.13	0.99
6	460.61	538.22	12.73	0.04	0.97	6	460.49	538.09	12.75	0.13	0.93
7	357.09	526.53	12.96	0.04	0.97	7	356.92	526.29	12.86	0.13	0.98
8	522.20	484.15	13.05	0.04	0.80	13	522.10	484.22	13.24	0.13	0.89
9	469.64	550.93	13.05	0.04	0.98	8	469.54	550.77	12.95	0.13	0.92
10	499.29	548.86	13.09	0.04	0.96	9	499.08	548.77	13.00	0.13	0.97
11	524.38	489.51	13.19	0.04	0.96	14	524.35	489.40	13.28	0.13	0.94
12	492.10	549.68	13.27	0.04	0.98	12	492.09	549.48	13.18	0.13	0.94
13	344.14	553.06	13.29	0.04	1.00	10	343.95	552.87	13.11	0.13	0.99
14	365.28	605.85	13.32	0.04	0.99	11	365.12	605.63	13.17	0.13	0.97

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
15	232.16	337.62	13.36	0.04	0.98	19	232.18	337.55	13.52	0.13	0.96
16	481.85	527.70	13.45	0.04	0.95	17	481.86	527.04	13.37	0.13	0.96
17	136.62	457.45	13.58	0.04	0.96	16	136.41	457.27	13.37	0.13	0.93
18	381.01	526.74	13.58	0.04	0.99	18	380.84	526.57	13.41	0.13	0.95
19	443.59	397.91	13.62	0.04	0.95	25	443.43	398.41	13.69	0.13	0.91
20	285.96	487.96	13.63	0.04	1.00	15	285.77	487.74	13.37	0.13	0.96
21	501.75	566.90	13.65	0.04	0.98	21	501.61	566.75	13.62	0.13	0.90
22	441.45	662.07	13.72	0.04	0.97	20	441.33	661.85	13.61	0.13	0.97
23	467.62	678.18	13.78	0.04	0.98	26	467.52	678.03	13.70	0.13	0.93
24	128.74	685.51	13.84	0.04	0.96	27	128.51	685.25	13.73	0.13	0.93
25	260.29	364.94	13.84	0.04	0.93	43	260.19	364.76	14.33	0.13	0.89
26	362.33	680.19	13.84	0.04	0.98	24	362.20	679.97	13.69	0.13	0.98
27	301.54	485.36	13.85	0.04	0.95	23	301.41	485.02	13.67	0.13	0.94
28	437.16	546.19	13.91	0.04	0.99	28	437.02	546.07	13.78	0.13	0.99
29	305.72	822.53	13.93	0.04	0.96	34	305.57	822.32	14.07	0.13	0.94
30	427.49	492.32	13.96	0.04	0.94	29	427.21	492.18	13.82	0.13	0.97
31	121.78	613.06	13.96	0.04	0.99	22	121.46	612.83	13.63	0.13	0.92
32	485.09	656.74	13.98	0.04	0.99	30	484.99	656.61	13.94	0.13	0.96
33	590.99	715.91	13.99	0.04	1.00	37	590.92	715.88	14.23	0.13	0.99
34	527.54	573.65	14.00	0.04	0.94	32	527.51	573.59	14.04	0.13	0.91
35	607.92	590.16	14.11	0.04	1.00	41	607.82	590.16	14.30	0.13	0.98
36	431.57	384.70	14.15	0.04	0.96	36	431.65	384.37	14.15	0.13	0.92
37	446.69	562.36	14.20	0.04	0.98	33	446.60	562.17	14.06	0.13	0.96
38	465.29	434.10	14.20	0.04	0.99	35	465.15	433.97	14.10	0.13	0.99
39	486.83	471.58	14.35	0.04	0.97	39	486.68	471.41	14.28	0.13	0.94
40	410.56	479.51	14.38	0.04	0.95	38	410.48	479.10	14.24	0.13	0.92
41	413.38	465.49	14.39	0.04	0.92	40	413.57	465.22	14.29	0.13	0.93
42	464.21	487.26	14.42	0.04	0.98	42	464.10	487.06	14.31	0.13	0.99
43	490.10	518.61	14.49	0.05	0.93	53	490.12	518.42	14.77	0.13	0.84

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	Ks	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
44	306.51	666.04	14.61	0.04	0.96	46	306.36	665.77	14.49	0.13	0.96
45	856.87	706.75	14.64	0.04	0.97	80	856.75	707.04	15.30	0.13	0.92
46	337.30	547.95	14.64	0.04	0.97	44	337.21	547.74	14.42	0.13	0.97
47	655.59	154.74	14.68	0.04	0.95	65	655.54	154.82	14.94	0.13	0.90
48	554.95	515.72	14.68	0.04	0.98	52	554.92	515.70	14.76	0.13	0.96
49	432.80	500.49	14.69	0.04	0.96	49	432.56	500.34	14.62	0.13	0.94
50	486.37	361.88	14.70	0.04	0.98	55	486.55	361.55	14.80	0.13	0.82
51	197.08	669.14	14.70	0.04	0.99	45	196.79	668.93	14.43	0.13	0.98
52	445.30	425.77	14.72	0.04	0.98	47	445.14	425.64	14.56	0.13	0.97
53	503.64	458.20	14.77	0.04	0.97	51	503.56	458.10	14.71	0.13	0.93
54	471.55	560.36	14.78	0.05	0.89	57	471.49	560.13	14.81	0.13	0.91
55	560.25	617.46	14.78	0.04	0.96	58	560.16	617.38	14.84	0.13	0.95
56	415.11	579.56	14.78	0.04	0.97	48	414.98	579.39	14.61	0.13	0.97
57	235.42	365.40	14.79	0.04	0.93	54	235.14	365.40	14.80	0.13	0.96
58	509.98	507.10	14.80	0.05	0.98	56	510.01	506.92	14.80	0.13	0.98
59	508.72	492.74	14.83	0.05	0.74	31	508.99	492.77	14.03	0.13	0.86
60	538.38	534.34	14.83	0.05	0.96	60	538.23	534.25	14.88	0.13	0.96
61	179.29	311.06	14.84	0.04	0.99	79	179.07	310.87	15.29	0.13	1.00
62	417.74	438.74	14.85	0.04	0.98	50	417.64	438.58	14.69	0.13	0.92
63	528.10	590.14	14.87	0.04	1.00	66	528.10	590.14	14.96	0.13	0.99
64	433.98	332.11	14.97	0.04	0.99	61	433.93	331.92	14.92	0.13	0.81
65	258.36	784.50	14.98	0.04	0.95	62	258.16	784.32	14.93	0.13	0.97
66	423.70	338.90	15.02	0.04	0.98	67	423.58	338.76	14.96	0.13	0.92
67	606.07	765.38	15.03	0.04	0.98	85	606.28	765.45	15.34	0.13	0.96
68	172.06	992.01	15.10	0.04	1.00	91	171.85	991.78	15.39	0.13	0.98
69	394.44	520.54	15.11	0.04	0.94	64	394.28	520.35	14.93	0.13	0.94
70	235.43	501.65	15.16	0.04	0.96	63	235.24	501.44	14.93	0.13	0.95
72	471.35	566.47	15.18	0.05	0.96	70	471.23	566.16	15.17	0.13	0.95
73	221.48	529.48	15.22	0.04	0.94	68	221.34	529.19	15.03	0.13	0.96

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
74	500.50	467.42	15.22	0.05	0.94	84	500.42	467.34	15.33	0.13	0.92
75	474.06	701.19	15.23	0.04	0.99	110	473.57	700.71	15.70	0.13	0.91
76	389.77	808.55	15.25	0.04	0.97	77	389.66	808.42	15.24	0.13	0.94
77	469.86	398.37	15.26	0.04	0.98	82	470.02	397.96	15.33	0.13	0.82
78	524.57	731.12	15.27	0.04	0.97	92	524.45	731.04	15.42	0.13	0.93
79	456.59	606.74	15.32	0.04	0.96	71	456.56	606.51	15.17	0.13	0.91
80	201.84	353.80	15.32	0.04	0.99	73	201.61	353.60	15.22	0.13	0.93
81	401.43	817.45	15.33	0.04	0.94	87	401.26	817.34	15.35	0.13	0.96
82	343.51	540.69	15.33	0.04	0.94	69	343.46	540.34	15.08	0.13	0.92
83	516.76	634.79	15.36	0.04	0.98	88	516.65	634.68	15.38	0.13	0.93
84	479.18	461.08	15.40	0.05	0.99	83	479.03	460.93	15.33	0.13	0.99
85	295.64	459.76	15.42	0.04	0.97	72	295.40	459.55	15.21	0.13	0.92
86	360.45	714.89	15.43	0.04	0.97	76	360.28	714.71	15.24	0.13	0.97
87	538.04	392.07	15.45	0.04	0.99	123	538.45	391.54	15.86	0.13	0.99
88	254.09	625.09	15.45	0.04	0.99	74	253.79	625.01	15.23	0.13	0.98
89	536.53	619.32	15.46	0.04	0.90	98	536.02	619.64	15.53	0.13	0.93
90	363.69	476.67	15.46	0.04	0.96	117	363.30	476.38	15.77	0.13	0.90
91	512.57	363.64	15.47	0.04	0.95	95	512.54	363.57	15.50	0.13	0.91
92	314.47	428.66	15.47	0.04	0.94	81	314.29	428.46	15.31	0.13	0.93
93	781.66	723.79	15.50	0.04	0.97	144	781.50	723.94	16.08	0.13	0.92
94	332.52	436.17	15.51	0.05	0.86	78	332.72	436.36	15.26	0.13	0.86
95	466.80	759.77	15.51	0.04	0.99	101	466.72	759.66	15.56	0.13	0.94
96	492.57	417.61	15.51	0.04	0.95	96	492.48	417.45	15.51	0.13	0.92
97	448.00	630.64	15.52	0.04	0.98	89	447.90	630.45	15.38	0.13	0.96
98	72.08	654.01	15.53	0.04	1.00	75	71.84	653.78	15.23	0.13	0.98
99	357.02	590.61	15.54	0.04	0.98	135	356.92	590.64	15.95	0.13	0.96
100	146.71	665.66	15.56	0.04	0.97	97	146.50	665.44	15.52	0.13	0.91
101	589.05	634.82	15.58	0.04	0.99	116	588.75	634.78	15.76	0.13	0.98
102	568.78	611.11	15.59	0.04	0.96	111	568.62	611.42	15.71	0.13	0.96

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ _K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ _J	C _J
103	627.86	396.28	15.61	0.04	0.98	127	627.81	396.20	15.88	0.13	0.97
104	267.81	283.91	15.63	0.04	0.99	105	267.58	283.83	15.60	0.13	0.94
105	509.24	642.48	15.63	0.04	0.96	109	509.12	642.35	15.70	0.13	0.96
106	278.50	593.64	15.64	0.04	0.94	86	278.34	593.48	15.35	0.13	0.93
107	568.21	427.94	15.64	0.04	0.99	112	568.15	427.86	15.72	0.13	0.98
108	592.00	444.19	15.66	0.04	0.99	138	592.36	443.85	15.98	0.13	0.84
109	261.27	437.07	15.67	0.04	0.97	106	260.70	436.91	15.61	0.13	0.96
110	305.46	416.61	15.67	0.04	0.95	100	305.24	416.38	15.55	0.13	0.95
111	398.50	717.74	15.68	0.04	0.96	99	398.38	717.54	15.55	0.13	0.94
113	419.37	562.36	15.69	0.05	0.96	103	419.24	562.14	15.58	0.13	0.97
114	573.63	368.73	15.71	0.04	0.96	129	573.68	368.53	15.90	0.13	0.91
115	466.42	734.45	15.74	0.04	0.94	186	466.50	734.32	16.44	0.13	0.92
116	615.98	485.25	15.75	0.04	0.99	276	616.08	485.11	17.21	0.13	0.98
117	681.89	358.62	15.75	0.04	0.97	149	681.91	358.60	16.11	0.13	0.94
118	391.04	615.27	15.76	0.04	0.99	197	390.84	615.08	16.52	0.13	0.99
119	478.76	243.71	15.78	0.04	0.98	122	478.66	243.60	15.85	0.13	0.93
120	205.42	322.31	15.79	0.04	0.95	115	205.19	322.13	15.75	0.13	0.98
121	546.54	605.56	15.80	0.05	0.96	118	546.49	605.49	15.79	0.13	0.92
122	372.59	591.93	15.81	0.04	0.97	102	372.51	591.73	15.58	0.13	0.91
123	665.97	465.04	15.83	0.04	0.99	169	665.36	465.29	16.28	0.13	0.98
125	363.96	370.77	15.85	0.04	0.99	120	363.61	370.91	15.83	0.13	0.95
126	204.04	814.91	15.87	0.04	1.00	128	203.84	814.65	15.90	0.13	0.97
127	929.79	981.62	15.87	0.04	0.80	168	930.01	982.04	16.27	0.13	0.81
128	320.33	832.56	15.87	0.04	0.96	130	320.16	832.41	15.90	0.13	0.95
129	615.40	459.44	15.88	0.04	0.94	146	615.37	459.47	16.10	0.13	0.93
130	480.79	563.37	15.88	0.07	0.97	119	480.58	563.25	15.81	0.13	0.94
131	495.07	439.93	15.90	0.05	0.98	121	494.88	439.78	15.83	0.13	0.97
133	143.30	626.37	15.92	0.04	0.90	107	143.39	625.73	15.65	0.13	0.95
134	371.28	618.88	15.93	0.04	0.97	113	371.21	618.44	15.74	0.13	0.94

ID _K	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	J	σ_J	C _J
135	549.49	485.85	15.95	0.06	0.94	142	549.58	485.75	16.06	0.13	0.90
136	218.01	120.95	15.96	0.04	0.99	137	217.80	120.79	15.97	0.13	0.97
137	216.34	720.07	15.98	0.04	0.98	139	216.12	719.76	15.99	0.13	0.98
138	364.98	178.15	15.98	0.04	0.99	136	364.83	178.02	15.97	0.13	0.98
139	856.62	949.03	15.98	0.04	0.96	218	856.80	949.50	16.73	0.13	0.83
140	336.26	341.70	15.98	0.04	0.97	133	335.88	341.45	15.92	0.13	0.96
141	465.93	602.54	16.01	0.05	0.97	134	465.97	602.30	15.95	0.13	0.97
142	453.53	563.81	16.01	0.06	0.94	114	453.34	562.94	15.74	0.13	0.89
143	544.72	449.90	16.02	0.05	0.98	156	544.64	449.83	16.17	0.13	0.93
144	292.91	680.33	16.02	0.04	0.98	284	292.77	680.02	17.26	0.13	0.98
145	289.62	395.70	16.03	0.05	0.97	124	289.47	395.55	15.86	0.13	0.92
146	760.28	708.31	16.04	0.04	0.98	185	760.03	708.38	16.40	0.13	0.91
147	804.15	513.44	16.04	0.04	0.96	205	804.20	513.61	16.60	0.13	0.92
148	475.80	482.75	16.05	0.07	0.86	166	474.95	483.32	16.23	0.13	0.90
149	404.80	561.55	16.06	0.05	0.96	162	404.53	561.28	16.22	0.13	0.94
150	429.49	591.94	16.07	0.05	0.96	126	429.29	591.79	15.88	0.13	0.96
151	439.03	963.45	16.08	0.04	0.97	182	438.97	963.41	16.37	0.13	0.95
152	303.72	465.53	16.08	0.05	0.96	140	303.45	465.35	16.01	0.13	0.92
153	300.36	382.36	16.12	0.05	0.96	175	300.18	382.15	16.32	0.13	0.99
154	594.84	489.81	16.12	0.05	0.98	179	594.53	489.90	16.36	0.13	0.95
155	536.77	652.43	16.13	0.04	0.97	151	536.65	652.36	16.12	0.13	0.96
156	388.27	588.70	16.14	0.04	0.98	132	388.22	588.52	15.92	0.13	0.95
157	510.67	560.37	16.14	0.08	0.96	160	510.65	559.85	16.21	0.13	0.91
158	572.80	508.75	16.15	0.05	0.97	164	572.71	508.74	16.22	0.13	0.91
159	521.93	552.94	16.17	0.08	0.90	191	521.76	552.85	16.46	0.13	0.84
160	149.84	721.07	16.22	0.04	0.99	150	149.59	720.84	16.12	0.13	0.94
161	618.13	330.25	16.22	0.04	0.99	210	617.84	330.07	16.63	0.13	0.97
162	266.12	375.59	16.22	0.07	0.82	145	266.15	375.01	16.09	0.13	0.94
163	434.86	324.69	16.24	0.04	0.98	172	434.92	324.81	16.30	0.13	0.95

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
164	443.33	703.52	16.24	0.04	0.93	158	442.75	703.44	16.19	0.13	0.95
165	499.37	621.53	16.24	0.05	0.96	173	498.79	621.35	16.31	0.13	0.97
167	469.57	449.31	16.25	0.06	0.95	159	469.44	449.10	16.20	0.13	0.93
168	379.37	621.10	16.26	0.04	0.97	147	379.22	620.86	16.11	0.13	0.97
169	342.17	623.55	16.27	0.04	0.97	143	341.88	623.37	16.07	0.13	0.97
170	548.88	631.74	16.29	0.05	0.97	212	548.70	631.67	16.65	0.13	0.94
172	431.62	725.69	16.33	0.04	0.95	171	431.44	725.60	16.30	0.13	0.92
174	506.26	578.08	16.35	0.07	0.93	167	505.66	577.66	16.27	0.13	0.95
175	477.40	640.78	16.36	0.05	0.97	174	477.33	640.70	16.31	0.13	0.96
176	157.18	618.85	16.37	0.04	0.99	148	156.94	618.55	16.11	0.13	0.96
177	571.06	579.74	16.39	0.05	0.96	321	571.03	579.83	17.44	0.13	0.98
178	458.26	499.27	16.40	0.08	0.93	161	458.27	498.94	16.21	0.13	0.94
179	588.01	455.23	16.40	0.05	0.99	199	587.84	455.20	16.54	0.13	0.98
181	415.33	456.98	16.42	0.05	0.96	152	415.22	456.61	16.12	0.13	0.95
182	411.12	548.13	16.43	0.05	0.96	165	410.97	548.06	16.22	0.13	0.99
183	618.52	625.61	16.44	0.05	0.91	206	618.47	625.72	16.60	0.13	0.90
184	355.86	181.53	16.44	0.04	0.96	195	355.71	181.41	16.49	0.13	0.96
185	916.91	572.59	16.45	0.04	0.95	274	917.10	572.75	17.21	0.13	0.92
186	356.44	347.45	16.45	0.04	0.94	183	356.31	347.30	16.38	0.13	0.94
187	307.36	697.37	16.45	0.04	0.95	170	307.28	697.13	16.29	0.13	0.97
188	404.09	551.46	16.46	0.05	0.96	247	404.08	551.17	16.97	0.13	0.97
189	407.99	519.10	16.47	0.06	0.96	176	407.85	518.99	16.32	0.13	0.99
190	75.64	919.84	16.48	0.04	0.97	189	75.52	919.69	16.46	0.13	0.91
191	121.35	162.75	16.49	0.04	0.96	198	121.29	162.56	16.53	0.13	0.93
192	571.83	501.10	16.50	0.06	0.97	222	571.95	500.91	16.78	0.13	0.97
193	457.57	395.80	16.50	0.05	0.95	192	457.55	395.90	16.46	0.13	0.94
194	647.01	669.60	16.50	0.04	0.97	263	647.60	669.67	17.08	0.13	0.95
195	527.54	622.11	16.51	0.05	0.95	239	527.70	621.86	16.92	0.13	0.91
196	590.84	504.63	16.51	0.05	0.96	204	590.79	504.54	16.60	0.13	0.92

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
197	419.69	774.82	16.51	0.04	0.96	237	419.26	774.64	16.91	0.13	0.94
198	331.10	596.31	16.52	0.04	0.98	178	330.90	596.11	16.33	0.13	0.99
199	417.62	789.19	16.52	0.04	0.97	209	417.54	789.08	16.62	0.13	0.92
200	220.27	591.22	16.54	0.04	0.98	320	220.06	590.97	17.43	0.13	0.99
201	397.38	463.06	16.54	0.05	0.96	281	397.17	462.79	17.25	0.13	0.99
202	634.45	48.44	16.57	0.04	0.93	236	634.25	48.63	16.90	0.13	0.91
203	134.70	897.26	16.57	0.04	0.98	214	134.47	897.07	16.66	0.13	0.93
204	402.25	752.33	16.58	0.04	0.94	215	401.67	752.14	16.69	0.13	0.97
205	251.72	328.58	16.58	0.07	0.95	207	251.61	328.41	16.62	0.13	0.90
206	591.69	566.79	16.59	0.05	0.97	231	591.61	566.78	16.86	0.13	0.93
207	507.51	391.99	16.59	0.05	0.96	331	507.29	391.87	17.47	0.13	0.97
208	665.15	434.66	16.59	0.04	0.97	243	665.48	434.46	16.95	0.13	0.96
209	291.84	933.62	16.60	0.04	0.97	220	291.70	933.55	16.75	0.13	0.93
210	371.62	535.54	16.60	0.05	0.93	202	371.22	535.43	16.56	0.13	0.91
211	641.43	689.12	16.61	0.04	0.95	280	642.15	688.94	17.23	0.13	0.81
212	462.98	662.33	16.62	0.05	0.97	253	462.59	662.46	17.00	0.13	0.96
213	628.49	481.63	16.62	0.05	0.94	416	628.43	481.66	17.87	0.13	0.94
214	309.44	284.36	16.62	0.04	0.95	203	309.23	284.19	16.58	0.13	0.97
215	526.45	560.94	16.63	0.09	0.90	249	526.55	560.60	16.99	0.13	0.92
216	178.77	469.84	16.63	0.05	0.96	194	178.42	469.50	16.48	0.13	0.87
217	381.40	510.31	16.63	0.05	0.95	200	381.33	510.12	16.55	0.13	0.95
218	535.28	599.70	16.64	0.06	0.97	342	535.26	599.41	17.53	0.13	0.93
219	422.72	485.12	16.65	0.07	0.97	188	422.49	485.48	16.45	0.13	0.93
220	199.27	681.14	16.65	0.04	0.98	190	199.05	681.03	16.46	0.13	0.99
221	441.30	508.05	16.66	0.09	0.93	196	441.26	507.84	16.50	0.13	0.90
222	488.33	440.04	16.68	0.07	0.96	213	488.30	440.01	16.66	0.13	0.96
223	393.12	573.81	16.68	0.05	0.86	234	393.44	572.53	16.90	0.13	0.89
224	532.15	642.56	16.68	0.05	0.95	224	532.13	642.68	16.79	0.13	0.96
227	151.75	645.00	16.69	0.04	0.98	193	151.48	644.70	16.47	0.13	0.93

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
228	525.82	864.40	16.69	0.05	0.97	242	525.79	864.44	16.95	0.13	0.95
229	619.98	427.23	16.72	0.05	0.98	238	619.82	427.28	16.91	0.13	0.96
230	459.97	440.67	16.75	0.07	0.96	181	460.57	439.33	16.36	0.13	0.81
231	656.47	533.14	16.76	0.04	0.96	272	656.33	533.16	17.17	0.13	0.93
232	112.88	687.59	16.76	0.04	0.97	229	112.73	687.25	16.85	0.13	0.96
233	489.47	484.00	16.76	0.13	0.75	269	489.43	483.52	17.16	0.14	0.83
234	537.54	565.81	16.77	0.08	0.96	251	537.46	565.50	16.99	0.13	0.90
235	305.40	310.66	16.77	0.04	0.96	225	304.91	311.00	16.83	0.13	0.98
236	364.49	784.74	16.78	0.04	0.95	355	364.32	784.62	17.59	0.13	0.95
237	520.26	541.87	16.79	0.14	0.97	371	520.28	541.70	17.68	0.15	0.86
238	795.81	845.87	16.80	0.04	0.97	304	795.82	846.03	17.36	0.13	0.93
239	174.79	753.54	16.80	0.05	0.95	459	174.63	753.34	18.01	0.13	0.96
240	218.86	572.78	16.82	0.04	0.98	211	218.56	572.45	16.65	0.13	0.92
241	190.11	480.64	16.82	0.05	0.97	219	189.84	480.39	16.74	0.13	0.98
242	387.98	727.63	16.84	0.04	0.95	318	386.82	728.10	17.43	0.13	0.91
243	510.27	808.09	16.85	0.04	0.97	266	510.24	808.02	17.11	0.13	0.97
244	279.57	674.31	16.85	0.04	0.95	230	279.41	674.15	16.85	0.13	0.94
245	197.27	455.69	16.86	0.05	0.97	332	197.05	455.38	17.47	0.13	0.97
246	542.55	347.95	16.87	0.04	0.94	278	541.89	348.25	17.23	0.13	0.96
247	475.34	583.24	16.87	0.09	0.92	223	474.88	583.15	16.78	0.13	0.96
248	348.60	188.93	16.87	0.04	0.96	240	348.46	188.79	16.92	0.13	0.90
249	356.44	546.87	16.89	0.05	0.92	306	356.87	546.97	17.37	0.13	0.84
250	818.18	761.05	16.89	0.05	0.98	347	817.98	761.15	17.56	0.13	0.93
251	394.33	370.33	16.89	0.05	0.94	228	394.29	369.95	16.84	0.13	0.96
252	575.78	708.35	16.90	0.05	0.96	258	575.73	708.19	17.05	0.13	0.93
253	234.80	720.70	16.90	0.04	0.97	241	234.66	720.49	16.92	0.13	0.94
254	651.87	245.54	16.90	0.05	0.95	275	651.90	245.46	17.21	0.13	0.93
255	342.94	521.65	16.91	0.05	0.91	289	342.58	521.57	17.29	0.13	0.94
256	513.92	312.18	16.92	0.04	0.98	427	513.81	312.14	17.90	0.13	0.97

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
257	586.90	587.84	16.92	0.06	0.98	267	586.81	587.70	17.11	0.13	0.95
259	626.32	541.52	16.94	0.05	0.94	277	626.53	541.35	17.22	0.13	0.92
260	278.63	450.43	16.94	0.06	0.95	419	278.62	450.08	17.88	0.13	0.98
261	555.04	190.96	16.95	0.06	0.98	271	554.90	191.02	17.16	0.13	0.97
262	324.26	376.85	16.96	0.05	0.87	248	324.12	376.72	16.98	0.13	0.98
263	129.76	512.78	16.97	0.05	0.97	462	129.50	512.49	18.02	0.13	0.91
265	462.74	457.28	16.97	0.09	0.81	245	462.31	457.26	16.96	0.13	0.87
266	256.09	504.11	17.00	0.05	0.97	227	255.88	503.82	16.84	0.13	0.98
267	369.04	377.93	17.01	0.05	0.97	257	368.97	377.72	17.03	0.13	0.97
268	591.04	671.65	17.02	0.05	0.96	288	591.10	671.56	17.29	0.13	0.95
269	405.41	734.91	17.02	0.04	0.96	376	405.52	734.88	17.70	0.13	0.91
270	712.77	794.49	17.02	0.04	0.95	339	712.86	794.45	17.51	0.13	0.90
271	48.07	409.04	17.03	0.04	0.97	232	47.71	408.79	16.88	0.13	0.97
272	380.90	710.26	17.03	0.04	0.84	235	380.85	710.21	16.90	0.13	0.93
273	577.39	581.44	17.03	0.07	0.94	268	577.32	581.31	17.13	0.13	0.96
274	183.61	656.65	17.04	0.04	0.86	302	183.40	656.76	17.35	0.13	0.88
275	513.16	686.44	17.04	0.05	0.92	290	512.37	686.29	17.30	0.13	0.92
276	551.91	701.05	17.04	0.05	0.98	325	551.91	700.85	17.45	0.13	0.99
277	366.04	548.40	17.05	0.05	0.92	221	365.97	548.14	16.77	0.13	0.94
278	385.93	648.75	17.05	0.04	0.97	252	385.69	648.59	17.00	0.13	0.93
279	883.37	773.31	17.06	0.05	0.67	298	882.40	773.37	17.34	0.13	0.85
280	308.22	338.28	17.07	0.05	0.96	256	307.96	338.19	17.02	0.13	0.99
281	601.01	477.40	17.07	0.06	0.95	308	601.44	476.93	17.37	0.13	0.88
282	233.38	670.10	17.08	0.04	0.97	250	233.19	669.78	16.99	0.13	0.98
283	625.91	619.29	17.08	0.05	0.93	309	626.05	619.72	17.38	0.13	0.95
284	491.77	214.14	17.09	0.05	0.98	542	491.56	214.20	18.39	0.13	0.92
285	168.86	82.26	17.10	0.04	0.96	300	168.48	81.71	17.35	0.13	0.92
286	250.79	563.27	17.10	0.04	0.97	246	250.53	563.13	16.97	0.13	0.93
287	429.41	470.46	17.12	0.09	0.85	293	429.40	470.25	17.32	0.13	0.84

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
288	581.63	677.17	17.12	0.05	0.95	445	581.88	677.04	17.96	0.13	0.98
289	541.66	851.29	17.12	0.06	0.94	388	541.53	851.15	17.73	0.13	0.91
290	868.75	632.99	17.12	0.05	0.94	364	868.67	633.10	17.65	0.13	0.91
291	630.46	510.08	17.12	0.05	0.93	312	630.24	510.19	17.39	0.13	0.95
292	521.28	989.33	17.13	0.07	0.96	352	521.10	989.34	17.57	0.13	0.94
294	208.29	492.06	17.13	0.05	0.97	254	208.07	492.01	17.00	0.13	1.00
296	96.29	770.67	17.14	0.04	0.96	382	95.93	770.46	17.72	0.13	0.96
298	330.72	663.36	17.15	0.04	0.95	260	330.50	663.14	17.06	0.13	0.94
299	866.45	337.78	17.15	0.04	0.94	383	866.39	337.87	17.72	0.13	0.91
300	310.37	395.38	17.16	0.07	0.94	294	310.05	395.22	17.32	0.13	0.98
301	583.95	376.78	17.16	0.05	0.97	303	583.84	376.62	17.36	0.13	0.94
302	883.51	832.22	17.16	0.04	0.92	437	883.29	832.42	17.94	0.13	0.85
303	230.04	558.10	17.18	0.05	0.97	396	229.90	558.09	17.76	0.13	0.99
304	596.51	557.76	17.18	0.06	0.94	319	596.57	557.71	17.43	0.13	0.92
305	455.71	634.85	17.18	0.06	0.82	264	455.38	634.44	17.09	0.13	0.90
306	273.66	777.94	17.19	0.04	0.95	357	273.74	778.42	17.60	0.13	0.94
307	661.30	374.31	17.20	0.04	0.87	315	661.30	373.86	17.41	0.13	0.82
308	114.67	340.71	17.20	0.04	0.94	273	114.28	340.53	17.17	0.13	0.94
309	583.57	496.01	17.21	0.08	0.91	334	583.27	496.27	17.48	0.13	0.90
310	573.39	620.48	17.21	0.06	0.89	292	573.09	620.29	17.30	0.13	0.93
311	510.94	116.82	17.21	0.06	0.96	337	510.81	116.66	17.50	0.13	0.94
312	542.57	396.36	17.21	0.06	0.93	367	542.55	395.72	17.67	0.13	0.90
313	774.31	526.20	17.21	0.05	0.95	385	774.36	526.10	17.72	0.13	0.93
314	233.01	627.87	17.22	0.04	0.98	262	232.90	627.62	17.08	0.13	0.97
315	175.27	945.11	17.23	0.04	0.96	493	175.01	945.06	18.14	0.13	0.99
316	453.13	469.40	17.24	0.11	0.95	365	452.84	469.26	17.66	0.14	0.94
317	318.46	379.71	17.25	0.06	0.91	436	318.44	379.83	17.94	0.13	0.91
318	789.12	599.38	17.25	0.04	0.96	404	789.28	599.59	17.79	0.13	0.90
319	454.50	611.92	17.26	0.07	0.83	259	453.78	610.53	17.05	0.13	0.80

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
320	413.43	154.48	17.26	0.07	0.93	314	413.35	154.55	17.40	0.13	0.94
322	447.42	371.62	17.27	0.06	0.94	432	447.28	371.49	17.92	0.13	0.93
323	356.03	663.21	17.27	0.04	0.97	393	355.91	663.14	17.76	0.13	0.98
325	483.80	452.96	17.27	0.11	0.96	435	483.63	452.98	17.94	0.13	0.84
326	274.32	650.24	17.27	0.04	0.93	359	274.11	649.52	17.61	0.13	0.86
327	366.20	555.78	17.28	0.06	0.93	345	366.08	555.69	17.55	0.13	0.91
328	402.17	515.99	17.28	0.09	0.92	261	402.22	516.19	17.08	0.13	0.93
329	209.46	355.80	17.28	0.06	0.93	480	209.19	355.57	18.09	0.13	0.89
330	675.12	395.72	17.29	0.04	0.98	575	675.24	395.62	18.50	0.13	0.93
331	296.49	502.12	17.29	0.06	0.94	341	296.48	501.77	17.53	0.13	0.90
332	399.90	301.04	17.30	0.04	0.96	593	399.69	300.94	18.56	0.13	0.96
333	390.59	961.30	17.31	0.07	0.95	406	390.43	960.98	17.80	0.13	0.93
335	734.81	823.43	17.33	0.04	0.94	422	734.76	823.63	17.88	0.13	0.88
336	555.74	648.09	17.33	0.06	0.96	607	555.90	647.92	18.61	0.14	0.90
337	444.88	484.71	17.34	0.13	0.96	425	444.68	484.65	17.90	0.15	0.91
338	392.64	256.14	17.34	0.05	0.94	372	392.43	256.01	17.69	0.13	0.93
339	693.33	771.28	17.35	0.04	0.94	403	693.55	771.30	17.79	0.13	0.89
340	365.07	966.81	17.35	0.08	0.96	423	365.05	966.68	17.88	0.13	0.97
341	567.02	239.79	17.36	0.06	0.97	363	566.67	239.88	17.64	0.13	0.94
342	876.28	638.03	17.36	0.05	0.92	433	876.62	638.12	17.93	0.13	0.85
343	60.06	878.79	17.36	0.04	0.97	323	59.67	878.54	17.44	0.13	0.94
344	518.13	724.72	17.36	0.05	0.95	379	518.02	725.21	17.71	0.13	0.86
345	536.34	692.03	17.36	0.05	0.96	330	536.31	691.94	17.45	0.13	0.97
346	194.97	717.04	17.36	0.04	0.98	305	194.69	716.80	17.36	0.13	0.96
347	256.06	493.70	17.37	0.05	0.95	285	255.68	493.50	17.27	0.13	0.96
348	487.57	759.40	17.38	0.05	0.93	340	487.46	759.28	17.52	0.13	0.92
349	356.45	462.27	17.39	0.09	0.91	296	356.53	462.24	17.34	0.13	0.91
350	849.29	634.40	17.39	0.05	0.82	464	849.25	634.21	18.03	0.13	0.85
351	733.99	280.91	17.39	0.05	0.95	397	733.96	281.03	17.76	0.13	0.96

ID _K	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	J	σ_J	C _J
352	285.46	643.27	17.40	0.04	0.93	424	285.32	643.23	17.90	0.13	0.95
353	461.67	633.46	17.40	0.06	0.94	439	461.54	633.22	17.95	0.13	0.92
354	306.47	796.58	17.40	0.04	0.93	328	306.20	796.46	17.45	0.13	0.95
355	846.48	796.70	17.41	0.05	0.89	426	846.66	796.82	17.90	0.13	0.89
356	432.80	249.79	17.41	0.05	0.96	631	432.53	249.50	18.68	0.13	0.90
357	376.02	709.90	17.42	0.05	0.77	336	376.01	709.66	17.50	0.13	0.95
358	718.80	601.85	17.42	0.05	0.97	602	718.79	601.94	18.58	0.13	0.97
359	549.22	367.90	17.42	0.05	0.94	468	549.29	367.92	18.04	0.13	0.95
362	235.91	567.24	17.42	0.05	0.97	295	235.46	567.01	17.33	0.13	0.94
363	558.36	574.47	17.43	0.10	0.94	511	558.44	574.15	18.20	0.13	0.94
364	517.17	928.28	17.43	0.09	0.97	429	516.98	928.24	17.91	0.13	0.97
365	798.14	494.63	17.43	0.05	0.90	430	798.79	494.58	17.92	0.13	0.91
366	409.23	615.84	17.44	0.06	0.94	402	408.66	615.83	17.78	0.13	0.87
367	182.80	630.65	17.45	0.05	0.95	381	182.45	630.23	17.71	0.13	0.92
368	598.46	621.56	17.45	0.06	0.92	560	598.37	621.45	18.44	0.13	0.94
369	788.47	628.96	17.45	0.05	0.93	438	788.50	629.16	17.94	0.13	0.91
370	332.35	421.72	17.46	0.09	0.89	311	332.23	422.42	17.38	0.13	0.80
371	233.30	656.06	17.46	0.04	0.95	301	233.26	655.88	17.35	0.13	0.98
373	410.38	283.87	17.46	0.04	0.95	455	410.24	283.92	18.00	0.13	0.97
374	467.86	588.23	17.46	0.12	0.90	291	467.71	587.89	17.30	0.13	0.93
375	203.24	233.93	17.46	0.04	0.96	326	202.93	233.91	17.45	0.13	0.99
376	347.46	496.85	17.47	0.08	0.94	481	347.31	496.60	18.10	0.13	0.93
377	544.59	412.44	17.47	0.07	0.92	356	544.44	412.60	17.59	0.13	0.94
378	233.89	996.59	17.47	0.04	0.95	428	233.96	996.38	17.90	0.13	0.97
379	419.22	587.01	17.47	0.08	0.91	368	419.50	586.35	17.68	0.13	0.89
380	466.15	461.65	17.48	0.14	0.88	506	465.93	461.10	18.19	0.14	0.85
381	569.02	733.46	17.48	0.05	0.95	460	568.93	733.47	18.02	0.13	0.97
382	485.26	428.98	17.48	0.11	0.94	384	485.23	428.97	17.72	0.13	0.98
383	519.01	154.35	17.48	0.08	0.96	389	518.85	154.39	17.74	0.13	0.97

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
385	179.83	689.29	17.49	0.05	0.95	407	179.69	689.05	17.80	0.13	0.97
386	699.09	859.26	17.49	0.04	0.96	440	699.18	859.10	17.96	0.13	0.93
387	333.03	253.66	17.49	0.04	0.92	354	332.76	253.56	17.59	0.13	0.95
388	628.18	525.27	17.50	0.06	0.92	395	628.11	525.40	17.76	0.13	0.94
389	629.53	175.34	17.50	0.04	0.92	529	629.54	175.22	18.29	0.13	0.95
390	488.70	87.86	17.51	0.07	0.96	616	488.45	87.93	18.63	0.13	0.93
391	446.87	612.59	17.51	0.07	0.75	361	447.23	612.46	17.64	0.13	0.89
392	501.36	356.31	17.52	0.06	0.92	639	501.21	356.14	18.70	0.13	0.89
393	229.54	687.30	17.52	0.04	0.92	317	229.38	687.30	17.42	0.13	0.92
394	665.53	368.30	17.52	0.04	0.94	391	665.53	368.76	17.74	0.13	0.87
395	727.42	761.14	17.53	0.04	0.94	479	727.29	761.56	18.09	0.13	0.89
396	421.12	579.39	17.53	0.09	0.81	351	420.54	578.59	17.57	0.13	0.89
397	444.12	468.19	17.53	0.13	0.90	378	444.41	467.45	17.70	0.13	0.88
398	415.08	331.65	17.54	0.05	0.95	338	414.87	331.52	17.50	0.13	0.96
399	329.74	246.34	17.55	0.04	0.94	597	329.79	246.25	18.57	0.13	0.96
400	374.87	331.01	17.56	0.05	0.95	414	374.77	331.15	17.85	0.13	0.95
401	844.80	867.92	17.56	0.05	0.94	522	844.61	868.09	18.27	0.13	0.82
402	310.38	658.35	17.56	0.04	0.92	350	310.38	658.22	17.57	0.13	0.88
403	362.31	469.08	17.56	0.09	0.86	699	362.70	467.72	18.91	0.13	0.85
404	742.39	439.71	17.56	0.04	0.94	664	742.23	439.76	18.79	0.13	0.95
405	577.70	897.58	17.57	0.10	0.93	454	577.77	897.66	18.00	0.13	0.94
406	339.49	418.36	17.57	0.09	0.91	327	339.58	417.66	17.45	0.13	0.91
407	504.54	635.29	17.57	0.07	0.82	405	504.19	635.79	17.80	0.13	0.94
408	489.84	326.50	17.58	0.05	0.95	532	489.82	326.35	18.33	0.13	0.94
409	356.68	375.56	17.58	0.06	0.88	370	356.71	375.60	17.68	0.13	0.91
410	200.07	826.35	17.58	0.04	0.94	369	200.00	826.30	17.68	0.13	0.98
411	843.60	630.00	17.58	0.05	0.93	499	843.93	630.18	18.16	0.13	0.83
412	155.21	494.49	17.58	0.06	0.92	375	155.04	494.72	17.70	0.13	0.98
413	301.53	180.29	17.58	0.05	0.93	731	301.40	180.10	19.04	0.13	0.93

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
414	396.20	530.54	17.59	0.10	0.89	500	396.25	530.50	18.16	0.13	0.93
415	313.90	408.59	17.60	0.09	0.95	343	313.74	408.30	17.54	0.13	0.95
416	429.30	578.47	17.60	0.10	0.89	489	429.54	577.84	18.13	0.13	0.94
418	416.96	640.73	17.61	0.06	0.87	335	417.03	640.39	17.49	0.13	0.92
419	687.65	67.03	17.61	0.07	0.93	476	687.59	67.18	18.07	0.13	0.90
420	588.17	323.63	17.62	0.04	0.95	409	588.14	323.38	17.82	0.13	0.93
421	368.28	464.50	17.63	0.10	0.92	408	367.97	463.87	17.82	0.13	0.95
422	228.40	495.90	17.63	0.06	0.94	322	228.20	495.79	17.44	0.13	0.97
423	88.52	644.63	17.64	0.05	0.89	324	88.33	644.44	17.45	0.13	0.92
424	715.51	466.35	17.64	0.05	0.92	496	715.44	466.40	18.15	0.13	0.89
426	73.33	309.56	17.65	0.04	0.94	353	73.09	309.45	17.59	0.13	0.96
427	376.28	650.06	17.65	0.05	0.94	329	376.29	649.95	17.45	0.13	0.97
429	501.83	612.38	17.66	0.10	0.94	579	502.33	612.22	18.51	0.13	0.91
430	437.40	716.09	17.66	0.05	0.94	374	437.32	715.73	17.69	0.13	0.95
431	576.10	279.73	17.66	0.04	0.97	475	575.98	279.55	18.07	0.13	0.95
432	331.58	614.05	17.67	0.05	0.92	465	331.57	613.65	18.03	0.13	0.91
433	430.32	666.19	17.68	0.06	0.86	497	429.87	666.64	18.15	0.13	0.85
435	928.34	894.45	17.68	0.04	0.84	550	928.51	894.57	18.40	0.13	0.81
436	624.39	761.03	17.68	0.05	0.94	484	624.33	760.77	18.11	0.13	0.96
437	481.08	615.74	17.69	0.09	0.93	392	480.87	615.45	17.74	0.13	0.99
438	631.18	28.87	17.70	0.04	0.91	507	631.07	29.09	18.20	0.13	0.94
439	610.80	531.69	17.71	0.07	0.95	512	610.94	531.67	18.23	0.13	0.96
440	531.75	528.20	17.71	0.25	0.83	443	531.75	527.94	17.96	0.16	0.92
441	273.03	566.24	17.71	0.05	0.94	486	272.89	566.00	18.12	0.13	0.99
443	472.87	346.86	17.72	0.06	0.95	764	472.57	346.71	19.15	0.13	0.90
444	381.53	409.32	17.72	0.08	0.89	545	381.48	409.18	18.39	0.13	0.92
445	470.02	627.72	17.72	0.08	0.92	453	469.81	627.52	17.98	0.13	0.94
446	399.35	491.84	17.72	0.11	0.85	310	399.80	490.66	17.38	0.13	0.95
447	446.43	416.71	17.73	0.12	0.89	442	446.30	416.14	17.96	0.13	0.82

ID _K	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	J	σ_J	C _J
448	600.99	412.89	17.74	0.06	0.95	472	600.74	412.90	18.06	0.13	0.95
450	274.88	587.66	17.74	0.05	0.95	525	274.26	587.69	18.27	0.13	0.86
451	324.13	402.49	17.76	0.09	0.92	526	323.70	403.00	18.28	0.13	0.91
452	290.92	445.06	17.77	0.10	0.96	394	290.61	444.84	17.76	0.13	0.95
454	380.50	454.03	17.78	0.10	0.92	431	380.27	453.31	17.92	0.13	0.94
455	361.32	724.72	17.78	0.05	0.89	513	361.17	724.82	18.23	0.13	0.96
456	278.56	556.75	17.79	0.05	0.92	458	278.47	556.17	18.00	0.13	0.92
458	508.93	863.12	17.80	0.11	0.92	547	509.14	862.62	18.40	0.13	0.92
459	367.40	761.63	17.80	0.05	0.90	399	367.11	761.48	17.77	0.13	0.95
460	836.91	658.29	17.80	0.06	0.92	587	836.94	658.44	18.53	0.13	0.91
461	345.70	514.64	17.80	0.08	0.82	421	345.23	516.15	17.88	0.13	0.83
462	365.97	566.94	17.80	0.08	0.92	377	366.04	566.93	17.70	0.13	0.95
463	361.87	648.44	17.80	0.05	0.95	551	361.57	648.00	18.40	0.13	0.93
464	518.95	613.33	17.80	0.11	0.73	410	519.04	613.82	17.82	0.13	0.92
465	556.01	710.82	17.82	0.06	0.95	470	556.02	710.75	18.05	0.13	0.95
466	633.41	313.34	17.82	0.04	0.90	510	633.32	313.28	18.20	0.13	0.90
467	342.83	303.97	17.82	0.04	0.93	606	342.41	303.83	18.61	0.13	0.94
468	384.92	718.47	17.82	0.05	0.92	539	384.71	718.29	18.36	0.13	0.97
469	362.59	846.55	17.82	0.08	0.89	477	362.69	846.31	18.09	0.13	0.96
470	632.66	656.76	17.82	0.05	0.90	514	632.67	656.45	18.23	0.13	0.91
471	346.61	260.24	17.83	0.04	0.93	625	346.42	260.28	18.67	0.13	0.93
472	499.11	302.22	17.83	0.04	0.95	517	498.95	302.14	18.25	0.13	0.97
473	383.14	561.31	17.83	0.09	0.85	609	383.54	561.62	18.62	0.13	0.81
474	611.19	269.11	17.83	0.06	0.94	521	611.27	268.83	18.26	0.13	0.94
476	379.06	601.22	17.84	0.06	0.70	447	378.90	601.25	17.97	0.13	0.88
477	463.10	270.56	17.85	0.04	0.93	495	463.03	270.73	18.15	0.13	0.97
478	271.70	273.51	17.86	0.05	0.88	483	271.33	272.96	18.10	0.13	0.94
479	299.26	398.16	17.86	0.11	0.88	502	299.10	398.70	18.17	0.13	0.97
480	61.83	858.75	17.86	0.04	0.93	401	61.43	858.58	17.78	0.13	0.92

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
481	409.06	451.56	17.86	0.12	0.88	441	408.89	451.71	17.96	0.13	0.94
482	335.55	522.65	17.87	0.08	0.93	358	334.60	523.09	17.60	0.13	0.92
484	358.35	455.84	17.87	0.12	0.92	515	358.15	455.64	18.24	0.13	0.90
486	381.93	759.42	17.88	0.05	0.90	449	381.75	759.52	17.98	0.13	0.94
487	740.14	580.61	17.88	0.05	0.90	696	740.29	580.36	18.89	0.13	0.89
488	60.85	313.28	17.88	0.04	0.84	509	60.01	313.03	18.20	0.13	0.94
489	271.90	606.61	17.89	0.05	0.82	492	271.87	605.99	18.14	0.13	0.99
491	300.88	356.86	17.91	0.09	0.90	632	300.65	356.84	18.68	0.13	0.92
492	559.46	305.44	17.91	0.04	0.88	537	559.60	305.32	18.36	0.13	0.93
493	398.73	172.51	17.92	0.07	0.89	490	398.53	172.68	18.14	0.13	0.90
494	789.33	368.46	17.92	0.08	0.87	558	789.62	368.37	18.43	0.13	0.90
495	459.75	701.00	17.92	0.06	0.80	519	460.20	699.86	18.25	0.13	0.91
497	515.39	817.60	17.93	0.06	0.90	508	515.37	817.25	18.20	0.13	0.93
499	301.85	624.49	17.94	0.05	0.80	582	301.90	624.49	18.52	0.13	0.95
501	673.77	623.91	17.95	0.05	0.91	780	673.67	623.92	19.20	0.13	0.92
502	285.17	509.39	17.96	0.08	0.83	418	284.64	509.21	17.88	0.13	0.81
503	472.11	725.71	17.96	0.06	0.88	619	471.76	725.51	18.65	0.13	0.94
504	756.70	518.91	17.96	0.05	0.92	543	756.78	518.55	18.39	0.13	0.93
505	801.52	443.54	17.96	0.04	0.88	552	801.46	443.60	18.41	0.13	0.89
507	555.02	557.04	17.97	0.17	0.84	540	555.35	556.77	18.38	0.15	0.81
508	547.19	783.63	17.97	0.05	0.93	523	547.11	783.43	18.27	0.13	0.95
509	557.28	365.48	17.97	0.06	0.91	572	557.08	365.70	18.49	0.13	0.96
510	769.62	738.68	17.97	0.06	0.90	749	769.33	738.74	19.07	0.13	0.87
511	409.94	865.05	17.97	0.13	0.94	642	409.56	864.99	18.71	0.13	0.93
512	324.14	728.79	17.97	0.04	0.95	444	324.05	728.61	17.96	0.13	0.97
513	755.60	247.39	17.98	0.06	0.88	585	755.72	247.68	18.53	0.13	0.88
514	294.51	533.96	17.98	0.07	0.74	527	295.20	534.83	18.29	0.13	0.88
515	738.29	616.51	17.98	0.05	0.86	624	738.55	616.68	18.66	0.13	0.89
516	591.74	728.92	17.98	0.07	0.90	535	591.99	729.13	18.34	0.13	0.85

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
517	419.22	648.57	17.98	0.06	0.85	456	419.09	648.47	18.00	0.13	0.92
519	424.31	634.62	17.98	0.07	0.87	546	424.29	633.98	18.40	0.13	0.87
520	526.22	422.83	17.99	0.12	0.92	536	526.31	422.87	18.34	0.13	0.95
521	348.98	36.17	17.99	0.06	0.90	693	348.93	36.23	18.88	0.13	0.95
522	123.67	760.03	18.00	0.04	0.93	686	123.60	759.74	18.86	0.13	0.92
524	269.68	403.21	18.00	0.15	0.88	448	269.59	403.00	17.97	0.13	0.88
525	427.39	300.01	18.00	0.05	0.87	590	427.35	299.69	18.54	0.13	0.86
526	369.54	261.44	18.00	0.05	0.89	718	369.41	261.28	18.97	0.13	0.91
527	324.97	816.58	18.00	0.05	0.92	473	324.86	816.24	18.06	0.13	0.98
528	112.35	599.61	18.00	0.07	0.88	467	112.53	600.20	18.04	0.13	0.87
529	630.29	825.05	18.00	0.04	0.89	742	630.25	824.99	19.06	0.13	0.91
530	60.88	793.99	18.00	0.04	0.91	596	61.00	793.78	18.57	0.13	0.94
531	401.13	725.36	18.01	0.05	0.91	591	401.35	724.95	18.55	0.13	0.96
532	189.22	691.06	18.01	0.05	0.90	503	189.18	690.83	18.17	0.13	0.98
534	349.39	376.76	18.02	0.08	0.92	463	349.08	376.47	18.03	0.13	0.95
535	653.55	668.63	18.02	0.05	0.81	520	653.21	669.19	18.25	0.13	0.87
536	349.68	594.12	18.02	0.06	0.75	498	349.20	594.28	18.16	0.13	0.93
537	529.04	253.90	18.02	0.07	0.95	680	529.24	253.83	18.85	0.13	0.96
538	204.03	614.05	18.03	0.05	0.92	600	203.87	614.27	18.57	0.13	0.98
539	215.91	915.81	18.03	0.04	0.76	641	216.04	915.65	18.71	0.13	0.95
540	488.80	97.90	18.04	0.09	0.94	538	488.85	97.94	18.36	0.13	0.95
541	270.85	612.18	18.04	0.05	0.90	505	270.93	612.27	18.18	0.13	0.96
542	197.99	564.67	18.05	0.06	0.87	451	197.66	564.19	17.98	0.13	0.96
545	519.41	1013.99	18.05	0.04	0.89	649	519.33	1014.30	18.74	0.13	0.89
546	153.11	186.08	18.05	0.07	0.90	466	153.16	185.82	18.03	0.13	0.97
548	460.03	340.11	18.06	0.07	0.89	608	459.65	340.46	18.61	0.13	0.90
549	488.38	292.26	18.06	0.04	0.88	573	487.96	292.35	18.49	0.13	0.96
551	291.48	610.69	18.06	0.05	0.85	562	290.83	610.95	18.45	0.13	0.94
552	555.42	823.12	18.07	0.06	0.86	577	555.26	823.08	18.50	0.13	0.94

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ _K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ _J	C _J
554	341.84	392.00	18.08	0.10	0.93	615	341.67	391.89	18.63	0.13	0.93
556	682.55	619.86	18.09	0.05	0.91	691	682.87	619.96	18.87	0.13	0.90
557	55.36	675.41	18.09	0.05	0.85	784	54.97	675.18	19.22	0.13	0.96
558	449.67	290.97	18.09	0.04	0.89	677	449.47	290.76	18.84	0.13	0.92
559	561.38	497.41	18.10	0.22	0.82	644	561.53	496.64	18.71	0.15	0.83
561	604.61	611.84	18.10	0.10	0.87	656	604.86	612.02	18.76	0.13	0.90
563	337.77	571.57	18.10	0.07	0.82	485	337.35	572.89	18.11	0.13	0.81
564	719.17	375.03	18.10	0.04	0.84	605	718.95	375.42	18.60	0.13	0.95
565	404.62	330.10	18.10	0.05	0.84	736	404.29	329.71	19.05	0.14	0.89
566	796.11	878.92	18.11	0.05	0.87	743	796.51	879.12	19.06	0.13	0.91
567	651.51	578.92	18.11	0.06	0.91	588	651.39	578.72	18.54	0.13	0.95
568	783.98	782.69	18.11	0.05	0.90	665	783.84	782.97	18.81	0.13	0.93
569	208.41	526.17	18.12	0.07	0.83	412	208.19	526.04	17.82	0.13	0.99
570	241.25	454.70	18.12	0.08	0.87	474	241.05	454.41	18.07	0.13	0.96
571	417.57	598.52	18.12	0.10	0.87	681	416.70	599.50	18.85	0.13	0.82
574	785.73	661.49	18.12	0.06	0.88	949	786.12	661.41	19.80	0.13	0.84
575	396.13	745.96	18.13	0.05	0.91	626	396.32	746.15	18.67	0.13	0.95
576	241.77	255.39	18.13	0.04	0.88	698	241.12	255.28	18.91	0.13	0.96
577	197.85	703.00	18.13	0.04	0.91	549	197.71	702.87	18.40	0.13	0.96
578	331.06	200.12	18.13	0.04	0.91	501	331.02	200.02	18.17	0.13	0.99
579	393.16	398.95	18.13	0.09	0.91	544	393.17	398.88	18.39	0.13	0.92
580	385.59	472.55	18.13	0.14	0.88	689	385.24	472.35	18.86	0.13	0.82
583	470.62	660.64	18.14	0.09	0.78	635	470.27	661.23	18.70	0.13	0.83
584	482.55	811.03	18.15	0.07	0.88	580	482.23	810.88	18.51	0.13	0.96
585	200.03	528.08	18.15	0.07	0.86	595	199.66	528.29	18.56	0.13	0.93
586	439.49	918.37	18.15	0.14	0.88	643	439.64	918.16	18.71	0.13	0.94
587	357.62	745.80	18.15	0.05	0.85	604	357.46	745.69	18.59	0.13	0.91
588	528.99	762.23	18.16	0.05	0.87	812	529.45	762.01	19.35	0.13	0.89
589	407.19	360.03	18.16	0.07	0.76	620	407.20	359.92	18.66	0.13	0.91

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
590	167.57	478.91	18.16	0.08	0.85	613	167.52	478.86	18.62	0.13	0.93
591	379.45	162.80	18.17	0.04	0.88	737	378.91	163.01	19.05	0.13	0.88
592	220.77	389.86	18.17	0.11	0.93	599	220.46	389.34	18.57	0.13	0.94
593	577.65	803.70	18.17	0.04	0.89	824	577.61	803.79	19.39	0.13	0.89
595	454.83	804.88	18.17	0.06	0.91	554	454.51	804.84	18.42	0.13	0.91
596	188.44	785.39	18.18	0.05	0.88	859	188.28	785.32	19.53	0.13	0.93
597	689.13	368.82	18.18	0.05	0.89	612	689.05	368.91	18.62	0.13	0.91
598	62.71	926.36	18.19	0.04	0.83	584	62.56	926.61	18.53	0.13	0.92
600	430.21	283.10	18.20	0.04	0.90	670	430.11	283.04	18.82	0.13	0.97
602	923.95	422.06	18.20	0.04	0.85	712	923.67	422.41	18.96	0.13	0.92
603	451.87	280.85	18.20	0.04	0.89	855	451.27	280.89	19.51	0.13	0.86
604	357.54	576.83	18.20	0.08	0.81	494	357.28	576.28	18.15	0.13	0.88
605	294.41	739.46	18.22	0.04	0.87	530	294.14	739.67	18.29	0.13	0.97
606	609.34	34.74	18.22	0.05	0.84	589	609.28	35.21	18.54	0.13	0.89
607	348.93	231.33	18.22	0.04	0.85	533	348.61	231.16	18.33	0.13	0.93
609	745.05	670.11	18.23	0.05	0.84	972	744.89	670.28	19.89	0.13	0.90
610	140.99	1018.01	18.23	0.04	0.79	461	140.67	1019.42	18.02	0.13	0.95
611	360.42	562.72	18.23	0.09	0.76	592	359.73	562.49	18.56	0.13	0.90
612	708.36	858.33	18.24	0.04	0.83	654	707.97	858.28	18.75	0.13	0.86
614	715.62	589.19	18.24	0.05	0.88	668	715.39	589.25	18.81	0.13	0.89
615	561.36	393.80	18.24	0.09	0.76	557	560.87	393.60	18.43	0.13	0.85
616	79.32	875.03	18.25	0.06	0.89	697	78.79	874.40	18.89	0.13	0.95
617	275.41	860.14	18.25	0.04	0.81	773	275.11	860.21	19.18	0.13	0.97
618	674.60	720.14	18.26	0.05	0.88	610	674.51	720.14	18.62	0.13	0.90
620	778.64	260.95	18.27	0.09	0.87	931	778.82	260.70	19.76	0.13	0.82
621	184.66	436.37	18.27	0.07	0.82	847	184.53	436.12	19.47	0.13	0.88
622	295.12	1000.18	18.27	0.05	0.88	617	294.97	999.97	18.64	0.13	0.98
623	740.34	350.96	18.28	0.06	0.87	729	739.88	350.70	19.03	0.13	0.93
624	187.28	494.91	18.29	0.08	0.85	711	187.45	494.77	18.96	0.13	0.92

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
625	594.90	215.05	18.29	0.15	0.82	745	595.09	214.77	19.06	0.13	0.93
626	249.95	420.84	18.29	0.12	0.92	694	249.69	420.75	18.88	0.13	0.95
627	422.26	704.78	18.29	0.06	0.80	518	421.97	704.78	18.25	0.13	0.97
628	815.18	533.83	18.29	0.06	0.80	661	815.01	533.70	18.78	0.13	0.89
629	399.08	361.40	18.29	0.08	0.71	652	400.35	360.62	18.74	0.13	0.84
631	179.48	491.87	18.30	0.08	0.78	504	179.41	491.74	18.18	0.13	0.94
632	662.83	449.77	18.30	0.08	0.88	885	662.93	449.55	19.60	0.13	0.86
633	367.98	148.28	18.30	0.05	0.87	555	367.82	147.48	18.42	0.13	0.94
634	720.69	703.78	18.31	0.05	0.88	825	720.43	703.68	19.39	0.13	0.87
635	404.80	354.85	18.31	0.08	0.73	723	404.16	354.65	19.00	0.13	0.83
636	771.65	760.20	18.31	0.06	0.83	760	771.60	760.64	19.13	0.13	0.91
637	220.52	919.55	18.31	0.04	0.85	640	220.98	919.25	18.71	0.13	0.93
638	653.04	630.88	18.31	0.06	0.88	830	653.43	631.15	19.41	0.13	0.93
639	604.27	503.63	18.32	0.14	0.84	782	604.04	503.53	19.20	0.14	0.82
640	613.69	966.79	18.32	0.16	0.88	673	613.60	966.49	18.83	0.13	0.84
641	277.24	262.38	18.32	0.05	0.86	564	277.06	262.30	18.45	0.13	0.95
642	394.47	777.44	18.32	0.05	0.82	755	394.86	777.52	19.10	0.13	0.93
643	304.65	282.40	18.32	0.05	0.83	646	304.70	281.59	18.72	0.13	0.91
644	212.91	505.50	18.33	0.08	0.83	567	212.11	505.71	18.46	0.13	0.95
646	193.71	90.03	18.33	0.04	0.83	672	193.80	89.33	18.82	0.13	0.96
647	456.75	199.49	18.33	0.14	0.85	716	456.52	199.52	18.97	0.13	0.90
649	180.57	665.54	18.34	0.06	0.85	516	180.14	665.14	18.25	0.13	0.97
650	259.26	509.79	18.35	0.09	0.83	692	258.63	510.11	18.88	0.13	0.93
651	280.95	849.08	18.35	0.05	0.92	750	280.85	848.99	19.09	0.13	0.97
654	413.25	255.77	18.36	0.06	0.86	754	412.80	256.28	19.10	0.13	0.96
655	645.35	502.65	18.36	0.10	0.73	660	645.81	502.58	18.78	0.13	0.91
657	835.03	348.17	18.36	0.09	0.82	703	835.32	347.92	18.93	0.13	0.89
658	258.59	519.25	18.36	0.08	0.84	647	258.05	519.08	18.72	0.13	0.93
659	701.60	744.47	18.36	0.05	0.79	769	701.35	744.72	19.16	0.13	0.88

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
660	317.03	559.21	18.36	0.08	0.79	569	316.76	558.74	18.47	0.13	0.93
662	566.04	389.00	18.37	0.10	0.87	556	565.76	389.55	18.43	0.13	0.92
665	800.23	751.98	18.37	0.08	0.88	722	799.83	752.05	18.99	0.13	0.92
666	173.78	826.70	18.37	0.05	0.86	622	173.74	826.45	18.66	0.13	0.95
667	347.91	203.90	18.38	0.05	0.86	651	347.46	203.00	18.74	0.13	0.88
668	570.07	787.82	18.38	0.05	0.86	882	570.14	787.90	19.60	0.13	0.96
669	221.68	808.17	18.38	0.04	0.85	709	221.65	807.73	18.95	0.13	0.93
670	660.20	672.08	18.38	0.05	0.81	629	659.70	671.65	18.67	0.13	0.83
671	241.48	629.53	18.38	0.05	0.79	565	241.08	629.46	18.45	0.13	0.95
672	321.88	507.57	18.39	0.13	0.87	570	321.64	507.58	18.48	0.13	0.93
673	608.30	901.37	18.39	0.15	0.87	787	607.88	901.03	19.23	0.13	0.95
675	211.94	283.88	18.39	0.05	0.89	611	211.18	283.53	18.62	0.13	0.98
676	704.25	970.57	18.39	0.05	0.84	752	704.22	969.62	19.09	0.13	0.85
677	365.94	579.13	18.39	0.10	0.78	531	364.92	579.48	18.32	0.13	0.92
678	657.30	312.81	18.39	0.05	0.83	838	656.98	312.78	19.44	0.13	0.91
679	647.87	457.36	18.40	0.10	0.83	669	647.74	457.53	18.81	0.13	0.94
680	306.95	628.86	18.40	0.05	0.86	491	306.81	629.11	18.14	0.13	0.96
681	607.39	820.32	18.40	0.04	0.81	725	607.09	820.50	19.01	0.13	0.90
682	137.16	912.89	18.41	0.04	0.80	715	137.28	912.21	18.97	0.13	0.96
683	719.14	802.67	18.41	0.05	0.81	634	719.09	801.92	18.69	0.13	0.87
684	136.65	872.67	18.42	0.09	0.78	638	136.75	871.92	18.70	0.13	0.97
685	209.06	956.92	18.42	0.04	0.78	951	208.82	956.83	19.80	0.13	0.94
688	778.49	673.55	18.42	0.07	0.83	927	778.60	673.62	19.75	0.13	0.86
689	384.82	632.28	18.43	0.06	0.83	789	385.10	631.63	19.23	0.13	0.92
691	756.23	817.87	18.43	0.05	0.80	795	756.08	817.77	19.27	0.13	0.92
692	404.04	672.24	18.43	0.07	0.87	879	403.87	671.80	19.58	0.13	0.93
695	483.92	255.57	18.44	0.05	0.75	598	484.02	256.13	18.57	0.13	0.91
696	137.40	318.70	18.44	0.05	0.80	559	136.93	318.27	18.44	0.13	0.99
697	283.73	612.85	18.45	0.05	0.89	548	283.35	612.44	18.40	0.13	0.87

ID _K	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	X _{pix}	Y _{pix}	J	σ_J	C _J
698	487.64	870.73	18.45	0.24	0.80	713	487.92	870.21	18.96	0.13	0.95
699	367.78	453.63	18.45	0.18	0.86	827	367.90	453.38	19.39	0.13	0.90
701	623.11	492.04	18.46	0.14	0.88	628	622.99	491.75	18.67	0.13	0.90
702	760.30	455.34	18.47	0.05	0.82	906	760.12	455.65	19.66	0.13	0.90
703	566.60	291.58	18.47	0.04	0.84	759	566.86	291.25	19.12	0.13	0.92
704	621.76	346.97	18.48	0.05	0.82	781	622.14	347.10	19.20	0.13	0.94
705	176.39	580.08	18.48	0.08	0.88	676	176.39	579.70	18.83	0.13	0.95
707	80.56	345.83	18.50	0.05	0.72	710	80.21	345.81	18.95	0.13	0.96
708	84.89	105.42	18.50	0.08	0.78	770	84.79	105.85	19.16	0.13	0.95
710	312.93	588.14	18.50	0.07	0.91	553	312.81	588.22	18.42	0.13	0.99
711	55.26	838.48	18.50	0.04	0.76	702	55.08	838.18	18.93	0.13	0.98
712	587.53	358.88	18.50	0.06	0.72	797	587.36	358.61	19.28	0.13	0.80
714	661.05	748.37	18.51	0.05	0.83	733	661.08	748.83	19.04	0.13	0.95
715	511.34	654.82	18.51	0.12	0.72	800	511.83	654.97	19.31	0.15	0.85
719	101.29	969.19	18.51	0.05	0.84	738	101.38	969.04	19.05	0.13	0.92
721	616.93	236.67	18.52	0.13	0.76	815	616.69	236.01	19.37	0.13	0.93
722	821.36	777.58	18.52	0.08	0.84	826	821.40	777.19	19.39	0.13	0.89
723	354.31	698.76	18.52	0.05	0.85	636	353.78	699.33	18.70	0.13	0.81
725	244.27	620.34	18.52	0.05	0.76	571	244.15	620.50	18.48	0.13	0.95
727	672.30	342.60	18.53	0.05	0.81	939	672.80	342.49	19.78	0.14	0.92
728	602.40	661.80	18.53	0.08	0.81	767	602.33	661.33	19.15	0.13	0.94
729	480.57	729.19	18.53	0.07	0.81	637	480.29	728.73	18.70	0.13	0.96
732	534.46	265.12	18.54	0.06	0.85	667	534.16	265.59	18.81	0.13	0.94
733	598.63	573.71	18.54	0.16	0.86	822	598.86	573.69	19.39	0.13	0.80
734	151.05	738.82	18.54	0.04	0.81	685	150.75	738.85	18.86	0.13	0.96
735	630.83	968.30	18.54	0.14	0.86	897	630.49	967.88	19.63	0.13	0.91
736	661.28	911.43	18.54	0.10	0.78	817	661.10	911.97	19.38	0.13	0.90
739	242.81	400.81	18.55	0.19	0.77	563	242.35	400.73	18.45	0.13	0.89
743	338.23	315.26	18.56	0.05	0.80	657	338.16	315.14	18.77	0.13	0.96

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
744	534.98	419.04	18.56	0.17	0.74	828	534.07	419.29	19.39	0.13	0.82
748	166.69	730.17	18.57	0.05	0.85	762	165.95	730.16	19.14	0.13	0.98
749	564.92	676.60	18.58	0.08	0.83	884	564.71	676.73	19.60	0.13	0.96
750	388.90	547.75	18.58	0.18	0.72	574	388.86	547.81	18.49	0.13	0.83
753	618.26	682.23	18.58	0.07	0.86	923	618.38	681.79	19.74	0.13	0.92
755	755.85	629.04	18.58	0.07	0.87	941	756.29	629.21	19.78	0.13	0.82
756	49.06	462.11	18.59	0.04	0.76	707	49.39	461.23	18.94	0.13	0.90
757	607.84	827.06	18.59	0.05	0.79	813	608.15	827.09	19.36	0.13	0.91
759	257.47	464.44	18.59	0.12	0.82	796	257.12	463.73	19.28	0.13	0.86
760	422.35	638.83	18.60	0.10	0.67	581	422.34	639.21	18.51	0.13	0.80
761	650.91	505.47	18.60	0.11	0.78	774	650.86	506.04	19.18	0.13	0.80
764	313.67	620.63	18.61	0.06	0.81	683	313.13	620.62	18.85	0.13	0.94
765	520.61	744.73	18.61	0.07	0.78	772	520.48	744.60	19.17	0.13	0.91
766	819.03	445.69	18.61	0.05	0.68	687	817.71	445.94	18.86	0.13	0.90
767	696.80	250.55	18.62	0.17	0.83	768	696.69	251.39	19.16	0.13	0.91
768	281.13	871.41	18.62	0.05	0.77	618	281.18	871.34	18.64	0.13	0.96
769	341.97	703.37	18.62	0.05	0.83	586	341.86	703.07	18.53	0.13	0.98
770	575.74	686.85	18.63	0.09	0.83	776	575.76	686.60	19.19	0.13	0.94
771	629.11	436.82	18.63	0.12	0.85	921	628.95	437.14	19.73	0.13	0.90
772	588.83	352.14	18.63	0.06	0.82	758	588.57	352.52	19.12	0.13	0.87
773	305.36	68.88	18.63	0.12	0.74	704	304.82	68.37	18.93	0.13	0.95
774	500.59	778.59	18.64	0.05	0.75	719	500.36	778.58	18.98	0.13	0.91
775	698.13	422.83	18.64	0.06	0.84	799	697.99	422.98	19.30	0.13	0.95
776	279.01	956.54	18.64	0.07	0.76	684	278.89	955.94	18.86	0.13	0.98
777	363.23	484.10	18.65	0.21	0.73	662	362.10	483.89	18.79	0.13	0.86
778	85.20	543.88	18.65	0.09	0.73	578	84.90	543.80	18.50	0.13	0.98
779	300.66	754.55	18.65	0.05	0.80	679	300.46	753.86	18.85	0.13	0.94
780	448.73	783.13	18.65	0.05	0.86	614	448.32	783.15	18.62	0.13	0.95
781	220.10	964.74	18.65	0.05	0.67	888	219.89	965.39	19.60	0.13	0.93

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
783	461.97	843.13	18.66	0.26	0.86	890	461.56	843.26	19.61	0.13	0.91
784	288.31	300.35	18.66	0.09	0.81	801	288.34	299.60	19.31	0.13	0.89
785	341.79	327.43	18.66	0.06	0.80	823	341.62	328.47	19.39	0.13	0.89
787	288.84	426.00	18.67	0.20	0.77	721	289.49	426.18	18.99	0.13	0.87
789	832.46	823.26	18.67	0.06	0.76	932	832.72	823.91	19.76	0.13	0.87
791	287.54	884.45	18.67	0.05	0.70	811	286.72	884.05	19.35	0.13	0.94
793	381.62	798.88	18.68	0.05	0.71	777	381.65	798.58	19.19	0.13	0.90
795	594.45	410.60	18.68	0.12	0.72	807	594.92	412.02	19.33	0.13	0.81
797	158.28	548.23	18.69	0.10	0.70	627	157.66	548.13	18.67	0.13	0.95
799	173.71	503.42	18.69	0.11	0.76	794	173.57	501.87	19.27	0.13	0.90
801	236.77	644.81	18.70	0.05	0.71	674	237.01	643.95	18.83	0.13	0.97
802	195.18	258.32	18.70	0.04	0.76	899	194.55	257.80	19.63	0.13	0.92
803	138.91	993.24	18.71	0.05	0.74	900	138.44	993.55	19.64	0.13	0.86
804	421.29	653.33	18.71	0.10	0.78	753	421.55	653.31	19.09	0.13	0.93
805	47.03	151.28	18.71	0.04	0.71	964	46.12	151.07	19.86	0.13	0.86
806	680.73	914.48	18.71	0.07	0.81	998	681.70	914.65	20.05	0.13	0.83
807	406.12	335.10	18.71	0.08	0.81	791	406.19	335.12	19.25	0.14	0.83
809	265.57	521.73	18.72	0.11	0.72	675	265.62	521.70	18.83	0.13	0.95
811	245.11	719.00	18.72	0.04	0.74	829	245.19	718.16	19.39	0.13	0.90
812	461.49	909.05	18.72	0.28	0.82	938	461.16	908.37	19.77	0.13	0.91
813	248.35	576.25	18.73	0.06	0.81	790	248.29	576.13	19.24	0.13	0.94
817	663.42	526.90	18.73	0.09	0.65	751	663.59	526.27	19.09	0.13	0.87
819	528.06	681.66	18.74	0.10	0.80	701	527.91	681.96	18.92	0.13	0.96
820	425.97	741.84	18.74	0.07	0.73	735	425.91	741.66	19.05	0.13	0.94
823	118.89	553.10	18.74	0.10	0.73	700	118.98	553.25	18.91	0.13	0.98
824	401.99	634.63	18.75	0.09	0.79	655	401.70	634.11	18.76	0.13	0.97
825	314.37	252.74	18.75	0.05	0.82	805	314.02	253.16	19.33	0.13	0.96
826	572.80	914.96	18.76	0.26	0.71	771	573.12	915.30	19.16	0.13	0.94
827	212.57	635.96	18.76	0.06	0.72	633	212.61	635.51	18.68	0.13	0.91

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
828	599.63	384.08	18.76	0.09	0.81	706	599.66	383.79	18.93	0.13	0.91
829	74.58	638.57	18.76	0.09	0.76	870	74.19	637.63	19.56	0.13	0.87
830	879.38	530.16	18.77	0.05	0.78	852	880.13	530.42	19.49	0.13	0.82
833	251.95	644.74	18.77	0.05	0.68	717	251.79	644.13	18.97	0.13	0.84
835	287.87	794.06	18.77	0.05	0.72	957	287.96	793.35	19.82	0.13	0.92
838	739.40	533.01	18.78	0.07	0.70	804	739.60	533.32	19.33	0.13	0.90
839	192.53	22.01	18.78	0.05	0.78	808	192.68	21.64	19.33	0.13	0.92
841	641.31	527.04	18.78	0.12	0.88	783	641.77	526.66	19.21	0.13	0.88
842	244.05	637.58	18.79	0.05	0.71	844	243.48	635.68	19.46	0.13	0.81
843	532.91	774.95	18.79	0.06	0.81	720	532.64	775.53	18.98	0.13	0.94
844	85.84	365.53	18.79	0.05	0.76	860	85.06	366.26	19.53	0.13	0.94
845	615.40	254.69	18.79	0.13	0.74	993	615.54	253.90	20.01	0.13	0.89
851	418.07	671.58	18.80	0.09	0.71	724	417.72	670.98	19.00	0.13	0.92
852	693.55	324.70	18.81	0.05	0.79	849	693.26	325.86	19.48	0.13	0.94
854	584.46	285.87	18.81	0.05	0.85	946	585.20	285.55	19.79	0.13	0.86
856	284.36	92.64	18.82	0.16	0.68	798	284.34	93.14	19.29	0.13	0.88
858	54.57	582.07	18.83	0.06	0.78	886	54.81	581.74	19.60	0.13	0.94
859	487.73	634.93	18.83	0.18	0.73	648	487.51	633.89	18.73	0.13	0.82
861	564.01	654.61	18.83	0.13	0.68	850	563.30	653.90	19.48	0.16	0.82
862	839.13	837.68	18.83	0.06	0.71	820	838.78	837.14	19.38	0.13	0.88
863	737.36	887.17	18.84	0.05	0.77	876	737.40	887.53	19.57	0.13	0.86
865	82.95	895.46	18.84	0.08	0.69	757	83.88	894.53	19.11	0.13	0.95
866	793.02	531.97	18.84	0.10	0.79	846	792.73	531.97	19.46	0.13	0.91
868	179.56	856.53	18.85	0.05	0.66	960	179.01	856.19	19.83	0.13	0.94
869	118.91	364.39	18.85	0.06	0.65	678	118.52	363.86	18.84	0.13	0.92
870	154.52	509.20	18.85	0.12	0.74	851	154.65	508.84	19.48	0.13	0.91
871	419.59	911.02	18.85	0.26	0.75	814	420.04	911.05	19.37	0.13	0.96
872	492.17	395.83	18.85	0.24	0.78	653	491.86	395.90	18.75	0.13	0.95
873	714.94	772.10	18.86	0.06	0.75	956	713.83	771.79	19.81	0.13	0.90

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
875	739.17	464.23	18.86	0.08	0.76	839	738.21	464.58	19.45	0.13	0.91
877	240.13	527.55	18.87	0.10	0.67	650	241.30	527.82	18.74	0.13	0.89
878	332.77	631.60	18.87	0.07	0.77	623	332.34	631.38	18.66	0.13	0.91
880	70.11	562.44	18.87	0.09	0.71	708	69.24	561.65	18.94	0.13	0.95
881	423.58	451.37	18.88	0.30	0.76	488	422.74	451.84	18.12	0.13	0.84
884	579.51	870.68	18.89	0.27	0.68	967	579.31	869.80	19.87	0.13	0.83
885	812.35	557.78	18.89	0.08	0.74	947	813.04	558.13	19.80	0.13	0.87
886	452.96	231.71	18.89	0.08	0.71	901	452.26	231.46	19.64	0.13	0.81
887	222.64	418.72	18.89	0.14	0.72	887	223.77	417.86	19.60	0.13	0.91
888	366.45	877.69	18.90	0.22	0.68	986	366.15	877.19	19.97	0.13	0.92
889	324.36	612.50	18.90	0.07	0.68	948	323.61	611.55	19.80	0.13	0.90
893	356.53	655.10	18.91	0.07	0.73	741	357.25	656.34	19.06	0.13	0.93
894	769.57	431.21	18.91	0.05	0.76	1004	768.69	430.75	20.10	0.13	0.88
895	631.09	939.43	18.91	0.19	0.78	842	631.29	939.01	19.46	0.13	0.83
896	591.51	220.66	18.91	0.24	0.80	929	591.67	219.71	19.75	0.13	0.89
898	780.44	888.48	18.91	0.06	0.66	877	780.30	888.54	19.57	0.13	0.85
901	324.15	709.31	18.93	0.05	0.78	1030	323.28	709.05	20.26	0.14	0.84
903	176.72	516.45	18.94	0.12	0.70	727	176.42	515.87	19.03	0.13	0.94
905	203.88	506.77	18.94	0.12	0.72	892	202.88	505.34	19.62	0.13	0.95
906	742.11	428.32	18.94	0.06	0.75	1075	741.26	429.02	20.65	0.14	0.81
907	59.33	437.40	18.94	0.05	0.74	878	58.94	438.15	19.58	0.13	0.98
909	504.55	283.05	18.95	0.05	0.66	740	503.78	283.61	19.06	0.13	0.90
910	218.68	46.10	18.95	0.07	0.73	761	218.35	46.34	19.13	0.13	0.87
913	449.69	346.72	18.98	0.15	0.78	928	449.24	347.15	19.75	0.13	0.92
915	233.99	604.87	18.98	0.06	0.72	970	234.22	605.64	19.88	0.13	0.85
917	616.01	926.51	18.98	0.26	0.74	802	615.96	927.72	19.32	0.13	0.86
919	578.20	341.14	18.99	0.06	0.67	835	578.32	341.26	19.43	0.13	0.86
920	207.49	595.80	18.99	0.07	0.70	1000	208.07	596.55	20.07	0.13	0.87
921	501.10	424.23	19.00	0.32	0.76	821	501.31	424.56	19.38	0.13	0.84

ID _K	Xpix	Ypix	K _s	σ_K	C _K	ID _J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C _J
922	457.86	833.54	19.00	0.30	0.69	1028	457.49	833.73	20.24	0.14	0.84
923	312.13	91.36	19.00	0.19	0.66	763	311.91	91.64	19.14	0.13	0.94
924	376.27	762.74	19.01	0.07	0.68	833	376.27	762.81	19.42	0.13	0.89
925	257.67	608.81	19.01	0.06	0.76	985	258.03	608.56	19.97	0.13	0.81
926	678.31	483.70	19.01	0.13	0.71	1032	678.30	484.58	20.28	0.15	0.88
927	143.84	726.58	19.01	0.06	0.70	950	143.48	726.53	19.80	0.13	0.81
928	880.30	616.40	19.01	0.10	0.72	1044	881.46	616.33	20.34	0.14	0.83
930	213.46	577.41	19.01	0.09	0.68	856	213.28	577.67	19.52	0.13	0.94
932	922.23	506.18	19.02	0.05	0.70	1010	923.13	505.69	20.14	0.13	0.87
934	356.75	488.87	19.02	0.28	0.70	756	356.66	488.89	19.10	0.13	0.94
936	173.50	110.13	19.03	0.05	0.76	875	173.89	110.60	19.57	0.13	0.93
941	506.75	289.25	19.04	0.05	0.80	819	506.88	289.13	19.38	0.13	0.90
942	491.33	714.43	19.04	0.12	0.79	765	490.84	714.36	19.15	0.13	0.95
943	656.45	356.20	19.04	0.06	0.72	857	656.44	355.86	19.52	0.13	0.81
948	108.80	279.01	19.07	0.05	0.76	746	107.78	279.29	19.07	0.13	0.96
949	384.56	751.17	19.07	0.08	0.67	809	384.52	751.06	19.34	0.13	0.92
951	198.81	574.48	19.07	0.10	0.67	788	198.99	573.64	19.23	0.13	0.94
954	107.94	494.39	19.08	0.12	0.66	766	108.05	494.64	19.15	0.13	0.94
961	808.79	613.96	19.11	0.09	0.74	987	808.97	614.15	19.97	0.13	0.93
964	198.04	927.65	19.11	0.05	0.72	871	196.71	928.35	19.56	0.13	0.93
966	617.59	563.55	19.12	0.19	0.81	848	617.68	564.31	19.47	0.13	0.83
967	194.43	525.40	19.12	0.13	0.73	1003	193.10	524.60	20.09	0.13	0.82
969	274.34	424.58	19.13	0.28	0.79	854	274.05	424.16	19.51	0.13	0.91
971	388.07	835.22	19.13	0.13	0.67	810	387.21	833.89	19.34	0.13	0.93
974	284.68	621.91	19.14	0.06	0.70	1055	283.82	621.74	20.44	0.14	0.82
977	726.46	609.48	19.15	0.09	0.66	988	726.60	609.86	19.97	0.13	0.83
981	575.31	549.40	19.17	0.33	0.73	747	575.27	548.39	19.07	0.14	0.87
983	641.78	491.36	19.18	0.21	0.71	843	641.72	491.04	19.46	0.13	0.89
985	347.77	934.74	19.19	0.32	0.66	1016	348.81	934.92	20.17	0.14	0.84

ID_K	Xpix	Ypix	K_s	σ_K	C_K	ID_J	Xpix	Ypix	J	σ_J	C_J
986	197.68	292.32	19.19	0.10	0.82	1002	197.76	291.88	20.08	0.15	0.81
989	573.42	456.26	19.21	0.32	0.70	1033	573.22	457.37	20.28	0.14	0.84
990	501.70	744.42	19.21	0.10	0.66	1061	501.57	743.47	20.56	0.15	0.89
995	227.41	768.77	19.21	0.05	0.70	955	226.86	768.45	19.81	0.13	0.84
997	416.25	797.02	19.23	0.06	0.71	896	416.04	796.00	19.63	0.13	0.91
999	393.96	760.55	19.24	0.08	0.81	913	393.68	759.71	19.70	0.13	0.82
1000	514.21	190.09	19.24	0.30	0.72	1012	513.27	190.35	20.14	0.13	0.91
1002	567.92	588.90	19.26	0.36	0.83	834	566.99	589.10	19.42	0.14	0.88
1009	293.95	756.55	19.30	0.05	0.70	1015	294.14	756.17	20.17	0.14	0.84
1012	724.36	620.80	19.31	0.10	0.69	1057	723.44	622.56	20.47	0.14	0.85
1016	637.57	221.26	19.34	0.23	0.70	1052	636.92	221.49	20.41	0.14	0.85
1019	494.25	632.68	19.36	0.29	0.67	792	493.49	632.17	19.25	0.13	0.93
1020	327.07	967.96	19.36	0.33	0.71	891	327.12	966.90	19.61	0.13	0.94
1021	230.98	423.03	19.36	0.22	0.69	1065	230.93	423.70	20.61	0.14	0.82
1027	717.65	426.03	19.40	0.08	0.66	1072	717.79	426.71	20.63	0.14	0.81
1030	467.65	365.99	19.42	0.29	0.75	971	466.86	366.38	19.89	0.15	0.85
1033	321.53	934.85	19.45	0.27	0.71	963	321.50	934.59	19.86	0.13	0.91
1034	104.54	444.06	19.45	0.12	0.72	734	103.46	443.60	19.04	0.13	0.92
1036	337.94	367.49	19.46	0.22	0.69	1018	337.64	367.29	20.19	0.14	0.83
1038	266.86	887.41	19.50	0.06	0.72	915	266.34	887.52	19.71	0.13	0.88
1039	95.24	959.23	19.50	0.15	0.67	1095	94.86	959.09	21.00	0.16	0.81

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